

ASSESSMENT OF RESOURCE UTILIZATION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILL DEVELOPMENT IN A KNOWLEDGE ECONOMY SOCIETY

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Abstract

The purpose of acquiring entrepreneurial skills is to secure a living or self-reliance using creative talent to establish a venture that will ensure and sustain growth of wealth in Acknowledge economy society. Therefore, universities have to adapt to the requirements imposed by the knowledge economy and to change their teaching process based on knowledge transfer into developing students' skills which will allow them to perform in a turbulent business environment. The paper focuses on resources utilization and entrepreneurial skills development in a knowledge economy society. The research was guided by four research question. The instrument designed to collect data was the structured questionnaire which was developed by the researcher and has only one section which was designed to elicit information that is related to the research questions. The title of the questionnaire is: Resource Utilization and Entrepreneurial Skill Development in a Knowledge Economy Society". The Mean and Standard Deviation and the bench mark to accept or disagree an item is 3.00. The target population consists of four hundred (400) respondents. The instrument was subjected to face validation by the two experts from the Department of Adult Education. The result from the study shows a significant relationship between resources utilization and all the four variables of entrepreneurial skills development (business startup skills, perception of business opportunities, risk taking behavior and networking skills adoption) considered in this study. Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations that emphasize on wealth creation, poverty reduction and youth's self-employment, the federal and state government should provide the enabling environment that will promote entrepreneurship by providing sufficient resources for learning in all level of tertiary education. Secondly, students should be encouraged to have interest in entrepreneurship education through enlightenment on career prospects and opportunities in general and many more.

Keywords: Resource Entrepreneurship, Knowledge, Economy and Society

Introduction

Entrepreneurial and technological revolutions transform the contemporary economy into what is called the "knowledge economy" (KE). In this economy, a new form of organizations and work govern the world of business, demanding the rapid development of skills, solid knowledge and greater responsibility. Contemporary society thus becomes a learning society adapting to the new, and in this context

educational systems must aim at the formation of people able to contribute to the development of their own competencies to integrate fully in the socio-cultural context in which they live (Cooke & Leydesdorff, 2006). Knowledge is the fuel of today's economy and it is the foundation of the renaissance of all countries. Foray (2004) stated that technologies have always been underpinned by knowledge, but an economy run on knowledge is characterized by a critical role for information and communication technology (ICT), a high proportion of knowledge-intensive activity and intangible capital that amounts to more than tangible capital economy's capital stock. The source of economic growth and value-added activities increasingly relies on knowledge (Stehr, 1994). A knowledge-based economy refers to one that focuses in production and management of knowledge (Cooke & Leydesdorff, 2006). The organization for economic co-operation and development (OECD) defines a country with a knowledge-based economy as one where "the production, diffusion and use of technology and information are keys to economic activity and sustainable growth" (OECD, 1999). Such an economy depends on the adaptive and creative thinking skills of individuals to come up with solutions from problem prevalent in their society. This shows that a "knowledge-based economy" and a "knowledge-society" are mutually interactive and positively correlated. Furthermore, it means that a knowledge-based economy depends on the human capital as the major source of new innovative ideas, which is enabled by the information and communication technology (ICT). It is thus an open-source economy of ideas intended to invent a future state for a better society and ultimately, a more sustainable world than the present state (OECD, 1996).

Knowledge is produced, transmitted and applied in all activities, including in the creation of goods and information services. The resultant products are then referred to as "knowledge products". Demand for such products is increasingly on the rise, causing considerable change in the structure of the global economy as well. In this case, management in all sectors of the economy needs to use knowledge to achieve competitive advantage. Accordingly, a knowledge-based economy utilizes knowledge as a major tool in amassing wealth, raising efficiencies, enhancing economic growth, and creating jobs. Besides the development of Knowledge products, some countries relate a knowledge-based economy to higher education and research (Powell & Snellman, 2004). According to the World Bank (2007, 2012), education and training represent one of the four fundamental pillars of knowledge economy, initially, many of the leading countries depend on the traditional resources, such as labor and capital, to create wealth and fuel economic growth. However, with globalization, emerging trends and technological advancement in the present highly dynamic economic environment, most of them have gradually shifted into the new economy, they capitalize on creating new knowledge and innovation and adapting new technology to drive their progress in economic growth. Basically, they have changed into knowledge-based economy (Goding, 2006). Knowledge is their greatest asset that places them in the lead, compared to other countries that are still in the transition stage or are lagging behind. Notwithstanding, in the past two decades, most of the latter have witnessed the benefits and have been convinced to have change. Nigeria is one of those countries that is enthusiastically transitioning to a knowledge-based economy, especially through university education and research. Present international practices, theories and experiences have proven the fact that the contemporary drivers of economic

development have changed. More specifically, they ascertain that knowledge is now a key factor in economic growth. A knowledge-based economy results in new and increased employment opportunities. This is because it requires a workforce that can run the highly dynamic trends efficiently. People with the required skills thus get jobs in the new high-technology industries and new sectors. Thus, a knowledge-based economy results in investment to develop a highly skilled labor force (Fernandez 2001). Research technological advancement and a highly skilled workforce translate to productivity gains and in turn boost economic growth and development.

According to Bratianu and Vatamanescu (2017, p. 419). “Generic skills, also known as core skills, key skills, essential skills, basic skills, soft skills, key competences, or employability skills are those capabilities which are liable to power personal and professional development based on learning.” They are essential for increasing the chances of employability of the actual students and future knowledge workers in a turbulent business environment. Entrepreneurial skills are part of these generic skills and they increase the students’ capacity of thinking critically in real business context, of making successful decisions and solving complex problems, of coming with new ideas in new situations, demonstrating originality skills and openness to learn from both successes and failures (Bedwell et al., 2014; Curtin, 2004; Gibbons-Wood and Lange, et al., 2016).

In developing countries such as Nigeria the economic landscape is changing with a move from foreign direct investment to self-employment and entrepreneurship. This is noted in the increase number of individuals considering self-employment as a career option due to the high rate of unemployment in those economies. The key to success of establishing a culture of entrepreneurship is education and training which depend on all the stakeholders, including the state, educators, and learners themselves. According to Arogundade (2011), entrepreneurship education and training entail philosophy of self-reliance such as creating a new cultural and productive environment, promoting new sets of attitudes and culture for the attainment of future challenges. The development of a country is determined by the way production forces in and around the economy is organized. This opinion is supported by Ogundele (2007) who argued that the promotion and the development of entrepreneurial activities would aid the dispersal and diversification of economic activities and induce even development in a knowledge economy society. Entrepreneurship remains the gateway to sustainable wealth creation in this knowledge economy society (Ogundele, 2000). In the views of Matanmiand Awodun (2005), if Nigeria desires to move out of the disturbing high level of unemployment and ravaging level of poverty, adequate attention must be given to the growth of entrepreneurship. They concluded that Nigeria still remains in the doldrums because of the combination of ignorance, low-capacity building and lack of encouragement of entrepreneurship. An entrepreneurial skill according to Olagunju (2004) is the ability of and individual to explore an idea and create an enterprise whether big or small not only for personal gain but also for social and developmental gain. Hisrich and Peters (2002) defined entrepreneurial skill as the ability to create something new with value by devoting the necessary time and effort, assuming the resulting rewards of monetary and personal satisfaction and independence. Entrepreneurial skills are acquired through training that emphasizes the acquisition and development of appropriate knowledge and skill that will enable an individual to maximize the

resources around him within the limit of his capability, learner develop competencies needed for firm career commitments such as setting up business, marketing, services or being productive, wealth creators, employers of labor and self-reliant thereby contributing in nation building. Currently, entrepreneurship skills are one key attributes for people if they want to successfully navigate the job market. Many employers prefer graduates with entrepreneurship experience when hiring for entry-level positions especially in this knowledge economy society. They consider these people to be more accountable for their own actions, have team work skills and know how to execute. Employees with entrepreneurship experience are also considered to have better communication and sales skills that are necessary to be successful in business today. It is also widely accepted that entrepreneurship can be learnt and a positive relationship can be found between universities levels and high levels of entrepreneurial activity (GEM, 2006). The rapid development of IT technology also provides many opportunities for learning entrepreneurship skills (Zufeng and Chuling, 2011), or for college students to start their own business (Chen et al., 2012). This entrepreneurship education can create a new earning culture that corresponds better with students' habits and interests and can provide the necessary support for effective skills, such as starting and operating an e shop or other online activity can bridge the distance between learning concepts presented in the classroom and skills needed to solve practical problems connected with e-business activities. (Matlay, 2008).

In the knowledge economy, intangible assets, such as knowledge and information management, become the new core of competencies. We are in a world where we are dealing with "cognitive domains", where ideas are worth billions, while products cost less. Continuing the parallel between traditional knowledge economy, knowledge economy calls for a rethinking of the theory of the factors of production in the sense that the traditional factors become secondary and knowledge becomes the essential component of the system of contemporary economic and social development. Creating, acquiring and effectively developing knowledge within an organization has become the core source of competitive advantage. Organizations that use their knowledge as a source of competitive advantage are called "learning organizations" as a Traditional production factor. A knowledge-based organization can inspire a new entrepreneurial spirit and motivate managers to be concerned about transforming the organization into an organization capable of capturing, applying and developing value as a result of the implementation of performing technologies.

According to the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) (2007), utilization of educational resources is very crucial for effective living in the modern economy. Given its application to industry and personal development of students and every works of life, these resources are designed to build confidence in students and enhance their abilities to adapt to the changing situations in scientific and technologically oriented society. Nwosu and Nwaocha (2004) had argued that the utility and durability of educationally acquired skills, their consolidation and possible improvement will depend on their continued experimentation, testing and retesting on the facts of life. Hence, students graduating from the Nigerian education system should be able to transfer the knowledge and skills they have acquired using resources in their various institutions to solving their daily problems. It is however, sad to discover that many university graduates are unable to be self-reliant and useful to the society in which

they live. The implication is that the education system has failed to build in the graduates with the requisite skills and competencies for effective living as members of the wider society. This factor accounts for growing number of unemployed youths roaming the streets of Nigeria, especially university graduates. It is worrisome to see these able-bodied young men and women at such places as motor parks, busy road junctions and bus stops and some other socially deprived areas. These youths are easily recruited as touts, party and election thugs, cults, armed robbers among others. The inability of university graduates to be gainfully employed worsen the biting unemployment situation in the country. The sight of these hordes of unemployed graduates has continued to generate varied concerns over the failure of the education system to avail them appropriate entrepreneurial skills to enable them become entrepreneurs. Supporting the view that the university graduates from Nigerian education system should be well equipped with an appropriate entrepreneurial, scientific and technological knowledge and skills that will empower them economically for survival in our modern age of science technology is very apt. The best and easiest way of achieving this through acquisition of entrepreneurial skills and utilization of necessary resources embedded in the university curriculum. The marriage between curriculum and utilization of resources in higher education will lead to sound education and future massive production of wealth (case, 2005). The knowledge and skills acquire through this process could be of value by helping them to develop entrepreneurial skills. Okoli and Onwuachu (2009), posited that exposing students to entrepreneurial skills through practical lessons could enable them acquire skills to develop the capacity for critical thinking, generated ideas; and be able to repair and /or service the economy by setting up new business and improving the already existing business in diverse areas hence reducing the so much dependency on government jobs. In other to close this missing link, Oludipe and Lasis (2006) stated that for effective entrepreneurial skill acquisition to occur, provision and utilization of resources which enhance entrepreneurial education are vital.

State of the Problem

The world economy is experiencing the effects of rapid entrepreneurial as well as the impact of the emerging information age. The prediction is that this information age will bring about a new global economic order to be dominated by information and knowledge-based societies. Most African countries including Nigeria are facing new challenges to their socioeconomic development process as a result of this, globalization process and the impact of the emerging new information age is the order. There is no doubt that the information and knowledge-based economy of the future and the challenge facing Nigeria relate to how they should go about policies and entrepreneurial skills that could aid the process of moving their countries to the other side of the digital divide.

In this knowledge economy society, entrepreneurial skills play an important role in the socio-economic development as well as empowerment of the youth. Its significance can be seen in terms of contributions towards economic growth, employment creation, wealth generation, income redistribution and poverty alleviation, as well as for rapid economy development prosperity and a source for facilitating global competitiveness. In spite of this insignificance, it is evident that the rate of

unemployment among youths in Nigeria has been one of the biggest challenges confronting the development of the nation. This is because of the fact that, the number of unemployed youths every year keeps on increasing at a phenomenon that needs to be addressed urgently. This is evident through the statistics of unemployment rate in the country as stated by the National Bureau of Statistics (2016). The bureau stated its latest unemployment watch report between December 2015 and March 2016, the population of unemployed Nigerians increased by 518,000 to over 1.45 million. The need to avert the negative effects of unemployment and to improve labor productivity in this knowledge economy society will make the tackling of unemployment the problem to feature prominently in the development of the Nigerian government. An early intervention in terms of coming up with tangible findings that would enable initiation of appropriate guidelines to improve entrepreneurship is very crucial. If the rate of unemployment is not addressed properly and promptly most especially with the new society, the opportunities that would have been otherwise available for the youth to advance in the society might be closed.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine:

1. The influence between resource utilization and opportunity to enhance knowledge economy society.
2. The influence between resource utilization and business startup skills for the advancement of the knowledge economy society.
3. The influence between resource utilization and risk-taking behavior in then knowledge economy society.
4. The influence between resource utilization and networking skills in the knowledge

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study:

1. There is no significant influence between resource utilization and opportunity to enhance knowledge economy society.
2. Resource utilization will not significantly influence business startup skills for the advancement of the knowledge economy society.
3. There is no significant influence between resource utilization and risk taking behavior in the knowledge economy society.
4. Resource utilization will not significantly influence the adoption of networking skills in the knowledge economy society.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between resource utilization and opportunity to enhance knowledge economy society.

Table 1: Chi-square Test of influence between resource utilization and opportunity to enhance knowledge economy society

Response	Observed	Expected	Residual	X ² Cal	Df	p-value
Category	N	N				
1	46	99.3	-17.8	40.532	3	0.000
2	106	99.3	28.8			
3	128	99.3	6.8			
4	117	99.0	-55.3			
Total	397					

X² is significant at p>0.05 (1= Strongly Disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Agree, 4= strongly Agree)

The result from the table indicates a significant influence between resource utilization and opportunities to enhance knowledge economy society since X² Cal = 40.532, at p= 0.000>0.05 given degree of freedom. Thus the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant influence between resource utilization and opportunity to enhance knowledge economy society was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was retained.

Hypotheses Two: Resource utilization will not significantly influence business startup skills for the advancement of the knowledge economy society.

Table 2: Chi-square test of the nexus between resource utilization and business startup skills for the advancement of the knowledge economy society

Response	Observed	Expected	Residual	X ² Cal	Df	p-value
Category	N	N				
1	53	99.3	33.1	68.942*	3	0.000
2	140	99.3	37.8			
3	141	99.3	42.8			
4	63	99.0	-49.3			
Total	397					

X² significant at p>0.05 (1= Strongly Disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Agree, 4= strongly Agree).

The result from the table indicates a significant influence between resource utilization and business startup skills since X² Cal =68.429, at p= 0.000>0.05 given 3 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypotheses that states there is no significant influence between resource utilization and startup business skills was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was retained.

Hypothesis three: There is no significant relationship between resource utilization and risk-taking behavior in the knowledge economy society.

Table 3: Chi-square test of influence between resource utilization and risk-taking behavior in the knowledge economy;

Response	Observed	Expected	Residual	X ² Cal	Df	p-value
Category	N	N				
1	59	99.3	26			
2	112	99.3	4	85.266*	3	0.000
3	102	99.3	14			
4	124	99.0	-44			
Total	397					

X² is significant at $p > 0.05$ (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = strongly Agree)

The result from the table indicates a significant influence between resources utilization and risk-taking behavior skills since X^2 Cal 85.226*, at $p = 0.0000 > 0.05$ given degree of freedom. Thus, null hypotheses states that there is no significant relationship between resource utilization and risk-taking behavior was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was retained.

Hypothesis four: Resource utilization will not significantly influence the adoption of networking skills in the knowledge economy society.

Table 4: Chi-square test of influence between resource utilization and networking skills in the knowledge economy society

Response	Observed	Expected	Residual	X ² Cal	Df	p-value
Category	N	N				
1	26	99.3	-24.0			
2	115	99.3	-4.0	28.816*	3	0.000
3	117	99.3	34.0			
4	119	99.0	-6.0			
Total	397					

X² is significant at $p > 0.05$ (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = strongly Agree)

The result from the table indicates a significant relationship between resource utilization and adoption of networking skills was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was retained.

Discussion of Findings

Entrepreneurship has long been part of human survival story. It has recently been pushed forward again out of Economical challenges of new millennium both in first and third world countries. Prospective leaders of next generation of organizations need to be even more entrepreneurs. That is why university education must be transformed so as to be able to meet the needs of upcoming job markets. This enquiry asks the most

important players of an educational system, meaning its educators what must be done to guarantee future university graduates' high quality entrepreneurial skills. Factors underlying respondents' opinions on how to transform current universities into effective supplier of future entrepreneurs were explored to be student's orientation, career education and curriculum revitalization using a factor analysis approach. Results were supported by brown (2003), Chambers (2003) and Beyers (20001). It can be concluded here that academic staff as leverage point of any transformation must be retained in workshops such as: creative teaching techniques, entrepreneur and entrepreneurs brainstorming and incubating ideas. Adding entrepreneurship concepts and theories into current curriculum is necessary as the first step towards a systematic incorporation of entrepreneurial skills into the whole educational system and eventual transformation of the institution.

One study suggested that courses should be sponsored by existing entrepreneurs (Akpomi, 2008). Result from the study shows a significant influence between resource utilization and all the four variables of entrepreneurial skills development (business startup skills, perception of business opportunities, risk taking behavior and networking skills adoption) considered in this study. This contrast with others studies that adult education students entering the labor force lack these skills. The finding however in tune with the position of Johnson and burden (2003) who reported that adult education graduates entering the labor market recognized that the world of work sought entrepreneurial skills such as the ability to see business opportunities and opportunities and communicate it well, show initiative take business risk; and understood that qualifications alone were not adequate to secure good employment. The findings negates the position of Lloyd (2012) in which he decried non application of entrepreneurial skills acquired by university graduate in wealth creation. Although there is inherent relationship between resource utilization and entrepreneurial skill development as evidence from study however the stake reality is that this relationship has failed to transform in real wealth creation due to poor applications of resources in the educational system which apparently explains the increasing rate of unemployment amongst the graduates in the country. The position that was supported by Ajala (2002) and Babafemi (2007), in which they described the Nigerian education system as laudable but seem to suffer from poor implementation. Entrepreneurial skills development can only be meaningful and effective if back up by the necessary resources to enrich the instruction.

Conclusion

Resource utilization in education setting is related to skills development, problem-solving ability, discipline, motivation and self-confidence for people in the knowledge economy society. There seems to be agreement that attaining a high level of education positively influences the probability of becoming involved in wealth creation, however no utilization of resource in educational setting has hampered full development of productive entrepreneurship culture among our youths. There is need for various stakeholders, academic and training institutions to structure their entrepreneurship programmes as well as focus on partnership venture to expose students the needed skills for wealth creation especially in this knowledge economy society.

Recommendations

- Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:
- i. With the current emphasis on wealth creation, poverty reduction and youth's self-employment, the federal and state government should provide the enabling environment that will promote entrepreneurship by providing sufficient resources for learning in all level of tertiary education. There is urgent need to beef up resources needed for entrepreneurial education in the country especially human resources, workshop equipment and power supply, so that the interest of the existing young and prospective entrepreneurs could be sustained.
 - ii. Students should be encouraged to have interest in entrepreneurship education through enlightenment on career prospects and opportunities in general. There is need to change the mind-set of prospective distanced education students to see self-employment as an option. This will awaken their desire, and motivate them into identifying career opportunities available to them after school. To this end, entrepreneurship education shall be the fulcrum of teaching-learning and process.
 - iii. Management should formulate policies that will encourage high deployment of resources in open distance universities across Nigeria. Such policy should include provision of necessary infrastructure, provision of the needed manpower and other incentive for development of self –reliant entrepreneurs.
 - iv. Schools and their management should be made to be aware that students will acquire skills, only when they are exposed to regular workshop practice, with adequate resources. These measures will concretize teaching and learning and make learning to be permanent in the students.

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QUALITY SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT: CHALLENGES AND WAY FORWARD

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Abstract

Quality Science and Technology Education (STE) have been seen as instruments for the development of any nation. STE enables us to develop and produce relevant manpower needed for the reduction of graduate unemployment thereby, enhancing standard of living. STE have been found to have positive relationship with the development of nation. This paper highlighted the indicators of quality Science and Technology Education. Science and Technology Education for national development was also discussed. The main challenges to science and technology education in Nigeria were also examined. It was concluded that Science and Technology Education holds the key to national development. Recommendations such as adequate funding of science and technology education by governments, adequate and relevant materials should be supplied to our school laboratories so as to discourage the use of alternative to practicals among others were made.

Key words: Quality, Science, Technology, Education, National Development.

Introduction

Science and Technology Education has been seen as basis for national development. It enables us to produce and develop different manpower that are needed for the development of a nation. The contribution of science and technology education as an enabler for sustainable national economic development was affirmed at the world summit on sustainable development (WSSD) in 2002. According to David, Dallatu and Yusuf (2018), it is in this regard that in the framework of the New Partnership for African's Development (NEPAD), African leaders recognized that science and technology will play a major role in the economic transformation and sustainable development of any nation. STE has been an instrument for enhancing both the standard

of living and the economy of any nation. Developed nation such as USA, China, Japan and UK are not unconnected to the type of science and technology available to them (Wasagu, 2019).

There is a great link between quality science and technology, education and national development. Quality science and technology education is a base for the development of any nation. According to Pigozzi (2008) in Thom-Otuya and Inko-tariah (2016), quality science and technology education understands the past, is relevant to the present, and has a view to the future, it relates to knowledge building and the skillful applications of a forms of knowledge. Quality science and technology education is responsible for the transformation of a nation to a greater height. To Sulai, Sulai and Kaluri (2018), science is defined as an intellectual activity carried out by human, designed to discover the ways in which information can be organized to benefit human race, while technology is viewed as the application of knowledge for nation development and improvement of human life; it is about product and process.

Zakariya and Bello (2018) view technology as the application of knowledge obtained from scientific discoveries for development and improvement of human life. It is science of mechanical and industrial arts which involves applications of science in solving human problems that can bring in development (Suleiman, Fagbemi, Oyebani and Suleiman, 2018). Quality Science and Technology Education is therefore the skill developer, and skills built up viable economy that consequently brings about the development of any nation. Quality Science and Technology Education lends to economic and national development. It affects peoples' life styles as it helps to transform raw resources into goods and services for better quality of life. According to Ideozu (2018), advanced economics need a continuous training of qualified scientists and technologists that are critical in driving the innovations which in turn have a critical role in the growth of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of any country. As pointed out by Ideozu (2018), innovation is mostly as a result of advance in quality science and technology education disciplines and as such, a rise in employment at all levels requiring STE skills, which triggered economic growth. Quality science and technology education produces scientifically and technologically literate citizens that can help to promote all round development of basic skills and the effective use of these skills in the development of the nation.

Indicators of Quality Science and Technology Education

Quality Science and Technology Education of any country depends on her needs. Quality in science and technology education is inclusive and strives to ensure that all learners are reached irrespective of their situation (Thom-Otuya, et al., 2016). According to them, a quality science and technology education should have the following indices:

- i. Adequate funding
- ii. Conducive and appropriate teaching and learning environment
- iii. A well-equipped standard laboratory
- iv. Effective quality control that helps to enforce standard
- v. Adequate and standard facilities for teaching and learning
- vi. Good quality and well-motivated staff.

Quality education as applicable to science and technology education according to UNICEF (2000) is characterized by;

- i. Learners who are healthy, well-nourished and ready to participate and learn, and supported in learning by their families and communities.
- ii. Environments that are healthy, safe, protective and gender-sensitive and provide adequate resources and facilities.
- iii. Content that is reflected in relevant curricula and materials or the acquisition of basics skills, especially in the area of literacy, numeracy and skills for life, and knowledge in such areas as gender, health, nutrition, HIV/Aids prevention and peace.
- iv. Processes through which trained teachers use child-centered teaching approaches in well-managed classrooms and schools and skillful assessment to facilitate learning and reduce disparities.
- v. Outcomes that encompass knowledge, skills and attitudes and are linked to national goals for education and positive participation in society.

However, some of the indicators of quality science and technology education according to Obasi (2010), are:

- i. Effective and efficient performance of graduates' society, industries, and other work places.
- ii. Employability (self, national and international of products/graduates (entrepreneurship level)/graduate employment statistics.
- iii. National and International mobility of generated manpower.
- iv. Market value or demand level of research products and other services provided by the institutions.
- v. International transferability/admissibility of graduates/students for higher studies without remedial conditions.
- vi. Level of discipline and patriotism of graduates.
- vii. High rating of an institution and its products nationally and internationally.

From the items above, one can see that the products of science and technology education are needed for national development. Hence, the saying that “no nation can develop beyond its science and technology education system” still remains.

Quality Science and Technology Education for National Development

Quality science and technology education is the base of any national development. Every part of human life is affected by the quality of science and technology education of our nation. Quality STE helps people to develop skills that can help to solve problems encountered on a day to day basis. Quality science and technology education is the appropriate education that can lead to the desired development of any nation.

National development according to Obasi (2010), is the social process by which a nation harnesses and mobilizes all resources (human and material) available to it for the purpose of positively transferring its environment. National development is then not only an economic exercise but involves both socio-economic exercise of societal life. For the development of any nation, the development of individuals within the society must be considered.

Development is generally perceived as social transformation of the society, projected to bring economic, social and material improvement in the life of the majority of the people with a view to gaining control over the environment (Sulai and Sulai and Kaluri, 2018). Development can also be seen as both scientific, technological and economic growth. As pointed out by David, Dallatu and Yusuf (2018), development is improvement in way of doing things, living standard, equipment, facilities, etc. This implies positive change that will enable us to meet with the demand of the changing world. According to the Longman Active Study Dictionary (New, (Ed) 2016), development can be seen as the collective activities by any human society directed at reducing any perceived obstacles to a higher standard of living and consequently maximizing the quality of life of the citizens. Development is therefore the growth integrated with economic, scientific, political and home-based technological expansion. Chalse-Ogan and Agomuo (2017), itemized the elements of developed nation to include; high standard of living, high agricultural productivity, high technological productivity, adequate exploration of the natural and mineral resources of society, less dependent on imported materials, presence of heavy industries, high literacy and numeracy rate of the citizens appropriate health care delivery and low unemployment. According to Obasi (2010), development may be defined as the collective activities by any human society directed at reducing the totality of perceived obstacles to a higher standard of living, thus, maximizing the quality of life of the society.

The development of any nation to a large extent depends on the development of individuals within the society. Since the knowledge, skills and competencies of human resources determine the level of wealth and development of any nation. The development of any nation is basically based on manpower development in terms of knowledge, skills and competencies and manpower development depends on the type of education acquired. Appropriate type of education contributes to the economic growth of any nation through manpower development that involves the acquisition of appropriate knowledge and skills. The type of education that enhances the desired development of any nation is the Science and Technology Education (STE).

Science and Technology Education produces scientifically and technologically literate citizens. Science and technology education has been the basis for the development of nations. STE affects people's lifestyles as it enhances any nation's ability to manufacture better and qualitative products that can help to improve health care services, preserve the environment and growth in economy. According to Izeodu (2018), advanced economic growth needs a continuous training of scientists and engineers who are critical in driving innovations and in turn have a crucial role in the growth of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of countries.

Quality Science and Technology Education had been the critical instruments used to uplift both the standard of living and economy of any nation. Developed nations such as USA, China, Japan and United Kingdom are not unconnected to the type of science and technology education available to them (Wasagu, 2019). He noted that STE is important in meeting societal needs like food, shelter, clothing, defense and security, governance, etc. Industrial developments around us depend on the applications of the principles of basic science and technology for its supply of innovations, which consequently leads to nation development through improved industrial products. With quality science and technology education, a nation can rise above over-dependence on

developed nations' technological prowess. The knowledge of science and technology education lends to economic and national development. The knowledge, skills and competences in STE affects people's lifestyles as it helps to transform raw resources into goods and services for better quality of life. (Suleiman, et. al., 2018). According to Ideogu (2018), quality Science and Technology Education is central to any nation's ability to manufacture better and qualitative products that can help to improve healthcare services and technology education produces scientifically and technologically literate citizens. It also promotes all round development of basic skills and the effective use of these skills in the development of the individuals and the society and the nation at large.

One of the theories of science and technology education and economic development is the Human capital theory. This theory emphasizes how increased demand for science and technology education leads to increase in the productivity and efficiency of workers through increased levels of cognitive and psychomotor skills possessed by the workforce. The relation between science and technology education and national development continues to be a question of critical concern in many countries.

As earlier pointed out by Wasagu (2019), the giant strides made by developed countries such as the USA, Japan and China are not unconnected to the type of science and technology education available in those countries. In recognition that science and technology are important for national development underscores the minimum needs of human societies. Such needs are food, shelter, clothing, water, energy, employment, basic education and healthcare. Without science and synergistically related disciplines, technology, development in these sectors is nowhere (Wasagu, 2013). A laudable national development will remain elusive if the challenges facing science and technology education in Nigeria are not adequately addressed.

Challenges to Science and Technology Education (STE) in Nigeria

The quality of science and technology delivery in Nigeria is not satisfactory. It has been criticized of poor quality, the training not suitable to our social economic situation, disregards of labour market, disregards of the needs of the society and high unemployment rate. Financing education in Nigeria is far below the UNESCO's recommendation that at least 26% of national budget should go to education.

In an increasing global economy, we need to evaluate ourselves to know how much we are performing and also to know if we are keeping up with the rest of the world. In paving with the rest of the world, it is important to reexamine the impact of globalization and its implications to our science and technology education. For instance, the G-8 countries represent 14% of the world population but because of the advancement in science and technology education, they account for 65% of the world economic output measured by GDP, UK is 1% of the world population but produces 10% of the world scientific research (Wasagu, 2013). Akpan (2009) in Wasagu (2013), pointed out that four of the G-8 countries, i.e. UK, USA, France and Russia account for 96% of the world nuclear weapons as well as 72% of the total military expenditure. These are some of the challenges to us to tackle in the course of using STE to develop our nation.

Other challenges to science and technology education in Nigeria are:

- The reification of science and technology subjects of difficult subjects.
- Lack of qualified and competent science and technology teachers.
- Nigeria government is rhetorically promoting science and technology education as engines of development but is not investing in it.
- Use of outdated curriculum and training facilities that results in a wide gap between what is taught and the needs of the labour market.
- Accessibility of laboratory equipment. There is disconnect between theory and practice among our students because most of our schools lack basic laboratory equipment.
- Poor learning outcomes due to poor learning environment.
- Inadequate teacher preparation and therefore questionable pedagogy.
- Heavy reliance on imported technology and manufactured goods.

Conclusion

The state of science and technology education needs drastic measures if it must serve as reliable and efficient base for the attainment of national development. The development of Nigeria lies in the productivity of its citizens. Quality science and technology education hold the key. The rate of high unemployment, lack of effective and efficient performance of graduate in society, industries, and other work places are indications of underdeveloped science and technology education. If Nigeria is to develop both scientifically and technologically so as to meet the demands of global world, governments should properly fund STE and build up the capacity of STE teachers.

Recommendations/Way forward

Sequel to the conclusion above, the following way forward is made:

1. If we are to develop both scientifically and technologically so as to meet the demands of the global world, the governments should properly fund science and technology education and build the capacity of STE teachers.
2. Changes in economic competitiveness are creating increasing demand for science and technology education. Our science and technology curricular should therefore change to reflect the skills required in modern market.
3. We need to develop in our youth the skills of participation and responsibility. Emphasis should be placed on training teachers that are well grounded in the subject matter of STE to teach at primary, secondary and tertiary levels of education.
4. The inadequate provision of science and technology resources – laboratory facilities, equipment, textbooks, workshops and supplies that hamper the effective teaching and learning of STE should be addressed.
5. Experiments of STE should be in our schools are still analog. There should be efforts to make a breakthrough. The concept of alternative to practicals should be discouraged in our schools. Relevant materials should be supplied.
6. There is need to improve on the quality of science and technology education teaching in our schools so that learners can gain knowledge, skills and competencies needed for the gradual but lasting national development.

7. Governments should avail the general populace with sound STE so that national development can be achieved.

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MANAGING ORGANISATIONAL CLIMATE FOR SAFETY, SECURITY AND SUSTAINABLE NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UMUAHIA NORTH LGA OF ABIA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigated managing organizational climate for safety and security and sustainable national development in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State. Four research questions guided the study. The study employed a descriptive survey design involving 130 respondents. This sample size was drawn using a simple random sampling technique. Two instruments were used to elicit responses from the respondents namely; Checklist and Questionnaire on Organizational Climate Safety and Security Management in Public Secondary Schools (QOCSSMPSS). Research questions 1 and 2 were answered using frequency and percentage while mean and standard deviation were used to analyze research question 3 and 4. The findings revealed among others that organizational climate determines the safety and security of the school and the attainment of educational goals and objectives at a very high extent, some security devices for the improvement of security situations as well as the emergency response plans for managing security in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA are not adequately available. The respondents agreed on the adequacy of all the 9 items on security measures that should be adopted in managing school plants. Based on the findings and the educational implications, it was recommended among others that the school administration should provide a healthy organizational climate to ensure a conducive teaching and learning environment for sustainable national development; school management should provide clear and appropriate measures for managing safety and security of secondary schools and the provision of intervention funds by the government to school management

Keywords: Secondary school, Safety and Security, Organizational climate, School Management, Sustainable National Development.

Introduction

Education is an essential ingredient which an individual or a nation can never neglect. The indispensability nature of education is such that it helps to shape individual's behaviours and makes them worthwhile citizens of their country. Education allows individuals live peacefully with one another (Isiozor, 2019). Isiozor further states that this process serves as a fulcrum towards which a country can be devoid of nefarious acts such as conflicts, crime, kidnapping, or hostage taking etc. Anyaogu (2016) in Isiozor (2019) see education as the eye, the way and the means of development of any nation. It is through education that an individual masters his environment and acquires the necessary equipment for living a worthwhile life. Secondary education occupies a very unique position in the educational system in Nigeria, because it is that level that determines the academic and professional career of students (Isiozor, 2019). Anyaogu (2016) in Isiozor (2019) noted that secondary education is the education children receive after primary education and before the tertiary level.

According to Federal Government of Nigeria (2013), the broad aims of secondary education within the overall objectives are preparing students for useful living within the society and preparing them for higher education. Precisely, the aim of secondary education is to provide opportunity for qualitative education for primary school leavers, cater for the differences in talents of the pupils, develop Nigeria cultural heritage, produce a generation of people who respect the dignity of labour, foster Nigeria's unity and to inspire its students with the desire for achievement and self-improvement both at school and in later life (Isiozor, 2019). She further states that only the provision of qualitative education can guarantee the accomplishment of the secondary education goals. Basil-Uchegbu, Anyakoha, and Uchegbu (2021) opine that moving towards sustainability in national productivity is a social challenge that entails international and national laws, planning, supply chain management, cooperate and individual lifestyles. Wlheris and Milling (2001) in Basil-Uchegbu et al (2021) define sustainability as the process of people maintaining change in a balanced environment, in which the exploitation of resources, the direction of investments, the orientation of technological development and institutional change are all in harmony and enhance both current and future potentials to meet human needs and aspirations. Supporting the above assertion, Basil-Uchegbu *et al* (2021) state that it is a call to action, a task in progress or journey and therefore a political process set out for common goals. Hence, sustainable national productivity (development) is a call to maintain a production process that aims to meet, raise and maintain living standards— economically, politically, educationally, technological without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet, their own needs. According to Iwe (2022), safe-guarding the academic environment for educational activities is very important. he further states that “no safe school, no future for the world”. This assertion was further explained as follows:

- The dream of harnessing the power of education for achieving goals in health, food, employment, enrolment, energy, security will come to naught.
- Without safe school, education for all will remain a pipe dream.
- Quality education yearned by all countries of the world will be hindered.

The ability to control and coordinate human and material resources in an organization goes a long way to determine the environmental atmosphere which as well determines the productivity of such organization.

Safe school has been described as an environment that is not dangerous and possesses no threats to physical, emotional, psychosocial and psychological well-being of the occupants. In order words, it is an environment that is secured and free from threat and danger (Iwe, 2022). The concept of “security and safety”, according to Borkowski (2000) in Gawlik-Kobylnska (2021), refers to individuals or groups. Its understanding is considered as a state – giving a sense of confidence and guaranteeing its behavior and a chance for improvement; it means no risk of losing something, e.g., health, material goods, respect, feelings. According to Safeopedia (2021) in Mubita (2021) safety is a concept that includes all measures and practices taken to preserve the life, health, and bodily integrity of individuals. Safety is the condition of being protected from harm or other non-desirable outcomes. Security is generally agreed to be about feeling of being safe from harm, fear, anxiety, oppression, danger, poverty, defense, protection and preservation of core values and threat to those values. Safe and Sound School (2014) in Mubita (2021) looked at safety in terms of school communities and explains as follows: “safety” is a global term, used to describe our efforts to keep the school community and environment safe. Safety is an “umbrella term” for the many types of issues and/or crises a school community addresses in order to ensure the overall wellness of its members. Examples of such safety issues are health, mental wellness, school climate, fire safety, weather safety, building security, dangerous persons, bullying, environmental disaster, crime in the community, and bus and traffic safety (Safe and Sound School, 2014). A place where there is security is a place of safety (Trump, 2010) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017). Maslow (1998) in Gawlik-Kobylnska (2021) defines safety as a basic human need, without which it is impossible to function and develop properly.

Organizational climate counts as a key factor that affects school productivity. It should be noted that in terms of organizational climate, concentration is placed on these five dimensions, which are leadership, motivation, communication, decision making and job satisfaction as they determine the school productivity (Agbajeola, 2019). Ajayi and Mandakini (2013) in Njoku and Modebelu (2019), defined organizational climate as the formal system of tasks and reporting relationships that control, coordinate, and motivate employees that they cooperate to achieve an organizational goal. In secondary schools, positive school organizational climate is recognized as an important target for school reform, improved behaviour of students and teachers’ good academic performance. According to Nicholson and Miljus in Adenike (2011), organizational climate includes management or leadership style, participation in decision making, provision of challenging jobs to employee, reduction of boredom and frustration, provision of good working condition and creation of suitable career ladder for academics. Timpe in Ngadiman and Rotmawati (2013) expresses the following six indicators: responsibility, coordination, work team, respect, work standard and clarity as determinants of organizational climate. School organizational climate is an important and all-embracing characteristic of the school environment that includes the psychological, social and physical factors. The psychological factors relate to the feelings, attitudes and values exhibitions of the stakeholders of the school –

administrators (principals), teachers, staff, students, parents, government agencies and the society. Social factors include the nature of the interactions, communications and group activities of the stakeholders and the physical factors are the tangible aspects of the environment such as the nature of the buildings, classroom conditions, laboratories and other educational materials (Oborah, 2009). Research has shown that when examining the causes of school security threats, it is important to take into account the school climate. Merrow (2004) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) posits that schools that have positive school climate have been associated with fewer behavioural and emotional problems for students. Additionally, specific researches on school climate indicate that a positive supportive, culturally conscious school climate can significantly shape the degree of academic success in schools (Trump, 2010) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017). Certainly, the principal as the head of an institution occupies a pivotal position that requires initiatives and skills for the day-to-day administration of secondary school.

Management is a vital function of school administration. The school principal has to plan, organize, direct, control and evaluate the staff and material resources to achieve the objectives of the school. Management is viewed as the coordination of all the resources of an organization, through the process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling in order to attain organizational goal (Ogunu (2009) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017). Graffin (2003) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) sees management as a set of functions directed at the efficient and effective utilization of resources in the pursuit of organizational goals. In school, management is the identification of the organization's objectives, mobilizing the people and material resources such as funds, equipment and facilities in the school to achieve school objectives. The management of safety and security is paramount to the effective management of schools. It is an issue that has attracted a great deal of attention and concern from learners, educators, teachers, parents, and the public at large. According to McGuire (2017) in Mubita (2021), the primary indicator of a safe school is the existence of a plan in the school policy meant to address situations that may be a threat to learners and staff need a safe and supportive school environment in order to succeed. Morrison (2007) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) asserted that like all other activities in the school, the safety and security of learners cannot be dealt with separately for specific occasions or purposes on an ad-hoc basis. It should be managed and be interwoven with all routine of school administration functions.

School leadership and management style are also important factors, which can either motivate or lower teachers' morale and commitment. Uwazurike and Ugoji (2022) asserted that leadership implies some power and personal characteristics and ability to get things done through the assistance and cooperation of the people within the organization and institution. The success of an organization depends on the quality of its leadership, as a leader inspires, motivates and direct the activities and actions of other members of the organization towards achieving the organizational goals and objectives. According to Aderalegbe (1974) in Uwazurike and Ugoji (2022), effective communication can greatly enhance staff morale, job satisfaction as well as improve instructional techniques which in effect, will put the school and the leader in the right direction. According to Achunine (2022), the principal is responsible for providing dynamic leadership to the school. The implication of this is that effective leadership

must be consonant with the situation, the nature of the problem and the characteristics of the members of the organization. Democratic leadership or participative management characterized by supportive relationship is more likely to work for the schools. Democratic administration in schools, according to Achunine (2022) entails utilization of committees and advisory councils, emphasizing teacher participation in policy formulation and group decision-making. He further states that the principal should see himself as an administrator and as a leader. As an administrator, he performs the function of overseeing operations, providing supervision to ensure that objectives are met. As a leader, he points the direction, inspires and encourages. The leader serves as a catalyst and as a control agent.

Duze and Ogba (2013) asserted that overseeing a safe and orderly school environment with active support for teachers on disciplinary issues is one of the managerial skills of a school principal. Nakpodia in Onyali (2014) sees discipline as training that develops self-control, character orderliness and efficiency. Ebenezer in Ibiam (2015), asserted that with reference to the school system, we speak of discipline when students are taught to respect school authorities, to observe school laws and regulations and to maintain an established standard of behaviours. Indiscipline according to Ezegebe in Onwurah (2004) denotes some forms of disorder which arises from a negation of the established rules and regulations, laid down procedures and patterns of normal behaviour in the conduct of human activities. Onyali (2014) reveals that in the school system, indiscipline connotes fighting, stealing, rioting, disobedience, examination malpractice, truancy, drug abuse etc. Onyali further asserted that discipline problems may emanate from the principal, the school, tutorial and non-tutorial staff, the students, the home and the society. No matter the area students' disruptive behaviours emanate, it has been observed that this aspect of school administration cannot be joked with. Therefore, every school administrator that desires to achieve educational goals through effective teaching/learning should be conversant with the causes of students' indiscipline and also, know how to manage the situation to achieve a safe and effective teaching and learning environment (Agoha, 2020). Trump (2010) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) warns that if learners do not feel safe to learn and teachers do not feel safe to teach, the focus shifts from academic task to discipline and personal safety.

According to Uwazurike (2022), administrators who foster good relationship with staff under them often times motivate them to record high productivity at work as well as a willing identification with administration. There is need for the administrator to show respect to staff, being trusting, considerate, showing modesty, sincerity and kind to all staff. He further states that when staff accept the administrator, co-operation with his policies and style of administration is assured often times (Uwazurike, 2022). Pepple (2016) is of the view that a good interpersonal relationship among workers is the key for achieving organizational goals and objectives. Ogbu (2010) reveals that the interaction between principals and teachers, among teachers and between teachers and students constitutes the main intercourse in the success and failure of educational enterprises

According to Nnabuo (2022), the school executive can relate effectively to the community by making the school 'open' operation. Duze and Ogba (2013) note that where school leaders promote effective school-family-community partnerships, they support students' learning, achievement and health development since families and

community members see the school strength, weakness and needs. Agbaja in Ogundele, Oparinda & Oyewale (2012) asserted that active community participations enhance effective school administration, that involvement of parent in decision making process of the school bring about school discipline, development of school facilities, teachers job performance and student academic performance.

Carter (2001) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) opines that school safety requires a broad-based effort by the entire community, including government, students, parents, law enforcement agencies, businesses, and faith-based organizations, among others. Carter stated that the government can help to ensure safe school by organizing periodic threat assessment in schools, creating school-wide prevention and intervention strategies, making school policies and legal issues supporting safe schools, implementing ongoing staff development to enhance safe schools ensuring quality school facilities and security technologies, fostering school, family, and community involvement and acquiring resources to enhance and sustain a safe learning environment. Ogunu (2009) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) asserted that government can ensure the safety and security of school through employment of personnel that will take charge of safety and security in schools, organizing periodic workshops on safety and security issues for school administrators, mobilizing civil society organizations to become active members of the school community police, provision/financing the procurement of safety and security equipment.

Modebelu (2019), categorized school organizational climate that can influence teachers' and students' performance into six such as open, close, autonomous, controlled, paternal and familiar climates. Eneasator in Adeyemi (2008) asserted that open school climate stands out as the best among the types of school climate, because it ensures that both the organizational goals and the group members' needs are satisfied, thereby resulting to high motivated and committed teachers.

Problem of the Study

The school administration is faced with the task of promoting and providing a supportive learning environment in which all learners and every member of school community are expected to feel safe and secured. There appear to be security threats across secondary schools in several places including Umuahia North LGA. There is also evidence that adequate measures have not been put in place to check the threats. The study therefore sought to explore ways of managing organizational climate for safety and security in secondary schools with a view of making the environment more conducive for teaching and learning toward achieving a sustainable national development.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is on managing organizational climate for safety and security in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State toward achieving a sustainable national development. Specifically, the study will:

1. Determine the security devices available for effective security management in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA;
2. Ascertain available emergency response plans for combating safety threats in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State;

3. Determine the organizational climate for safety and security in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State.
4. Ascertain measures to be adopted to ensure safe and secured school climate in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State.

Research Questions

1. What are the security devices available for effective security improvement in public secondary school in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State?
2. What are the available emergency response plans for managing safety threats in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State?
3. What measures are adopted by school administration to ensure a conducive organizational climate in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA?
4. What security measures should be adopted to ensure safe and secured school environment in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State?

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design with a total population of one hundred and sixty-two (162), comprising of seventeen (17) principals and one hundred and forty-five (145) teachers. Out of this population, a total of one hundred and thirty (130) respondents were sampled (14 principals and 116 teachers) using a simple random sampling technique. Two instruments were used to elicit responses from the respondents namely; Checklist and Questionnaire on Organizational Climate Safety and Security Management in Public Secondary Schools (QOCSSMPSS). The instrument was validated by two experts, one from Education Management and the other from Measurement and Evaluation and tested for its reliability and internal consistency using Cronbach Alpha Coefficient and a value of 0.74 was got. Research questions 1 and 2 were answered using frequency and percentage. A four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (1 point) was used for research question 3 and 4. The decision point was 2.50. Data was analyzed using mean score and standard deviation.

Results

Research Question I

What are the safety/security devices that are available for improving security situations in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State?

Table 1: Frequencies (F) and Percentages (%) of the respondents on available devices for the management of security in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State

Key: A = Available, NA = Not available
No. of Respondents = 130 (14 school principals and 116 teachers)

N/S	Items	F	%	Decision
1.	Iron doors	36	27.7	NA
2.	Visitors' guidelines	91	70.0	A
3.	Access control	49	47.6	NA
4.	Video surveillance (CCTV)	1	0.97	NA
5.	Burglar bars on the windows	83	63.8	A
6.	Staff and students ID cards	99	76.2	A
7.	Secured car park	52	40.0	NA
8.	Perimeter fencing of the school	112	86.2	A
9.	Manned control room with 24 hours operators	2	1.5	NA
10.	Sprinkler system to control fire damage	2	1.5	NA
11.	Spacious and well-ventilated classroom	109	83.8	A
12.	Central communication centre	44	33.8	NA
13.	Security lightening illuminating paths	43	33.1	NA
14.	Toilet/urinals	100	76.9	A
15.	A lightening system on sensitive areas	146	37.4	NA

In Table 1 data analysis, showed that only 6 items had percentage score above the benchmark of 50%, out of the 15 items on available devices for the management of security in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State. This indicates that the security devices for improving security in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA are not readily available.

Research Question 2

What are the available emergency response plans for managing security threats in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State?

Table 2: Frequencies (F) and Percentages (%) of respondents on available emergency response plans for managing safety threats in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State

S/N	Items	F	%	Decision
1.	Students roll call	111	85.4	A
2.	Students counseling services	100	76.9	A
3.	Emergency PTA meeting	73	56.2	A
4.	Emergency medical bag/Covid19 health protocols	19	14.6	NA
5.	Bell signals	114	87.9	A
6.	School Ambulance	2	1.5	NA
7.	Sand bucket	3	2.30	NA
8.	Sewage and refuse facilities	74	56.9	A
9.	Fire blanket	30	23.1	NA
10.	Fire extinguisher	25	19.2	NA
11.	Communication/recorder	3	2.3	NA

12.	Emergency Response Team	37	28.5	NA
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Key: A = Available, NA = Not available

No. of Respondents = 130 (14 school principals and 116 teachers)

In Table 2 data analysis showed that only 5 items had percentage score above the benchmark of 50% out of the 12 items on available emergency responses plans for managing safety threats in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State. This indicates that the emergency responses plan for managing safety threats in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State are not adequately available to manage threats to life and property.

Question 3. What are the measures adopted by the school administration to ensure a conducive organizational climate in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State?

S/N	Items		X	SD
Decision				
1.	The school administration motivate staff to sustain human behaviours towards goal attainment	2.87	0.18	A
2.	The school leader promotes effective school-family-community partnership	2.61	0.68	A
3.	The principal leadership style is commendable	2.78	0.52	A
4.	There is effective communication in the school	3.22	0.67	A
5.	There is teachers' participation in policy formulation and group discussion	3.17	0.73	A
6.	The principal control and coordinate human and material resources effectively and efficiently	2.93	0.55	A
7.	The school established effective disciplinary measures	3.09	0.31	A
8.	The principal shows respect, trust, sincerity and kindness to all staff	2.76	0.65	A
9.	The principal exploits all possible means to keep a healthy environment	2.69	0.58	A
10.	There is negligence by the school administration toward responding promptly to security matters	2.44	0.82	D
Cluster mean		2.86	0.57	A

Expected mean = 2.50

No. of Respondents = 130 (14 school principals and 116 teachers)

Table 3 revealed Mean rating score and Standard Deviation of responses on measures adopted by the school administration to ensure a conducive organizational climate in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA of Abia State. The cluster mean of 2.86 indicates that the respondents agreed on the measures adopted by the school administration to ensure a conducive organizational climate such as staff motivation, effective school-family-community partnership, leadership style, effective communication, teachers' participation in decision making and effective disciplinary measures.

Question 4 What security measures should be adopted to ensure a safe and conducive school climate in public secondary schools in Umuahia North LGA?

S/N	Items	X	SD	Decision
1.	Having a model school safety plan	3.15	.80	A
2.	Building school safety expectation into school programmes	3.49	.66	A
3.	Providing emergency equipment in schools	3.44	.54	A
4.	Establishing security audits for checking damaged equipment and facilities that need repair.	3.18	.51	A
5.	Building a network of parents and community volunteers	3.19	.69	A
6.	Training programmes for educators and principals on school safety and crisis response	3.45	.57	A
7.	Having crisis response team development for emergency	3.16	.81	A
8.	Having constant students drills on safety and security matters	3.45	.57	A
9.	Having constant school site surveys	3.06	.82	A
	Cluster mean	3.29	0,66	A

Expected mean = 2.50

No. of Respondents = 130 (14 school principals and 116 teachers)

Table 4 shows the opinion of respondents (principals and teachers) on all the 9 items on security measures that should be adopted to ensure a safe and conducive school climate with cluster mean of 3.29.

Discussion

From the results of the data analysis made, there is indication that the school administrations, to ensure a safe and secured environment, adopted a positive organizational climate. The result revealed that there is staff motivation to sustain human behaviours, teachers' participation in decision making, effective disciplinary measures, effective communication and effective school-family-community partnership. This indicates that the leadership style of the school principals helps to create a positive organizational climate in schools. This is in line with Agbajeola (2019) who posited that organizational climate counts as a key factor that affects school productivity. Merrow (2004) in Nwobodo and Udebunu (2017) posits that schools that have positive school climate have been associated with fewer behavioural and emotional problems for students. Additionally, specific researches on school climate indicate that a positive supportive, culturally conscious school climate can significantly shape the degree of academic success in schools (Trump, 2010). The findings also revealed that the security devices for improving security and which is also needed to check the level of insecurity threatening and causing danger and disaster in the learning environment in public secondary schools are generally not available, the emergency response plans which address threat prevention and emergency preparedness are not available either. The respondents agreed on the adequacy of all the 9 items on security measures that should be adopted to ensure conducive learning environment. According to McGuire (2017) in Mubita (2021), the primary indicator of a safe school is the existence of a plan in the school policy meant to address situations that may be a threat to learners and staff need a safe and supportive school environment in order to succeed. Morrison (2007) asserted that like all other activities in the school, the safety and

security of learners cannot be dealt with separately for specific occasions or purposes on an ad-hoc basis. It should be managed and be interwoven with all routine of school administration functions.

Conclusion

It is now evident from the findings of this study that organizational climate counts as a key factor that affects school safety, security and productivity. It plays significant roles in the management and administration of the school organization as well as enhances a conducive learning environment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings;

1. The school management should sustain a healthy organizational climate as well as introduce emergency response plans/devices for managing safety threats in the school.
2. The school management should provide clear and appropriate measures for managing the safety and security in schools.
3. The government should provide intervention funds to school management.

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ACADEMIC CORRUPT PRACTICES AND STUDENTS' EDUCATIONAL OUTCOME IN PUBLIC TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN SOKOTO STATE: IMPLICATION FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The research investigates the academic corrupt practices and students' educational outcome in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto state Nigeria. The research design used was descriptive survey. The total population of this study consisted of one thousand seven hundred and seventy-nine (1779) lecturers and heads of public tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. One thousand seven hundred and four (1704) are lecturers and seventy-five (75) are Heads of Department. Total sample of three hundred and ninety-seven (397) using Research Advisors 2006. However, a deliberate sampling technique was used, to distribute the heads of departments. Proportionate sampling and Simple random sampling techniques were used to distribute the instruments across the lecturers in the nine (9) public institutions in the state. Self-designed instrument was used for the collection of data for the study, tagged as Survey of Academic Corrupt Practices Questionnaire (SACPQ). (SACPQ) questionnaire comprised of eighty (80) items. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by the validates in the School of General Education, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. Test re-test method of reliability, given fifty (50) samples of questionnaires. The data collected analysed statistically by the means of Pearson Product Moment Co-efficient and the index was 0.89. This shows that the instrument is adequate. Inferential statistical techniques ANCOVA and chi-square was used to analyse the hypotheses of the study. The findings revealed that there is significant difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, admission-related corrupt practices, research related corrupt practices, Examination related corrupt practices and lectures related corrupt practices concur in all public tertiary institutions in the state. It was concluded that admission-related corrupt practices were the highest form of academic corrupt practices in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, followed by research related corrupt practices, Examination related corrupt practices and the least was Lectures related corrupt practices. The study recommended that: School Managements should consider and approve the thorough supervision and inspections of all forms of teaching and learning in their institutions in order to discourage all forms of corrupt practices in the state.

Key Words: Academic Corrupt Practices, National Development, Students' Educational Outcome

Introduction

Every civilized society has its own values and norms, and the aim of education in Nigeria is to inculcate these norms and value into the young ones. Such values include good character, integrity, honesty, hard work, and respect for constituted authority order etc. However, with societal changes, these norms and values are not only watered down but malpractices of sorts have permeated it and the educational sector is not spared. (Uche, (2014). Education in Nigeria is an instrument for excellence and effecting National development. Education is one of the most powerful instruments for reducing poverty and inequality. The tertiary institutions are made up of Universities, Polytechnics, Colleges of Education and other post-secondary institutions that require Secondary School Certificate for admission of its students. By implication, teachers at primary, secondary, and tertiary institutions, are trained in various institution of higher learning. This makes this study a crucial one as devices that prevail in the tertiary level of education are likely to be perpetuated at the lower levels (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2004).

It is observed that, the fundamental importance of education, particularly to developing countries indicates that large investments in education have resulted in smaller than expected effects. The same is true in Sokoto state context, the decrease in educational investment as most expected, has tremendous impact on educational outcomes, inefficiencies from the tertiary institutions' administrators, weak absorption capacities, and corruption at various levels of education, are issues of education outcomes. The issue of corruption has become topical and headline news in most countries and at the international level although the practice is believed to have existed long ago. Carr (2011) opines that corruption is a phenomenon that has always existed but in recent time the awareness of it has grown at international, national, state and local levels. The serious and extensive discourse about the subject has arisen probably because of its devastating effects on the individual and the society in general. According to the African Union in Hallack & Poisons (2002), corruption was estimated to directly and indirectly affect growth and development. Iddrisu (2003) opines that corruption kills initiative and rewards lazy people; corruption weakens society as it hampers the equitable distribution of values and the operation of justice; and it violates public trust and corrodes social capital.

Corruption as a conundrum has been a canker worm which has eaten deeply into the fabric of the society. Most countries are reported to be plagued with corruption and its concomitant effects on their people and economies. Nnodum (2008) asserts that the issues of corruption and people's involvement in the practice have become an endemic and cancerous menace plaguing and interfering with all facets of development and levels of human existence in Nigeria, which the situation is not different from that of Sokoto State. Sokoto is not void of academic corruption, weak primary and secondary education. The students are not reflecting their intellectual capacity. Maxwell (2013) observed that students' national examination grade in the country has a negative correlation with the CGPA of the students after gaining admission into tertiary institution their performance could not translate the result obtained at national examinations. This is to tell us that in our educational institutions there are lots of compromises allowed which in turn produces half backed graduates and this has declined the roles of tertiary institution.

Review of Related Literature

Despite all the attention corruption in education has attracted, the search for a common and all-embracing definition of corruption has remained elusive. There are two issues for this paradox. Firstly, corruption is expressive of a multitude of deviant behaviours. Secondly, the meaning or understanding of corruption does often vary from one culture to another and even within the same culture over time. The concept corruption, Fasokun (2010) defines as a behaviour which exploits human person, disdainfully uses men and women for selfish interests. The person who exhibits such behaviour gains at the detriment of the other party. Corruption is a problem of routine deviation from established standards and norms of public officials and parties they interact with. Ruzindana, in Kassahu, (2011) asserts that, corruption is a price, reward and gift or favour bestowed with or promised with the view to prevent justice, in whatever way corruption is defined as acts which are perceived to be against public interest or violate certain legal or moral laws and principles and some of these are directly or indirectly harmful to the society.

Academic corruption is an aspect of corruption that happens in the educational sector. Adedimeji (2015) submits that academic corruption involves all forms of deviation from justice, honesty, fairness, probity, impartiality and discipline expected from institutions of learning. Academic corruption actually stems from moral impurity and it manifests in selfish acts that are detrimental to the goal of education and advancement of society. Dimkpa (2011) opined that, academic corruption includes all forms of corrupt practices taking place in the academia and which have a direct negative effect on the quality and standard of education.

In explaining possible areas where corruption may occur in schools and classroom, Tanako in Whawo (2015) revealed that offer of bribes/favours to staff/teachers in exchange for contracts often result in substandard services and increase in procurement costs. He also added that, corruption can destroy equal educational opportunities by paying bribes to the disadvantage of poorer students. The vice underlying corruption is not selfishness", but stupidity arising from short-sightedness. The source argued that without corruption, all citizens would, after some years of honesty boost the economy and would become richer. The fear of the evils of corruption can be inferred from the assertion. Corruption is anti-national, anti-poor, and anti-economic development. The danger now is that corruption is being taken for granted and "the capacity for making money as much as possible from one's position is welcomed". Tanako in Whawo (2015)

Madu (2020) concur that, academic corruption is classified into three forms (1) Research-related Corruption: (2) Examination-related Corruption: (3) Sex for marks and lectures related corruption. According to Okebukola (2018), the rate of plagiarism as a form of academic corruption at the master's level is between 15 and 20 per cent and 8 per cent at the PhD level in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. The percentage is even much higher in the undergraduate levels. Archibong, (2013) reported cases of swapping of names for publications in order to take credit; inclusion of names to publish paper in which one did not contribute to; and falsification of data/research findings. Also, some lecturers publish the research findings of their supervisees without any recourse for partnership with the students. (2) Examination-related Corruption: this is characterized with the act of collecting money for change of grade or producing fake result; collecting

money for continuous assessment (Nwankwo and Nweke, 2016); One very trendy form of examination-related corrupt practices in Nigerian tertiary institutions of learning is sex for marks, Lecture Related Corruption: Okebukola (2018) notes that, it is academic corruption when lecturers do not show up in classes as required. Similarly, Adedimeji (2015) submits that, unethical sale of handouts, and deliberate failure to teach students when due are some of the most pervasive forms of academic corruption on our campuses. The Anti-Corruption Resource Centre (2006) also noted securing of lecturing appointments with forged certificates as an academic corruption. The implication being the display of incompetence. Above all, lecturers' appointment by political office holders mostly in state owned tertiary institutions gave birth to a new form of academic corruption

The word "development" connotes an incremental positive change in both the quantity and quality of something, characterized by advancement, strength and success. National Development according to Egbefo (2012) may be construed as the ability of a nation to make gradual transition from lower standard of living to a higher standard of living for the vast majority of its people. This suggests an improvement in the wellbeing of the majority of the citizens. In consonance with Egbefo's view, Madu, Aboyade and Aboyade (2016), maintained that, national development refers to the ability of a country to improve the social welfare of the people, for example, by providing social amenities like good education, infrastructure, medical care and social services. The features that can lead any country to development are: rich natural resources, rapid industrialization, increase in working population, stable political environment and very importantly, a corrupt-free educational system.

Statement of the Problem

Corruption is one of the major developmental challenges in Nigeria educational system. Corruption has also contributed immensely to the fallen standard of education in Nigeria, it has jeopardized the quality of education from primary to tertiary level, teachers, school administrators' parents, students and all other stakeholders are involved in the ills of corruption. Issues of corruption become prevalent in the Nigerian educational context which has plunged the system into a state of confusion and disarray. Higher institutions have been observed to be graduating half-baked graduates, granduands that can hardly write a very simple informal letter. The way one gets its certificate does not matter hence corruption in education becomes endemic in our society, if we tell our selves the truth, we will also have the courage and sense of mission to map out viable solutions to the problems. Among several problems facing the educational system in Nigeria academic corruption is a major one. This type of corruption is more dangerous and more serious threat to the future of Nigeria. Yushau, (2010) submits we must pause, reflect, take stock and look at where we are, where we want to be and to tell the truth so that we can move forward.

Perceived corrupt practices in tertiary institutions observed to have become intractable in educational institutions. Soap and Memory (2014) opined that, the practice has the tendency to make universities fail to achieve their goal of developing competent and morally upright people for socio- economic and political development of nations. The moral upbringing of students of tertiary educational institutions is paramount important to the sustainability and development of the societies they are

being trained for. The alleged acts of corruption have the tendency to negatively influence the students who are affected by the acts. There is the tendency for the graduates to carry the animosities that result from the corruption experiences they encountered at school to their places of work to the detriment of the societies and the innocent people that their work activities would affect. Although some studies have been conducted on the issue of corruption on academics and in educational institutions to understand it in order to prescribe appropriate solutions to it, some grey areas existed in extant literature that needed attention. It was realised that literature on corruption did not provide sufficient data on the initiators of the alleged corrupt practices in academic institutions and the conditions that serve as fertile grounds for the acts to be perpetuated. It is imperative to note that the fight against corruption of academic staff will succeed, largely, only when the initiators of the acts are known. This is because knowing the initiators would help authorities fashion appropriate. Where corruption is rampant there is a great risk that social trust may wither away and that the development potential of whole country may be undermined. It is against this background that the researchers investigate the academic corrupt practices and students' educational outcome in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto State.

Research Questions

In addressing the aforementioned problems, the following research questions were raised:

1. Find out the forms of academic corrupt practices in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State.
2. Find out how academic corrupt practices affect the academic outcome of students in public tertiary institution in Sokoto state
3. Find out how students' academic outcome through corruption practices affects national development in Sokoto State

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the research:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the forms of corruption practices in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference on how academic corruption affect students' academic outcome in public tertiary institution in Sokoto state

H₀₃: There is no significant difference on how students' academic outcome through Corruption practices affects national development in Sokoto state

Theoretical Framework

The Social learning theory forms the theoretical base for this study. The social learning theory assumes that a person's environment greatly affects his or her behaviour and that weak mechanism of social control enables corruption, criminal and other deviant behaviour in the society. The Nigerian educational sector is an integral part of the whole Nigerian society and having been overwhelmed by corruption, the individuals in this case lecturers are not isolated from their corrupt environment and therefore will assimilate negative tendencies.

Methodology

The study used a descriptive survey design as a method of data collection. It is Quantitative in the sense that it was based on methodological principles of description. The total population of this study consisted of one thousand seven hundred and seventy-nine (1779) lecturers and heads of public tertiary institutions in Sokoto State. One thousand seven hundred and four (1704) are lecturers and seventy-five (75) are Heads of Departments. Sample size of three hundred and twenty-seven (327) using Research Advisors 2006. However, a deliberate sampling technique was used to distribute the sample to heads of different department while Proportionate sampling and Simple random sampling techniques were used to distribute the instruments across the lecturers in the nine (9) public institutions in the state. A self-designed instrument that was used to collect data for the study tagged as Survey of Academic Corrupt Practices Questionnaire (SACPQ). It comprises of eighty (80) items. The questionnaire consisted of four (4) parts, Part A: personal information B: elicits information about forms of academic corruption, consisting administrative related corruption, examination related corruption, research related corruption and lectures related corruption Part C: elicits information about how academic corrupt practices affect graduates and Part D: elicits information about academic corrupt practices as they affect national development. The validity of the instrument was ascertained by the panel of experts in the School of General Education, Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto. Some of the items in the questionnaire were recast and restructured to meet standard. After corrections and amendments, the number of items corrected and amended were divided by the initial number of items of the questionnaire to establish the content validity of the instrument.

The Content Validity Index of 0.70 and above is established, using the formula below:

$$\text{CVI} = \frac{\text{Total number of items declared valid}}{\text{Total number of items}}$$

0.92 was the content validity index, this shows that the instrument is valid for data collection in the study. The researcher used test re-test method of reliability, given fifty (50) samples of questionnaires for the first and second test. An interval of four weeks was given between the first and second administration of the instrument. The data collected were analysed statistically by the means of using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and the Correlation Co-efficient was 0.89. This shows that the instrument was reliable. The data collected were analyzed using simple descriptive such as frequency table, percentage, and mean to analyse the research questions and inferential statistical techniques such as ANCOVA and chi-square to analyse the hypotheses of the study, using statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 20). Mean scored was interpreted as follows 0-1.99 as Low, 2.0-3.49 as Moderate and 3.5 – 4.0 as high.

Results

Data generated were analysed based on the research hypotheses as shown below:

Forms of Academic Corrupt Practices in Public Tertiary Institution

To find the answer to the research hypothesis one, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to analyse the data as shown in the table 3,4 and 5.

Table 1: Admission-Related Academic Corrupt Practices

Variables	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
Payment of bribes for promotions or scholarship of admitted staff or Student	2.9871	.11293	Moderate
Collection of bribes for students' accreditation	2.9278	.49800	Moderate
Payment of bribes to obtain offer as lecturer	2.9098	.40616	Moderate
Payment of bribes to obtain admission as student	3.0052	.30495	Moderate
Professional misconduct some admitted staff	2.8763	.54289	Moderate
Politicians influencing employment of unqualified lecturers	2.9974	.30919	Moderate
Unauthorized absenteeism or Habitual late coming	2.9948	.35941	Moderate
Unauthorized collection of money from students for admission	2.0541	.56115	Low
Forgery or mutilation of official document	2.0567	.55859	Low
Fighting in or within the school premises for admission	2.0387	.50430	Low
Total mean scored (N.397)	2.6825	.16783	Moderate

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 1 highlights the admission related academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools. Result revealed that there was moderate form of admission related corruption with total mean scored of 2.6825 and standard deviation of .16783. It is also characterised with lecturers paying of bribe for promotions or scholarship, Payment of bribes to obtain offer as lecturer, Collection of bribe for students' accreditation and admission and Politicians influencing employment of unqualified lecturers (considering the total mean score of 2.9871,2.9278, 2.9098,3.0052,2.9974 and 2.9948 respectively> Average mean scored 2.0). This shows that there was moderate form of admission related academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools, Sokoto State.

Table 2: Research-Related Academic Corrupt Practices

Variables	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
Intellectual thievery or plagiarism	2.0670	.43210	Low
Swapping and replacing of names for students' projects	2.9588	.47506	Moderate
Swapping and replacing of names for publications	2.0026	.42832	Low
Falsification of data/research findings by students	2.9588	.37815	Moderate
Falsification of data for publications by lecturers	2.0825	.43539	Low
Payment of bribes for publications by lecturers	2.0258	.33620	Low
Collection of money from students for projects work	2.8969	.57483	Moderate
Payment of bribes for student projects supervisors	2.0747	.40294	Low
Sex for student's projects	2.0412	.41090	Low
Supervisors accepting fee for students' projects data analyses	2.9082	.47078	Moderate
Total mean scored (N.397)	2.6157	.49262	Moderate

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 2 highlights the research-related academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools. Result revealed that there was moderate form of research related corruption considering the total mean scored of 2.6157 and standard deviation of .49262. It is also characterised with Supervisors accepting fee for students' projects, data analyses, collection of money from students for projects work, Falsification of data/research findings by the students and supervisors Swapping and replacing of names for students' projects (considering the total mean score of 2.9082,2.8969, 2.9098,2.9588 and 2.9588 respectively > Average mean scored 2.0).This shows that there was moderate form of research-related academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools, Sokoto State.

Table 3: Examination-Related Corrupt Practices

Variables	Mean	S D..	Interpretation
leakage or selling of examination questions in advance	2.0361	.41138	Low
collecting money for change of grade	2.9356	.39174	Moderate
collecting money for continuous assessment	1.9974	.43431	Low
female students approach male lecturers with request to offer sex for marks	2.9304	.33380	Moderate
students to cheating in examination hall	2.0026	.30072	Low
covering up exam malpractice cases	2.0258	.39943	Low
awarding undeserved scores to students	2.1082	.48078	Low
falsification of exam record or result	2.9407	.48127	Moderate
exam without covering the course outline	3.7835	.68918	High
lecturers demand sex from female students	2.9124	.41615	Moderate
Total mean scored (N.397)	2.5673	.13634	Moderate

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 3 highlights the examination-related corrupt practices in public tertiary institutions. Result revealed that there was moderate form of examination related corruption considering the total mean scored of 2.5673 and standard deviation of .13634. It is also characterised with collecting money for change of grade, female students approach male lecturers with request to offer sex for marks, falsification of exam record or result, giving students exam without covering the course outline and lecturers demand sex from female students (considering the total mean score of 2.9356,2.9304, 2.9407,2.9588, 3.7835 and 2.9124 respectively > Average mean scored 2.0).This shows that there was moderate form of examination-related corrupt practices in public tertiary schools, Sokoto State.

Table 4: Lectures-Related Corrupt Practices

Variables	Mean	S.D.	Interpretation
Deliberate failure to teach students	2.0155	.3868	Low
Securing of lecturing appointments with forged certificates	1.1572	.5647	Low
Lecturers lobby for allocation more courses than they can adequately handle	2.9407	.3791	Moderate
Certain courses with large number of students	3.7397	.6983	High
Siphoning of school instructional material/ teaching aids	2.8634	.4596	Moderate

Forcing students to buy text books with assignments attached	2.0876	.3485	Low
Forceful/compulsory sale of substandard text to students	2.9768	.3402	Moderate
Regular absenteeism/habitual behavior of going to classes late	2.9768	.3402	Moderate
Disservice to the students /telling stories unrelated to the topic(s)	2.0052	.2963	Low
Lecturer borrows books from the library and fails to return them,	2.0902	.4598	Low
Total mean scored (N.397)	2.4923	.1287	Moderate

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 4 highlights the lectures-related corrupt practices in public tertiary schools. Result revealed that there was moderate form of lectures related corruption considering the total mean scored of 2.4923 and standard deviation of .12877. It is also characterised with Lecturers lobby for allocation more courses than they can adequately handle, siphoning of school instructional materials, compulsory sale of substandard text to students and regular absenteeism and going to classes late (considering the total mean score of 2.9407, 3.7397, 2.8634, 2.9768, and 2.9768 respectively > Average mean scored 2.0). This shows that there was moderate form of lectures-related corrupt practices in public tertiary schools, Sokoto State.

Table 5: Summary of forms of academic corruption

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Mean Ranking
Admission-related academic corrupt practices	2.6825	.16783	1 st
Research-related academic corrupt practices	2.6157	.49262	2 nd
Examination-related academic corrupt practices	2.5673	.13634	3 rd
Lectures -related academic corrupt practices	2.4923	.12877	4 th

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 5 highlights the summary of forms of academic corruption in public tertiary schools. Result revealed that the admission-related academic corrupt practice was the highest form of academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools, Sokoto State. This was followed by Research related corruption, Examination related corruption and the least was lectures related corruption (considering the total mean score of 2.6825 > 2.6157, 2.5673, 2.4923 respectively). This shows that there was moderate form of admission, research, examination and Lectures related academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools, Sokoto State.

How Corruption Affect the Academic Outcome of Students in Public Tertiary Institution

To find the answer to the research objective two mean and standard deviation were used to analyses the data as shown in the Table 6.

Table 6: How Academic Corrupt Practices Affect the Academic Outcome of Students

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Encourage poor certification of graduate	3.7655	.71466	High
Induces ill motivation for studies	3.8582	.46368	High
Bad study habits.	3.8505	.54115	High
Indiscipline among students	2.9948	.29636	Moderate
Encourage examination malpractices and cheating	3.0052	.29636	Moderate
Encourage students to seeking academic success via all means possible	3.7835	.68164	High
Poor quality of university graduates	3.8557	.53777	High
Inability of university graduates to perform tasks	3.0206	.24817	Moderate
Delayed absorption of graduates into labour market	3.0052	.41294	Moderate
Inability of graduates to communicate effectively	2.9510	.41939	Moderate
Total mean scored (N.397)	3.4103	.16250	Moderate

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 6 highlights how academic corrupt practices affect the academic outcome of students. Result revealed that there were moderate academic corrupt practices that affect the academic outcome of students considering the total mean scored of 3.4103 and standard deviation of .16250. This shows that there were moderate academic corrupt practices that affect the academic outcome of students in public tertiary institution, Sokoto State. It also encourages students seeking academic success via all means possible, induces ill motivation for studies, bad study habits and poor certification of graduates.

How Students Academics Outcome through Corruption Practices Affect National Development

To find the answer to the research objective two mean and standard deviation were used to analyses the data as shown in the table 7.

Table 7: How Academics Corrupt Practices Affect National Development

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Bad Governance	3.8299	.5539	High
Poor service delivery	2.9794	.3865	Moderate
Inadequate infrastructural amenities	3.8866	.3838	High
Scarcity of basic social amenities such as potable water	2.9716	.3960	Moderate
crime and insecurity	3.0000	.3050	Moderate
siphoned of public funds meant for national development	3.8608	.4144	High
Brain drain or human capital abuse	1.9974	.2920	Low
emigration of trained and talented individuals to other nations	3.0644	.2458	Moderate
lack of opportunity or unemployment	3.9356	.2458	High
Under development in democratic dispensation	3.0490	.2160	Moderate
Total mean scored (N.397)	3.2575	.1112	Moderate

Field work (2022)

The presented data in Table 7 highlights how academic corrupt practices affect the national development. Result revealed that there were moderate academic corrupt practices that affect the national development, considering the total mean scored of 3.2575 and standard deviation of .1112. This shows that there were moderate academic corrupt practices that affect the national development in Sokoto State. It also leads to bad Governance, Inadequate infrastructural amenities, siphoned of public funds meant for national development and Scarcity of basic social amenities such as potable water and electricity in the state.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State.

To find the answer to the hypothesis one, ANCOVA analyses were used to analyses the data as shown in the Table 8.

Table 8: Showing Difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Sig.
Corrected Model	7.481 ^a	3	2.494	32.594	.000	
Intercept	10406.413	1	10406.413	136026.916	.000	
Forms of Acad. Curr.	7.481	3	2.494	32.594	.000	HO1
Error	118.426	1548	.077			Rejected
Total	10532.320	1552				
Corrected Total	125.907	1551				

Field work (2022)

When the data collected were subjected to ANCOVA for the difference in the forms of academic corrupt practices as shown in table 8. The results revealed that there was significant difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices in public tertiary institution considering the ANCOVA value at 7.481 and the P-value = 0.000 > 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 was rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, hence, it is concluded that there was significant difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State.

Hypothesis 2: Academic Corrupt practices has not significantly affected the academic outcome of students in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State.

To find the answer to the hypothesis two, Chi-square analyses was employed to analyses the data as shown in the Table 9.

Table 9: showing how Academic Corrupt practices affect the academic outcome of students

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	DF	Chi-Square Value	P-Value	Decision
Student Academic outcome	388	3.4103	.16250	7	783.010	0.00	HO2 Rejected

Field work (2022)

When the data collected were subjected to Chi-square analyses for the effect of academic corrupt practices on the academic outcome of students as shown in table 9. The results revealed that academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the academic outcome of students considering the Chi-square value at 783.010 and the P-value = 0.000 > 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 was rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, hence, it is concluded that academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the academic outcome of students in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State.

Hypothesis 3: Academic Corrupt practices has not significantly affected the national development in Sokoto State.

To find the answer to the hypothesis three, Chi-square analyses was employed to analyses the data as shown in the Table 10.

Table 10 showing how Academic Corrupt practices affect the National Development

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	DF	Chi-Square Value	P-Value	Decision
National development	388	3.2575	.11123	5	511.320	0.00	HO3 Rejected

Field work (2022)

When the data collected were subjected to Chi-square analyses for the effect of academic corrupt practices on the national development as shown in table 10. The results revealed that academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the national development considering the Chi-square value at 511.320 and the P-value = 0.000 > 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis 3 was rejected and the alternative hypothesis is accepted, hence, it is concluded that academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the national development in Sokoto State.

Summary of Major Findings

1. There was significant difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices in public tertiary institutions in Sokoto State and the forms are admission-related corrupt practices, research related corrupt practices, Examination related corrupt practices and lectures related corrupt practices.
2. Academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the academic outcome of students in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State. It also encourages students seeking academic success via all means possible, induces ill motivation for studies, bad study habits and poor certification of graduates.
3. Academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the national development in Sokoto State. It also leads to bad Governance, Inadequate infrastructural amenities, siphoned of public funds meant for national development and Scarcity of basic social amenities such as potable water and electricity in the state.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the first hypothesis revealed that there was significant difference in the forms of Academic Corrupt practices in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State and the forms are admission-related corrupt practices, research related corrupt practices, Examination related corrupt practices and lectures related corrupt practices. The finding was supported by Madu (2020), Okebukola (2018), Nwankwo and Nweke (2016) and Adedimeji (2015) who submitted that Academic corruption is classified into three forms (1) Research-related Corruption (2) Examination-related Corruption and (3) Lecture-Related Corruption and submits that, unethical sale of handouts, and deliberate failure to teach students are some of the most pervasive forms of academic corruption on our campuses.

However, the finding of the second hypothesis revealed that academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the academic outcome of students in public tertiary institution in Sokoto State. It also encourages students seeking academic success via all means possible, induces ill motivation for studies, bad study habits and poor certification of graduates. The finding was in line with the study of Adedimeji (2015), who submitted that the backlashes of academic corruption are very clear in our society now. Our educational institutions “are filled with incompetent teachers who had been pushed through higher institutions of learning. Our hospitals have become mortuaries because doctors were not well trained as medical students and they appear more interested in the title than a career of saving lives. Our buildings collapse and fatalities occur because poor teaching and poor learning resulted in theoretical engineers that are bereft of quality.

Finally, the finding of the third hypothesis revealed that academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the national development in Sokoto State. It also leads to bad governance, inadequate infrastructural amenities, siphoning of public funds meant for national development and Scarcity of basic social amenities such as potable water and electricity in the state. The finding was in line with the study of Douglas and Magdaline (2017) who found out that Corruption in the education industry terribly creates infrastructural deficits that result in poor instructional delivery and making many people not to have access to education which in addition to being a fundamental human rights and a spring board for their empowerment and emancipation and this has caused infrastructural deficits and inability of a people to have access to education which systematically renders useless the ability of the people to engineer national development as generations of citizens are left frustrated, disgruntled and disenchanting in addition to manifesting terrible immorality in the forms of militancy and insurgency.

Conclusion

It was concluded that admission-related corrupt practices were the highest form of academic corrupt practices in public tertiary schools in Sokoto State, followed by research related corrupt practices, Examination related corrupt practices and the least was Lectures related corrupt practices.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. School Managements of universities, polytechnics and colleges should consider and approve the thorough supervision and inspections of all forms of academic corrupt practices in the public tertiary institutions in order to avoid all forms of professional misconduct in the state.
2. Workshops can be organized by the Head of the Departments to enlighten the students and parents on the dangers of Academic corrupt practices and how it affected the academic outcome of students.
3. Government and other stakeholder efforts are highly needed in the society through public enlightenment to educate the society on how Academic corrupt practices have significantly affected the national development in State.

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TEACHER TRAINING IN GLOBALIZED SOCIETY

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Abstract

This paper explores teachers training in a globalized society. Conceptual clarification on teachers, teacher training, globalization and educational globalization were presented. The need for teachers training and how training is done in a globalized society were highlighted. It was recommended amongst others that teachers training programmes in Nigeria must conform to global best practices.

Key Words: Teacher, Training, Globalized, Society, Educational

Introduction

Education is a satisfying item for consumption, its rewards are never-ending, in the sense that no man ever ceases to educate himself from the cradle to the grave. The object of education is the development of the human personality (Maiyo, Kyalo & Marcella, 2005), it functions within a framework of fundamental freedoms and human rights (UNESCO, 1968). Education, is a key to civilization and enlightenment and a source of wealth and power. It is the cornerstone of the growth and development of any country's social economic and political institutions. Harbison (1985), contends that the wealth of the nation fundamentally depends on the development of human resources. Education is becoming more invaluable to individuals. In today's environment, education provides individuals with a better chance of employment, which in turn leads to a better lifestyle, power and status. The commodification of knowledge as intellectual property has occurred particularly with regard to connecting the intellectual work with community, business, and government interests and priorities (Patted, 2003). The world has become a global village. No country can live in isolation without seeking impact of global trends and a change in all field of life, education is the most important tool in global development.

Teachers are indispensable assets in the Nigerian State if the goals of education enshrined in the National Policy of Education must be achieved. The teacher is regarded as the most important element within the educational program. It is the teacher, who is responsible for putting into practice the educational programs at any stage (Ikogi, et. al., 2021). Teachers' level of performance and commitment is proportional to the satisfaction they derive from their homes and the school environment (Odou-Matthew, 2021). This therefore implies that the government and other stakeholders must have a thorough understanding of what makes the teacher happy; which in turn will propel the actualization of educational goals.

Hopkins (2004) opined that the term globalization is derived from the word globalize, which refers to the emergence of an international network of economic systems. The forces and characteristics of globalization dynamics have put an end to the existence of traditional boundaries among nations, regions and ethnic divides. Suddenly, the whole world had become a global village. In education, the changes brought on by globalization have manifested through various channels and mechanisms as reforms of structures, modes of financing, administration and curriculum. For education to achieve its intent, the teacher must be well equipped to accommodate the changes posed by globalization. Effective training of teachers has been the only channel through which the teacher will continue to discharge his duty in the globalized setting. Hence, this study is geared towards examining need for teachers training and how training is done in a globalized society.

Conceptual Classification

Teacher

A teacher is a person who helps others to acquire knowledge, competences or values. Informally, the role of teacher may be taken on by anyone (e.g. when showing a colleague how to perform a specific task). In some countries, teaching young people of school age may be carried out in an informal setting, such as within the family (homeschooling), rather than in a formal setting such as a school or college. Some other professions may involve a significant amount of teaching (e.g. youth worker, pastor). In most countries, formal teaching of students is usually carried out by paid professional teachers.

A teacher's professional duties may extend beyond formal teaching. Outside of the classroom, teachers may accompany students on field trips, supervise study halls, help with the organization of school functions, and serve as supervisors for extracurricular activities. In some education systems, teachers may have responsibility for student discipline. A teacher can also be called an instructor. He is the pivot in educational system. Kocchar (2002) pointed out that the best curriculum and the most perfect syllabus remains dead unless quickened into life by the right methods of teaching and the right kind of teachers.

Caena (2011) observed that teaching is a highly complex activity. This is in part because teaching is a social practice that takes place in a specific context (time, place, culture, socio-political-economic situation etc.) and therefore reflects the values of that specific context (Cochran-Smith, 2006). However, there are certain factors that influence what is expected of teachers. They include history and tradition, social views about the purpose of education and accepted theories about learning, etc. The competencies required by a teacher are affected by the different ways in which the role is understood around the world. Broadly, Caena (2011), opined that there seem to be four models:

- i. The teacher as manager of instruction;
- ii. The teacher as caring person;
- iii. The teacher as expert learner; and
- iv. The teacher as cultural and civic person.

Teacher Training

Training is the process of acquiring specific skills to perform a job better (Jucious, 1963). It helps people to become qualified and proficient in doing some jobs (Dahama, 1979). Usually, an organization facilitates the employees' learning through training so that their modified behaviour contributes to the attainment of the organization's goals and objectives. Van-Dersal (1962) defined training as the process of teaching, informing, or educating people so that they may become as well qualified as possible to do their job at the same time become qualified to perform in positions of greater difficulty and responsibility.

Mathis and Jackson (1985) defined training as a learning process whereby people acquire skills, concepts, attitudes or knowledge to aid the achievement of goals. Hall and Goodale (1986) defined training to be "a planned effort by an organization to facilitate the learning of job-related knowledge and skills by its employee to improve employee performance and further organizational goal." Egumu and Oladunjoye (2016) opined that training is a process by which the learner is being equipped so that he can perform well on the role for which he is being trained. They elucidated that training is concerned with the acquisition of skills of a particular function. Hence, it has a specific intent.

From the definitions above, it can be deduced that training is a process, meaning that it is continuous, it is a planned and conscientious effort by the organization and it involves the acquisition of skills and knowledge which is aimed at improving the employee performance for the advancement of organizational goals.

Globalization

Hopkins (2004) pointed out that the term globalization is derived from the word globalize, which refers to the emergence of an international network of economic systems. One of the earliest known usages of the term as a noun was in a 1930 publication entitled *Towards New Education*, where it denoted a holistic view of human experience in education. Russell (1897) coined a related term, corporate giants, to refer to the largely national trusts and other large enterprises of the time. Feder (2006) postulated that the term 'globalization' had been used in its economic sense at least as early as 1981, and in other senses since at least as early as 1944. Levitt (1983) was credited with popularizing the term and bringing it into the mainstream business audience. Since its inception, the concept of globalization has inspired competing definitions and interpretations. Hopkin, (2004) and Bakari (2013) opined that its antecedents date back to the great movements of trade and empire across Asia and the Indian Ocean from the 15th century onward.

Accordingly, Albrone & King (1990) define globalization as "all those processes by which the people of the world are incorporated into a single world society." Giddens (1990) posited that "Globalization can thus be defined as the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away and vice versa". Robertson (1992), described globalization as the compression of the world and the intensification of the consciousness of the world as a whole.

Globalization can be referred to those spatial-temporal processes of change which underpin a transformation in the organization of human affairs by linking

together and expanding human activity across regions and continents. Without reference to such expansive spatial connections, there can be no clear or coherent formulation of this term. Held, Goldblatt, McGrew and Perraton (1999) opined that a satisfactory definition of globalization must capture each of these elements: extensity (stretching), intensity, velocity and impact.

Educational Globalization

Globalization has become a widespread idea in national and international dialogue in recent years. Globalization's shifting and controversial parameters make it difficult to define. It is clearly a dominant force, both positively and negatively, shaping the multiple environments in which we live. Despite the ambiguities in definition and significance, the anxieties and backlashes it generates, globalization will remain a dominant paradigm for the foreseeable future.

Global education, as a distinct construct from globalization, does what higher education has traditionally aimed to do: extend students' awareness of the world in which they live by opening them to the diverse heritage of human thought, action, and creativity. Global education places particular emphasis on the changes in communication and relationships among people throughout the world, highlighting such issues as human conflict, economic systems, human rights and social justice, human commonality and diversity, literatures and cultures, and the impact of the technological revolution. While it continues to depend on the traditional branches of specialist knowledge, global education seeks to weaken the boundaries between disciplines and encourages emphasis on what interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary studies can bring to the understanding and solution of human problems.

The forces and characteristics of globalization dynamics have ended traditional boundaries among nations, regions and ethnic divides. Suddenly the whole world had become a global village. Globalization in historical context has a longer origin than most people are prepared to acknowledge. The two trends in the 1980s and 1990s influenced educational policies all over the World. The first was the appearance of a new set of economic conditions associated with significant increases in the global competition faced by previously relatively well-protected national economies. The directions of these reforms vary, from the widespread development of curriculum and content standards and assessment in the formulation of generic teaching standards by the state education systems in the World. The outcomes of this trend varied and were, of course, partly political. In education, the changes brought on by globalization have manifested through various channels and mechanisms as reforms of structures, modes of financing, administration and curriculum. In several countries, they were expressed in the adoption of neo-liberal economic policies; they led to attempts to cut public expenditure, and to maximize the economic benefits of educational spending by increasing its efficiency and directing its goals to economic rather than social or cultural ends.

The second and more specific trend was a series of fundamental educational reforms; of which changes in the structure and content of teacher education were usually a part. The rigidity and control of teacher education reform policies playing into the hegemonic ideology of globalization might also be a way to create an illusion of organization and certainty in a world that is becoming more uncertain as boundaries

open up and disappear. Major international bodies such as World Bank, IMF, OECD, UNESCO, GAAT and so forth provided loans and donors for consolidation of human rights. These bodies systematically impose procedures based on their expectations so that their loans and donors are linked to structural changes in different civic and democratic implementations and conditions and conveyed in a participatory manner that include, for instance, the developing the role of civil society in developing countries. These international institutions place political and economic programs which appear to exit their own right and expectations and play a role in maintaining or altering those conditions. They exert their influence through stipulating that financial assistance to nation states is conditional upon the dismantling of trade barriers and of their entry into a global system of free markets, which again limits the ability of nation states to firewall their economies. The combination of these forces heavily conditions many nation state activities. Education is one such activity, not only in terms of its financing, but in terms of the uses to which it is actually put. There are intimate connections between political globalization, economic forces, and national domestic policies. School reforms and reforms in teacher education rely on global discourses that move from one country to another. Globalization does not, anyway, mean that national distinctions become erased or that everything becomes identical. Today's world is changing fast both economically and socially. While global competition is not perfect in all ways, for example free trade has not yet equated to fair trade, competition for ideas has never been stronger, education has been recognized as the basic means of promoting the skills of globalization.

The Need for Training

Shubin (1985) in Agulana & Awuju (2011) opined that training is for completeness. He highlighted the purpose of training as follows:

1. To increase the quality and productivity of personnel
2. To improve organizational climate
3. To address personnel growth and prevent obsolescence
4. To help a company fulfill its personnel needs
5. To improve the health and safety of personnel
6. To improve interpersonal communication, leadership and teamwork

Through effective training, organizations increase the capacity of their non performing employees. Moreover, continuous training is vital as a result of the developments in science and technology. The invention of the internet world, the Global System of Mobile communication (GSM), genetic engineering, quantum physics and sub atomic developments require continuous training.

Globalization in Teacher Training

Education plays a very vital and strategic role in the society. It has been identified as a conscious, deliberate and planned process designed to modify the behavior in a desirable and socially acceptable way to impart specific knowledge and skills. A nation's development potential depends upon its ability to continuously educate its population and its ability to create armies of skilled manpower. This is made possible by effective and modern teachers' training (Agulana & Awuju, 2011).

The training of teachers has moved longed time ago from analog model to a jet model. Most countries in Africa are still plagued with poor teacher training mechanism. The product of this system is poor society plagued with social vices and poverty (Maiyo, Kyalo & Marcella, 2005). The following factors are essential in globalization in teachers' training:

a) Information Technology

Information technology has influenced all aspects of human life hence acquiring knowledge and skill about it has become an essential element in teachers' training. In the present age of information revolution, information technology offers unprecedented opportunities to enhance learning effectiveness and expand access to high quality education. Today, technology is continuing to change teaching and learning in teacher education. For more than a century, the most predominant form of instruction in higher education has been classroom-based and instructor led; today this traditional approach to learning is being challenged by new technologies such as Multimedia, Telecommunications, and the Internet. Information Technology is taking place and even a literate person is feeling as if he is illiterate because he is unable to cope with the information explosion. It is both an important area of study in its own right and a tool that is being integrated into the everyday life of more and more people (ISTE, 1999).

Natarajan (2003) pointed out that in the future, our lives and livelihood will be substantially transformed by IT devices. In PC based learning, for instance, IT will be a powerful "thought support" system. When compared to a textbook or a lecture, in a view of multimedia interactivity, swift feedback and feeling of control. Although new technology by itself may not be sufficient to improve education, but appropriate use of Information Technology will help teachers to perform their job effectively.

Taylor (1997) defined Information science as the science that investigates the properties and behaviors of information, the forces governing the flow of information, and the means of processing information for optimum accessibility and usability. The field is derived from those related to mathematics, logic, linguistic, psychology, computer technology, graphic arts, management and other fields.

Information, which has been stored electronically and retrieved immediately through machine, is the information technology. UNESCO consider IT as "scientific, technological and engineering disciplines and management techniques used in information handling and processing, their application, computers and their interaction with men and machines and associated social, economic and cultural matters". Hence, application of IT to education involves many disciplines related to computers in handling, processing, management, automation and communication of information in the broader cultural and economic context of a society.

Information Technology is a systematic study of artifact that can be used to give form or description to facts in order to provide meaning to give form or description to facts in order to provide meaning or support for decision-making and artifact that can be used for the organization, processing, communication, and application of information. Thus, comprehensively IT can be defined as the use of hardware and software for efficient management of information, i.e., storage, retrieval, processing, communication, diffusion and sharing of information for social, economic and cultural uplift.

Information Technology (IT) is dynamic in nature. It has lots of potentiality to improve and manage different aspects of Teacher Education such as IT with reference to "technology in education", encompasses one or more of the following:

1. Media and AV communication, e.g. Alternative instructional delivery systems such as radio, ETV, etc.
2. Vocational training tools, such as CBT (Computer Based Training), CAD (computer- aided design), etc.;
3. Computers and computer-based systems for instructional delivery and management, e.g., CAI (Computer Assisted Instruction) etc.
4. Internet/web-based education e.g., not only educational information with text, graphics, and video but also courses should be offered by various web sites.
5. While IT refers primarily to the components of media, computer tools and instructional uses of computer-based systems, Instructional Technology lies at the core and in the starting point for any effective teacher education programmers.

b) Learning Environment

The enchanting description of a classroom at the fictitious Hogwarts School of Witchcraft and Wizardry captures three fundamental ideas from the environmental psychology of teaching and learning (Graetz 2016). First, all learning takes place in a physical environment with quantifiable and perceptible physical characteristics. Whether sitting in a large lecture hall, underneath a tree, or in front of a computer screen, students are engulfed by environmental information. He stated that the physical characteristics of learning environments can affect learners emotionally, with important cognitive and behavioral consequences. Although emotional reactions to environmental stimuli have been shown to vary widely across individuals and activities, most students would probably find learning difficult in a classroom that is stiflingly warm. Conversely, environments that elicit positive emotional responses may lead not only to enhanced learning but also to a powerful, emotional attachment to that space. It may become a place where students love to learn, a place they seek out when they wish to learn, and a place they remember fondly when they reflect on their learning experiences.

He went further to state that the areas of psychology that relate most directly to classroom design and learning environments are environmental, educational, human factors (engineering), and social psychology. Previous researches on the effects of such environmental variables as light, temperature, and noise on learning have yielded some predictable results that are addressed through traditional classroom design. Learning appears to be affected adversely by inadequate light, extreme temperatures, and loud noises—variables maintained within acceptable ranges in most college classrooms. Other results, however, reflect the often complex, subtle, and surprising interplay between the learner and the learning environment. Years of research on the impact of environmental variables on human thoughts, feelings, and behaviors indicate that other variables often moderate the effects of environmental variables. In a summary of the research on educational environments, Weinstein (1979) concluded that environmental variables can impact learners indirectly and that the effects of different physical settings often depend on the nature of the task and the learner. For example, distracting noises appear to slow reaction time and degrade performance to a greater degree in older versus younger adults and for introverts to a greater degree than extraverts.

Goel, Chhaya, Earnest and Malhar (2002) opined that for effective teaching to take place, the environment must be suitable and conducive. Teaching aids, devices and tools must be in abundance. The classrooms and hostels must be habitable. These attributes drive effective learning. Countries that want to be globally renowned for effective teachers' training must ensure that the enablers of learning are available

c) Remuneration

Remuneration can also be called compensation. It is considered to be the tips provided to an employee by an employer in exchange for the services performed; not to be confused with giving (away), or donating, or the act of providing to. A number of complementary benefits, however, are increasingly popular remuneration mechanisms. Remuneration is one component of reward management.

Countries that want to be renowned for teacher training must take teachers' welfare seriously. Salaries, emoluments and other entitlement must be paid as when due. One of the major problems of teachers' training in Nigeria is the poor welfare package. Teachers are one of the least paid civil servants with terrible reward system. Such an environment cannot participate in global scene in teachers' training. Countries such as United States of America, Russia and other developed countries see teachers' welfare as paramount to sustainable development. A reward system is the fulcrum for effective teachers' training. Government that really interested in teachers' training must provide good accommodations for both the trainers and trainees. Aside emoluments, a robust healthcare system must be in place to cater for the health needs of both the trainers and trainees. Prioritizing the welfare system of teachers will immeasurably drive effective learning.

d) International Standards

In any educational system, the teacher performs a significant function of perpetuating society's heritage and energizing human resources towards social progress. The level of a nation's education cannot rise far above the quality of the teacher of that nation. This therefore, makes the preparation and selection of teachers a significant social concern. There is a need to review and transform both the professional preparation of teachers and their in-service training. There is little doubt that likes all developing countries, educational particularly in its quest to achieve education for all by 2020. Undoubtedly, teachers lie at the heart of this educational crisis because only the teachers who possess the necessary technical competence and professional skills through a well-coordinated teacher's education program that can rise to meet the challenges of the crisis.

The Education commission recommended the introduction of "a sound program of professional education of teachers". It further remarked that investment in teacher education can yield very rich dividends because the financial resources required are small when measured against the resulting improvements in the education of millions. As a teacher tries to teach in the way in which he himself was taught by his favorite teachers, this tends to perpetuate the traditional methods of teaching. Such an attitude becomes an obstacle in progress in a situation like the present when new and dynamic methods of instruction are needed. This situation can be modified only by effective professional education which will initiate the teacher to the needed revolution in teaching and lay the foundations for his future professional growth.

Classroom management is not an end in itself but indicative of teachers' authority, inner strength, interpersonal relations and leadership role. A learning environment that seeks students' cooperation and minimizes disciplinary problems would be achieved by teachers who have expertise in content and instructional strategies, who make wise decisions about time and space, who demonstrate an attitude of valuing and caring their students. Preventive classroom management can be effected by planning rules and procedures beforehand as well as developing accountability in students for their academic work and classroom behavior. Effective managers have intervention skills for dealing quickly with disruptive in direct and fairways. The development of personality traits and cultivation of skills required for effective management is be achieved through theory, practice and effective monitoring.

e) Focus of Teacher training

The focus of teachers training should depart from the traditional method of professional teacher educational program which thus far has not produced the desired quality and professionalism. This system exposes the teacher to acquire a body of knowledge in a subject discipline. He/she takes courses in education, which involves methodology of teaching. Lastly, he/she goes through a supervised teaching practice which is referred to as apprentice. This system has not produced the desired result for a Transformative educational system in a globalized world, innovation required for both for teacher pre-service preparation and teacher in-service training.

It is for this reason, the school-based teacher professional preparation and development is advocated. This enables schools and teachers to play a much larger role in teacher's professional development. This will eventually make the schools be the first to reap the benefits of generation of good new teachers. The cluster school-based teacher in-service teacher development is an innovation being carried out. It is a system of mentoring whereby teacher's educators and or professional teachers support teachers directly in their classrooms with intensive period of mentoring and discussion in teachers' meetings within the schools and across a cluster of schools to develop reflective practices and reflective practitioners. The goal of global competitiveness, demands that both the curriculum and the teaching methods to be more focused on developing generic and attitudinal skills, such as critical thinking and problem solving as well as promoting national reconciliation (Srikant, 2012).

Conclusion and Recommendation

Teaching is a profession, which requires expert knowledge and specialized skills, acquired and maintained through rigorous and continuing study. It also calls for a sense of personal and corporate commitment to the education and welfare of the students. A teacher has many roles to perform. Identification and standardization of these roles is helpful in evolving a teaching portfolio. Roles of a teacher are not static but dynamic as these continue changing as per the demands of the society. Various policies also limit or extend the scope of these roles. World is positive about its potential for economic and political progress in the 21st century. The trends and characteristics of globalization perhaps call for a total re-invention or repackaging of the teaching profession.

The Teacher in the globalized environment must be prepared to think globally and act locally in matters relating to education. He must be able to create a learning, friendly and animating environment in the classroom. The teachers must be able to

participate effectively in the contemporary ICT imposed revolution in knowledge creation, distribution and management. Schools exist to impart knowledge and skills. It is therefore imperative for schools to move with time in matters relating to knowledge creation and distribution. The current state schools on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) should be improved as a priority and national emergency. Teacher education policies and practices also need a fundamental overhaul in order to ensure that modern teachers are produced from Teacher Training Institutions. Computer training and Information Technology must be central components in Teacher preparation programs. The ideal teacher in a globalized world must be an expert in a subject area as well as an expert in the use of Information Technology in teaching learning situations.

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MANAGING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF NHGSFP FOR INCREASED SCHOOL ENROLMENT IN ADMINISTRATION OF PUPILS IN PRIMARY 1-3 IN PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN AROCHUKWU LGA OF ABIA STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated managing the implementation of NHGSFP for increase school enrolment in administration of pupils in primary 1-3 in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey design with a total population of 500 comprising of 59 head teachers and 441 teachers. Out of this population, a total of 200 respondents were sampled (24 head teachers and 176 teachers) using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument was a rating scale titled: Implementation of NHGSFP for Increased School Enrolment in Administration of Pupils in Primary 1-3 in Public Primary Schools Questionnaire (INHGSFPAPPSQ), validated by validates. A four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points), Disagree (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (1 point) was used for the research questions. The decision point was 2.50. The reliability of the instrument was established at 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha. Three research questions guided the study. The questionnaire was used to elicit responses from the respondents. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to analyze the research questions. Based on the findings, it recommended among others that the head teachers should effectively maintain the cooks' attendance register, adequate monitoring and evaluation of the programme to ensure effective implementation, adequate funding of the school feeding programme.

Key Words: Management, Primary School, NHGSFP, Implementation, School Enrolment and Administration

Introduction

Education is viewed as an indispensable catalyst that strongly influences the development and economic fortunes of nations and the quality of life of its people. In Nigeria, education is the instrument par excellence for national development (FGN, 2013). It is the belief of the Nigerian nation that education is the vehicle that can drive the nation to national development (Kalu and Nwaneri, 2019). Education is of cardinal importance to many societies. Ihum (2021:99) while citing Bonang, opines that education inculcates the skills that are required to provide a means of livelihood to those with such skills. This is the most important reason human beings, right from the ages, have engaged in the training of younger generations to prepare and equip them with right skills and norms that are generally acceptable by the society for productive living. According to Anyaogu (2021), education is the eye, the way and the means for the development of any nation. Anyaogu further states that education in Nigeria as stated by the Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013:4) is an instrument for excellence for effective national development. Education has witnessed active participation by non-governmental agencies, communities, organizations, individuals as well as the government.

Education in Nigeria is deeply rooted in the philosophy and goals of the nation. Hence, Nigeria's philosophy of education (2013) is based on the development of the individual into a sound and effective citizen; the full integration of the individual into the community and the provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens of the country at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels both inside and outside the formal school system (Anyaogu, 2021:41). Primary education in Nigeria is the first stage in Nigerian education system and is the type of education for children between 6 to 11 years. Primary education precedes the secondary level of education and provides the foundation for the other two levels of the Nigerian education system (Isiozor, Emeribe & Anyanwu, 2017: 33). Anyanwu (2021) asserted that since the rest of the education system is built upon it, the primary level is the key to the success or failure of the whole system. Isiozor et al (2017:33) asserted that the major goal of primary education is to achieve literacy and numeracy that would guide further education development. They further state that according to the National Policy on Education (FRN; 2013), the duration for primary education shall be 6 years. The graduates of the primary schools gain the primary school leaving certificate, otherwise known as the First School Leaving Certificate and qualified graduates proceed to gain admission into secondary schools.

The goals of primary education are as follows; inculcate permanent literacy and numeracy and ability to communicate effectively; lay a sound basis for scientific and reflective thinking; give citizenship education as a basis for effective participation in and contribution to the life of the society; develop in the child the ability to adapt to the child's opportunities for developing manipulative skills that will enable the child function effectively in the society within the limits of the child's capacity; provide the child with basic tools for further educational advancement including preparation for trades and crafts of the locality (FRN, 2013). In pursuance of the above-named goals, primary education shall be tuition free, universal and compulsory (Anyaogu, 2021).

The National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP) is a Federal Government funded initiative in 2016. The Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs,

Disaster Management and Social Development took over the supervision of the programme when the Ministry was created in 2019. The programme is being implemented by the State Government social investment programme. It is aimed at delivering a cost-effective feeding programme, with specific focus on increasing school enrolment, reducing the fall-out of malnutrition, empowering cooks while supporting local agriculture through a value chain that supports small-holder farmers, thereby stimulating economic growth in Nigerian communities and reducing out-of-school children. The programme provides one free meal per day to public primary school children in government owned schools, especially pupils in Primary 1-3 and Pupils on the Alternate School Programme. The NHGSFP makes use of farm produce locally grown by smallholder farmers in each state to provide children nutritious mid-day meals on every school day. The programme links local farmers to the education sector by facilitating their access to the school feeding market (<https://www.fmhds.gov.ng>). According to Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing World Bank (2013) School feeding programmes have been defined as targeted social safety nets that provide both educational and health benefits to the most vulnerable children, thereby increasing enrolment rates, reducing absenteeism, and improving food security at the household level.

The objectives of the programme are thus; through the supply of one-free nutritious meal a day to school children, this helps with the provision of the daily nutrients requirements that children need to develop and grow properly; it provides an incentives to increase both enrolment of school aged children into formal schools, as well as the active participation of school children during school hours in various communities across the nation; the employment of cooks from the communities to cook the meals for the school children and purchasing of farm crops produced locally is one of the benefits. This produces a positive ripple effect in the local economy, by providing a form of stimulus, the purchasing power of the local population in the various participating communities; provides empowerment opportunities for women, thereby improving family and local economy (<https://www.fmhds.gov.ng>).

The National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP), according to the Federal Ministry of Humanitarian Affairs, Disaster Management and Social Development is aligned with SDG Goals. By 2030, ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective Goal-4 effective learning outcomes; ensure that all girls and boys have access to quality early childhood development, care and preprimary education so that they are ready for primary education. According to Anozie (2022) the NHGSFP is a strategic intervention programme with tremendous benefits for a variety of beneficiaries and stakeholders and it can only succeed through multi-sectorial partnership and cooperation in line with established standard of procedure at all levels of implementation. He further states that a good knowledge of concept and of the governance of the programme will enhance capacity of stakeholders to participate effectively and address any misconception. Okwanihe (2022) asserted that United Nations World Food Programme (WFP) says the NHGSFP has significantly increased school enrolment across Nigeria. Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Taylor and Ogbogu, (2016); Alabede et al, (2020) asserted that the programme aims to improve the enrollment of primary school children and reduce the drop-out rate, currently estimated

at over 30 percent. Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Adebisi, Adebisi, Jonathan & Asogwa. (2019); WFP (2021); Uduji and Okolo-Obasi (2021) further asserted that most of this shortage is due to poverty and this programme is built to address the most important basic need of school children and provide the nutrition needed to engage successfully with their education. According to Anozie (2022) the feeding cycle is 20 days every month during the school term. The meal is 100% free as the Federal Government of Nigeria bears the full cost of feeding pupils in Primary 1-3. Anozie further states that the Cooks on the HGSFP receives funds fortnightly and their responsibilities are to: Purchase the required ingredients for cooking based on the menu approved by the state; Prepare meals for their assigned pupils in a hygienic and clean; Arrive in the school prior to break; Sign the feeding attendance sheet of pupils served on a daily basis; Wash food bowls after meals and store in covered. Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) asserted that NHGSFP makes significant contribution to improving the health and educational status of rural school children, stimulate job creation and boost rural economy. This implies that a well-designed and integrated home-grown school feeding programme can make significant contribution to improving food security at the household level, spurring job creation and boosting agricultural markets. This suggests the need for a purposeful engagement and support from all stakeholders to ensure the success of home-grown school feeding programmes. Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Diallo asserted that it is a vision to reduce hunger among school children, so that hunger is not an obstacle to their development. Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Langinger, 2011; Mwenda and Gori, 2019; Sumberg and Sabates-Wheeler, 2011) asserted that this has provoked further studies of how school feeding should be implemented in developing countries to reach all hungry school children in need, in a way that is sustainable. Hence, Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Evans and Harper (2009) asserted that recent rethinking by the World Bank and World Food Programme incited a shift toward long-term, sustainable solutions that depend more upon local resources, local capacity, and community participation. This indicates that NHGSFP should be adequately managed for increase school enrolment to ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes.

Enrollment means the act of complying with state and local requirements relative to the registration or admission of a child for attendance in a school within a local school division. This term also means registration for courses within the student's home school or within related schools or programs. The primary aim of any education system is to ensure that all children of suitable age are enrolled in school and are attending. Achieving Universal participation of children in schooling is the core focus of the governments. (UNESCO Institute for Statistics <http://uis.unesco.org/>)

The value for School enrollment, preprimary (% gross) in Nigeria was 23.46 as of 2018. Net enrollment rate is the ratio of children of official school age who are enrolled in school to the population of the corresponding official school age. Primary education provides children with basic reading, writing, and mathematics skills along with an elementary understanding of such subjects as history, geography, natural science, social science, art, and music. <https://www.indexmundi.com/facts/nigeria/school-enrollment>

Management is one of the most important human activities ever. Management is essential for the coordination (galvanizing) of human efforts and activities to achieve goals that are impossible to achieve acting alone (Abraham, 2017). Management, according to Abraham (2017), while citing Weihrich, Cannice & Koonz is the process of designing and maintaining an environment in which individuals, working together in groups, efficiently accomplish selected aims. According to Nzegebulem and Onyeagbako (2019), management could be seen as the technique employed when coordinating and carrying out the administrative and managerial functions of an institution through planning, directing and controlling in order to successfully accomplish its goals and objectives. Thus, every school administrator has to ensure that both human and material resources are managed so as to achieve its goals and objectives. According to Anyaogu (2021) administration is the means by which formal goals are achieved through cooperative human efforts. Anyaogu (2021) while citing Anukam define administration as a process of getting things done in an organizational setting using available human and material resources. This process involves decision-making, organizing, communicating, directing, coordinating and evaluation carried out to achieve organizational goals. Anyaogu (2021) states that educational administrators major role rests with the effective and efficient implementation of plans, policies and programmes for the benefit of education. Policy implementation involves the act of putting the adopted policies into action; translating the policy statement into practical reality. It is the task of translating policy statement into operation and action by all concerned (Odionye, 2019). According to Odionye (2019), while citing Uzodinms, implementation of policy is crucial for the achievement of goals, aims and objective because policies (no matter how good and relevant they may seem) are good as not being in existence if they are not implemented at all or are poorly implemented. In order words, implementation stage is a very critical stage in policy cycle and should be undertaken with utmost seriousness.

The head teacher is the chief management officer in the school system. He oversees, coordinates and supervises the activities of other teaching and non-teaching staff in the primary school to achieve the educational goals (Isiozor, Emeribe & Anyanwu (2017: 34). According to Ibe (2016) the head teacher inspires subordinates by exemplary character or behaviour and show unalloyed commitment to the demands of their offices. Isiozor et al (2017) asserted that there is Assistant Head teacher who provides administrative assistance. In addition to the office of the Assistant Head Teacher, the primary school management allows the operation of committee system (delegation) as a way of facilitating the school administration and supporting the Head teacher toward achieving efficiency. Such committees may include welfare committee, disciplinary committee and extracurricular/sports committee. They further states that to enhance attendance and punctuality, the head teacher maintains the teachers' attendance register and staff movement book, which indicates staff entry and exit time. More so the head teachers motivate the staff to work through the provision of incentives and ensure the availability of relevant materials to facilitate teaching and learning activities.

According to Nnabuo (2022), the school executive can relate effectively to the community my making the school 'open' operation. Duze and Ogba (2013) note that where school leaders promote effective school-family-community partnerships, they support student learning, achievement and health development since families and

community members see the school strength, weakness and needs. Ogundele, Oparinda & Oyewale (2012) while citing Agbaja asserted that active community participations enhance effective school administrations, that involvement of parent in decision making process of the school bring about school discipline, development of school facilities, teachers job performance and students' academic performance. This can also facilitate increase school enrolment and reduction in out-of-school dropout.

Statement of the Problem

The National Home-Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSFP) aims to deliver a government-led, cost-effective school feeding programme using food that is locally grown by smallholder farmers, with specific focus on increasing school enrolment, reducing the fall-out of malnutrition as well as stimulating economic growth in Nigerian communities and reducing out-of-school children. In the face of debilitating economy, growing poverty, hardships, occasioned by years of poor policies and mismanagement of the nation's resources, the greatest challenge of many families has been how to cater for their children, especially feeding in the advent of COVID-19 pandemic. The study therefore sought to explore ways of managing NHGSFP implementation to increasing school enrolment, reducing the fall-out of malnutrition as well as stimulating economic growth in Nigerian communities and reducing out-of-school children.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to examine the implementation of NHGSFP for increase school enrolment in administration of pupils in primary 1-3 in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State. Specifically, the study will:

1. Determine the impacts of NHGSFP on pupils in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State.
2. Determine the activities of the food vendors in implementing the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State.
3. Ascertain measures to be adopted to ensure effective implementation of the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State.

Research Questions

1. What are the impacts of NHGSFP on pupils in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State?
2. What are the activities of the food vendors in implementing the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State?
3. What are the measures to be adopted to ensure effective implementation of the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State?

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive survey design with a total population of 500 comprising of 59 head teachers and 441 teachers. Out of this population, a total of 200 respondents were sampled (24 head teachers and 176 teachers) using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument was a four-point rating scale titled: Implementation of NHGSFP for Increase School Enrolment in Administration of Pupils in Primary 1-3

in Public Primary Schools Questionnaire (INHGSFPAPPSQ), validated by validates. Strongly Agree (4 points), Agree (3 points). Disagree (2 points) and Strongly Disagree (1 point) was used for the research questions. The decision point was 2.50. The reliability of the instrument was established at 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha. Three research questions guided the study. The questionnaire was used to elicit responses from the respondents. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to analyze the research questions.

Results

Research Question 1 What are the impacts of NHGSFP on pupils in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State?

Table 1: Mean rating scores and Standard Deviation of the impacts of NHGSFP on pupils in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA?

S/N	Items	X	SD	Decision
1.	The enrolment rate in the school increase	2.63	.97	A
2	significantly			
	School feeding motivate the pupils to come to school	2.71	.86	A
3	much earlier than before	2.51	.76	A
4	School feeding programme successfully check	2.58	.77	A
5	truancy	2.96	.87	A
6	School feeding programme improve learning	2.95	.85	A
7	outcomes	2.50	.73	A
8	The meal has attracted pupils to attend classes daily			
	There is increase in punctuality	2.54	.56	A
9	There is continuous stay of pupils in school			
	The school feeding has great impact on academic			D
10	Performance	2.33	.58	D
	The existing educational facilities are no longer sufficient	2.38	.62	
	due to Increase in enrolment			
	The pupils do feel satisfied after eating the meal			
	Cluster mean	2.61	.69	A

Table 1 result revealed that items 1-8 have high mean score above the criterion mean for decision except items 9 and 10. The Cluster Mean of 2.61 and Standard Deviation of .69 indicated Agree on the impact of the NHGSFP on pupils in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA.

Research Question 2 What are the activities of the food vendors in implementing the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State?

Table 2: Mean rating score and Standard Deviation of the activities of food vendors in implementing the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA

S/N	Items	X	SD	Decision
11.	There is high quality of meal served in school	2.05	.46	D
12.	There is sufficient food rations	2.01	.76	D
13.	The pupils are fed daily in every school day	1.96	.72	D

14	The cooks sign the feeding attendance sheet of pupils served on a daily basis	2.06	.48	D
15	The cooks follow the school meal menu strictly	2.45	.63	D
16	The cooks sign attendance registers daily	2.24	.58	D
17	Cooks show up on daily basis to execute the feeding system	2.49	.50	D
18	The cooks package the food well in a cooler	2.37	.61	D
19	The cooks arrive in the school prior to break	3.04	.93	A
20.	Food items served are sourced locally	3.56	.67	A
Cluster mean		2.42	0,63	D

Analysis from Table 2 revealed that the respondents disagreed on items 11-18 with mean rating of 2.05, 2.01, 1.96, 2.06, 2.24, 2.49, 2.45 and 2.37 respectively. But agreed on items 19 and 20 with mean rating of 3.04 and 3.56. The cluster mean of 2.42 and standard deviation of 0.63 indicated disagreement in the activities of the food vendors in the implementation of NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State.

Research Question 3 What are the measures that should be adopted to ensure effective implementation of the NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State?

Table 3: Mean rating score and Standard Deviation of the measures that should be adopted to ensure effective implementation of NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA

S/N	Items	X	SD	Decision
21	The Head teacher should effectively maintain the cook's attendance register	3.33	.84	A
22	Adequate monitoring and evaluation of the programme	2.70	.89	A
23	The community should effectively involve in the implementation of the programme	3.59	.54	A
24	There should be effective communication channels among the school authority, cooks and the community	2.93	.80	A
25	There should be prompt and regular payment of teachers' salaries to increase teachers' motivation	3.52	.64	A
26	There should be adequate supervision of meal preparation sites	2.95	.87	A
27	Food quality control need to be enhanced	2.85	.77	A
28	There should be adequate funds for the cooks	2.67	.93	A
29	NOA should be effectively mobilized for sensitization of the programme	2.91	.75	A
30	The smallholder farmers should be effectively involved in the value chain	2.64	.94	A
Cluster mean		3.01	0,80	A

Data in Table 3 reveal that all the items, achieved mean ratings ranging between 2.64 and 3.59 and standard deviation ranging between 0.54 and 0.95. The cluster mean of 3.01 and standard deviation of 0.80 indicates that they all agreed on the measures that should be adopted to ensure effective implementation of NHGSFP in public primary schools in Arochukwu LGA of Abia State.

Discussion of Findings

In Table 1, findings revealed that the enrolment rate in the school increased significantly as evidenced in the mean rating 2.63. The school feeding motivates the pupils to come much earlier than before as evidenced in the mean rating 2.71. The evidence from this study also pointed to the fact that the school feeding programme successfully check truancy (with mean rating 2.51) and the meal has attracted pupils to attend classes daily as evidenced in the mean rating 2.96. This is in line with Okwanihe (2022) who asserted that United Nations World Food Programme (WFP) says the NHGSFP has significantly increased school enrolment across Nigeria. To that end, Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Taylor and Ogbogu, (2016); Alabede et al, (2020) asserted that the programme aims to improve the enrollment of primary school children and reduce the drop-out rate. Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Adebisi, Adebisi, Jonathan & Asogwa. (2019); WFP (2021); Uduji and Okolo-Obasi (2021) further asserted that most of this shortage is due to poverty and this programme is built to address the most important basic need of school children and provide the nutrition needed to engage successfully with their education. The researcher is of the opinion that NHGSFP should be adequately managed for sustainable school enrolment to ensure the pupils complete free, equitable and quality primary education.

On the activities of the food vendors in implementing the NHGSFP, question items 11 to 18 were not accepted. The respondents disagreed that there is high quality of meal served in school, there is sufficient food rations, the pupils are fed daily in every school day, the cooks sign the feeding attendance sheet of pupils served on a daily basis, and the pupils are fed daily in every school day. They also disagreed that the cooks sign the attendance register daily and show up on daily basis to execute the feeding programme. This findings disagreed with Anozie (2022) who opined that the feeding cycle is 20 days every month during the school term and the cooks sign the feeding attendance sheet of pupils served on a daily basis. Our respondents agreed that the cooks arrive in the school prior to break while food items served are sourced locally. This findings agrees with Anozie (2022) who opined that the cooks arrive school prior to break and Okolo-Obasi & Uduji (2022) while citing Evans and Harper (2009) who asserted that recent rethinking by the World Bank and World Food Programme incited a shift toward long-term, sustainable solutions that depend more upon local resources, local capacity, and community participation.

The result of Table 3 shows that on the measures to be adopted to ensure effective implementation of NHGSFP, our respondents agreed that the head teachers should effectively maintain the cooks attendance register, adequate monitoring and evaluation of the programme, the community should be fully involved in its implementation, effective communication channels between the school authority, cooks and the community, adequate supervision of the meal preparation sites, adequate motivation and funding of the programme as well as effective sensitization of the programme. This

agrees with Nzegebulem and Onyeagbako (2019) who asserted that every school administrator has to ensure that both human and material resources are managed so as to achieve its goals and objectives. In support of the above assertion, Anyaogu (2021) while citing Anukam, opined that this process involves decision-making, organizing, communicating, directing, coordinating and evaluation carried out to achieve organizational goals. The findings also agrees with Anozie (2022) who asserted that the NHGSFP is a strategic intervention programme with tremendous benefits for a variety of beneficiaries and stakeholders and it can only succeed through multi-sectorial partnership and cooperation in line with established standard of procedure at all levels of implementation. He further states that a good knowledge of concept and of the governance of the programme will enhance capacity of stakeholders to participate effectively and address any misconception.

Conclusion

The development of communities and economies is interlinked with the growth of education. The National Home-grown school feeding programme (NHGSFP) aimed at providing both educational and health benefits to the most vulnerable children cannot be achieved without proper administration of primary school systems, partnership and cooperation of all the stakeholders involved in its implementation. The implication of effective implementation of the school feeding programme is to increase school enrolment and the attainment of the goals of primary education.

Recommendations

1. The Head teacher should effectively maintain the cooks' attendance register
2. Adequate monitoring and evaluation of the school feeding programme to ensure effective implementation.
3. Adequate funding of the school feeding programme
4. Proper sensitization of the programme

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ASPIRATION FOR ADVANCEMENT OF SCIENCE EDUCATION IN NIGERIA AND INSECURITY: THE NEED FOR PEACE EDUCATION

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Abstract

Our current dilemmas are related to the culture of violence, conflicts and war which poses a great danger to our existence resulting to upsurge of insecurity leaving the country with lots of setbacks particularly as it dares to advance in science education. Every war begins in the minds of men; it is in the minds of men that the defense of peace must be constructed since if we must reach peace, we must teach peace. The ultimate solutions of these problems are in the consciousness of citizens of the society to convert their culture of conflicts, abuses, violence, and corruption which sum up to insecurities to students and parents alike, to peaceful and prosperous societal thirst for development and growth by solving our problems with discussion and understanding. Therefore, we must transform the culture of violence, conflicts and war into a culture of nonviolence, peace and respect for others which is the fundamental goal of peace education which is the thrust of this paper. Conclusion and some recommendations were made in order to appreciate the need of peace education for every individual.

Key Words: Advancement, Science Education, Insecurity, Peace Education

Introduction

The measure of a nation's advancement is not through physical development as maybe seen in the number of buildings it has, the roads laid down, or bridges constructed amongst others but by the human resources developed by the nation through a well-defined system of education which create sustainability as a result of the boost in human resources development (Ayeni, 2021). According to Lawrence (2019), education is a lifelong process by which an individual develops all his capabilities and become useful to himself, his fellow beings and thus contribute to the development of the society in which he belongs through the process of acquiring knowledge and ideas that shape and condition man's attitude, actions and achievements. It could also be referred to any process which are carried out in schools formally, or informal or non-formal educational way, which develop children or adults, which are in broader context develop the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values leading to behavior change (Muhammed, 2020). It is the art of the utilization of knowledge for complete living through developing the child's moral, physical, emotional and intellectual power for his contribution in social reform. These can be achieved by the process of mastering the laws of nature, utilizing them effectively for the welfare of the individual and for social reconstruction; it is power (Ayeni, 2021). Nelson Mandela as cited by Duncan (2013) opined that, "Education is the most powerful weapon which you can use to change the world". Therefore, for national development and particularly, sustainable development of every nation, a sound educational system must be upheld because it is the bedrock upon which any nation can be built; this insinuates that scientific advancement is germane for any nation that wants to be globally recognized. Science suggests ideas and technology operationalizes them. Science clarifies and justifies how an objective may be achieved. He maintained that, the "how" is translated into practical realization and from here, technology takes over and complements science. This therefore shows that there is a symbolic relationship between science and technology as science is a systematic search for truth provides the basis for technology. Without technology, science becomes verge and practically impotent and without science, technology in itself does not exist.

Science Education

According to Pember and Humbe (2009), Science Education is the process of teaching or training particularly, in school to improve one's knowledge about the environment, develop one's skill of systematic inquiry and also natural attitudinal characteristics. It is geared towards acquiring critical thinking and exploration, which leads to sustainable development. The main purpose of science education is to promote scientific and technological literacy which helps individuals develop the ability to apply scientific knowledge creatively in everyday life; make them familiar with some processes of science that are helpful in decision making and problem solving; help them understand scientific issues involved in handling household technological devices; help develop empathy, understand scientific issues involved in handling household technological device and make appropriate decisions that are related to health, nutrition, environment, education and lifestyles among others (Okafor, 2004).

The benefits of science education in Africa cannot be overemphasized and one major effect is in the area Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Science

helps humans gain increased understanding of how the world works, while technology helps scientists make these discoveries. Technology is the systematic application of collective human rationality to the solution of human problems through the assertion of control over nature; technology is the engine of growth. Technology can be traced historically to the beginning of time to be man's quest to improve his way and quality of life. One important attribute of technology is that it does not just happen but it is learned through application of man's knowledge, skills, tools and materials (Egbogah, 2012).

Advancement in Science Education

In light of the shared similarities existing between science and technology advances in science particularly in the 19th century has experienced a positive shift globally (Egbogah, 2012). This shift has been seen in the security as in the development of robot and drones for an enhanced safety of lives and properties of citizens, in the medical field where critical surgery are done and the use of ray for enhancing health (cancer) and breeding of species of crops and animals in agriculture to enhance yield and productivity amidst others. He maintained that the sooner Nigeria realizes that her escape from poverty is predicated on her investment in science and technology education, the better for her. He explained that there is a technological power vacuum in Nigeria waiting to be filled by whichever geopolitical zone that cares to mobilize its people through dedicated and selfless services. Essentially, technology is the primary engine of economic growth. It is the key and fundamental requirement for value addition to raw materials and people. It provides the key to unlocking any country's potential in terms of decreasing overhead costs associated with out sourcing and creating employment opportunities.

Egbogah (2012), further stated that Science and Technology Education will not only prepare the Youths of Nigeria and indeed any other nation, for fulfilling career prospects, but also train their minds to address social problems with scientific minds. Youths equipped with science and technology education are also endowed with high employment opportunities. Many developed and advanced countries did progress much because of their heavy investments on science and technology. Examples: The United Kingdom and France benefited immensely from the industrial revolution in the 19th century. Similarly, the United States emerged from an agrarian economy in the 19th century into an industrial superpower in the 20th century. More recently, Taiwan and Korea have exploited advances in silicon microelectronics from the early 1960s. China and India have emerged as industrial leaders in manufacturing and information technology respectively. Malaysia has also followed in the footsteps of these later Asian successes.

Egbogah (2012) and Ayeni (2019) emphasized that, the achievements of all these countries recorded is because they invested heavily in people, factories and infrastructure that provided the foundation for today's industries. These successes were all based on carefully designed roadmaps of plans and strategies. Unfortunately, till today in Nigeria as a developing country, technology is seen or viewed as a consumable-item, and not something that can be produced or created. Analysis of technologically advanced economics shows that at each level of the economy, science and technology provide the engine for economic growth. For example, in the case of primary products,

application of science and technology significantly increase the yield from agricultural production and mineral beneficiation. Similarly, new and existing industries do stimulate economic growth at the intermediate level, while the overall volume of activity at the tertiary level is amplified by increased use of science and technology associated with information technology and improved distribution/marketing networks (Pember & Humbe 2009). Therefore, the need for countries like Nigeria with the intention to grow, need to as a matter of urgency invest significantly in science and technology as the importance cannot be overemphasized. Regrettably, despite all the benefits derived from science and technology education in the world, its development seems to be drowning due to several challenges in Nigeria. This can be achieved by developing the talent, the human capacity required to compete in a globally competitive world of today hence the need to sustain the advocacy for science education in Nigeria.

No economy has ever become developed with this skew in their system of education and training for national manpower supply and/or human capital development. The utter disregard for science and technology education as an instrument of development has caused incalculable damage to our corporate existence (Egbogah, 2012). The problems of mismanaged economy, mass unemployment, collapse of health and educational services, insecurity, inflation, collapsed infrastructure amongst others can all be traced to the inadequate attention paid to science and technology in Nigeria. It is the lack of science and technology initiative by Nigerians that has led people to turn their energy to the lust for power, greed and self-destruction. Sadly enough, every Nigerian finds every other person guilty as charged, except himself or herself. Government's policy on education has among other issues emphasized but not driven the following objectives:

- (i) The training of the mind and the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies-both mental and physical as equipment for the individual to live and contribute to the development of the society.
- (ii) Ensuring that all schools are properly equipped to promote sound and effective teaching, and in particular, that suitable textbooks and libraries are provided for school. Secondary education should be six-year duration and be given in two stages, a junior secondary school stage and a senior secondary school stage. The junior secondary school (3-year duration) will be both prevocational and academic. It would be free. The senior secondary school would be for those able and willing to have a complete six-year secondary education.
- (iii) A greater proportion of education expenditure would be devoted to science and technology and a greater attention paid to the development of scientific orientation. However, it is common knowledge that three decades after these objectives were set out to improve the standard of education in the country, not only has none of the objectives been realized, but also the standard of education has fallen far below what it was before (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2014).

Educational Insecurity and Challenges

Educational security is the creation of awareness in form of information, sign or signal to students in any learning environment. According to Farlex (2013), insecurity is the ability of not been sure, certain or doubtful of a situation. It can also be when one is inadequately guarded or protected or unsafe. Insecurity is also a state of being subject

to danger or injury. In recent times, this country has suffered plaques of crisis, each leading to scores of lives lost and destruction of properties. For a nation to build a solid prosperous economy, and begin the ultimate march towards social and political growth, security is a minimum requirement. One of the distinguishing characteristics of nationhood is a state's ability to provide security for her citizens, defend her sovereignty and territorial integrity (Udah, 2012). Nigeria is a developing country with myriads of problems such as Boko Haram, banditry, farmers headers conflict and lots more menace that is crippling the growth and development of science education. Daily trust newspaper (2014) reported the kidnapping of 276 female students from the Government Secondary School in the town of Chibok in Borno State, Nigeria on the night of 14 -15 April 2014, the daily newspapers on April 15, 2021 also lamented on the continuous decay and what has become like an annual ritual the Sankara School girls which were abducted by the murderous criminal elements as they were preparing for their West African Certificate Examinations. According to premium papers in 2022 alone, over 1000 students have been abducted with the possibility of more to come. Of recent, the entire country is on a high watch for its lives and properties following their escalated activities in the country resulting to high poverty, general decline in students' enrollment, unemployment, child labour, child abuse and increase corruption in the country amongst many others. According to Eme (2009), Nigeria needs a policy that is stable, peaceful and safe enough from criminal assaults, murder, chaos, tyranny and breakdown of authority, so that the populace can face issues of development with vigor and courage. During these attacks, science infrastructures pivotal to the education of students are destroyed resulting in a major setback in the learning process. Some parents' lives are lost leaving the children uncared for, roaming the streets and unable to complete their education.

It is on record that Nigeria had witnessed a drastic and frantic insecurity challenges in the last few years. These are in various forms; communal, religious, political and socioeconomic with varying degree of casualty, mostly affecting innocent citizens of this country. According to Dembo and Mustapha (2012), the most worrisome fact is that this incessant violence apart from maiming innocent souls has imprinted agony, tension and aggression in the minds of Nigerians. They further stated that we live in absolute suspicious and constant presentiment of an impending disaster. Most economic activities have come to a halt and private businesses are crippling with the result of the inability of employers to pay their employees. Therefore, government function rarely take place in public compare to the previous years, these are direct aftermath of insecurity in the country (Dembo & Mustapha, 2012). Albert (2004) is of the opinion that, security problems include; communal violence, political assassination, electoral violence, youth militancy in the Niger Delta, Oil theft, illegal oil bunkering and sea piracy. Insecurity challenges according to Eme (2009) are; urbanization process, poverty, electoral frauds and poor management of national economy. Others may include; the judiciary, state of our health institutions and maritime security (piracy, illegal fishing and oil theft amidst others.

Peace Education

Peace education is the process of teaching people about the threats of violence and strategies for peace," and may take place inside or outside a classroom (Harris &

Morrison, 2008). More so, Muhammed (2020) stated that peace education is the process of teaching people about the threats of conflicts, violence and developing strategies for peace, so as to secure prosperity, harmony and integration in the society. Peace education seeks to address, prevent and to reduce all forms of violence and conflicts in society, whether overt or covert or structural, ranging from the interpersonal level to societal level and from societal level to global level. It is significant that the promotion and understanding of peace and tolerance through peace education as a basic component of quality basic education. Peace education is not only fundamental but should be considered as basic right of all children, and should not be considered as an optional or extra-curricular activity in school. We are passing from a critical point in the history of our country, solving the dilemmas of citizens has become a matter of our very survival in the country. Pronouncements for the solutions of these problems are more pressing such as conflicts, violence, not respecting the opinion of others, unaware of conflict resolution, and destruction of society are on the rise. We are living in a unique time of country history, a time that calls on humanity's sincerity, creativity, and compassion to solve our problems. There are a number of techniques and approaches to solve these problems, but ultimately, the roots of these problems are in the consciousness of citizens of the country and to change the culture of conflicts, violence and solve our problems with discussion peacefully. Captivating the country cultural approach, our current dilemmas are related to the culture of violence, conflicts and war, which is becoming a global human phenomenon pervading all aspects of life.

According to Gajanan (2019), the introduction of peace education into our school curriculum for both young and adult is the only way through which one can transform the minds of the students. One should, however, remember that the students might now show much interest in peace education if they are introduced to the subject directly. On the other hand, if we make them to participate in different activities that include peace education, they would definitely realize the importance of peace and need for it. He maintained that, mere statement like 'violence should be avoided' or 'violence leads to more violence' can never put an end to violence and result in peace. But if we succeed, through absorbing activities, in making the students understand the importance of peace and the ultimate of peace, then the chances of achieving the ultimate aim of peace are enhanced. Merely integrating peace component in the curriculum, however, would not be adequate. To make process of peace education an effective one, we need competent teachers who can make the subject both interesting and effective.

It is in the view of the researcher that, peace education becomes one of the fundamental components of quality basic education therefore, in school curriculum, peace education should be used for the process of promoting the skills, knowledge, values and attitudes required to nourish these behavioural changes that will make students both youth and adults to avoid violence and conflict, to avoid violence and resolve conflict peacefully; and to promote the circumstances conducive to peace as such attitudes may be at intrapersonal level, interpersonal level, within groups and at national level or international level. To solve our problems, we must transform the culture of violence, conflicts and war into a culture of nonviolence, peace and respect for others which is the goal of peace education. Changing our thinking and minds; our beliefs, perception and our point of view and to make deliberate and concerted efforts

to inculcate it in the curriculum in order to eliminate violence from society which are deep embedded in our way of life and culture.

As Albert Einstein according to Naboth (2012) stated that, “The problems we have cannot be solved at the same level of thinking that created them.” he believes that peace education which is key would further raise our life style, way and level of thinking and we would be able to solve our conflicts, disputes and wars peacefully through negotiations and discussions which is the fundamental feature that affects the way we see the world. He maintained that besides these other factors that affect our view and way of thinking, such as our religion, our family life, our society and our community, in all these factors the one that is key to change our inner, thinking, the way we behave towards others is the formal schooling. Informal education through our parents, society, communities, TV and other media, and places of worships has a profound impact on our personality and our view. School is a place where students spend most of their time, and we could equip them with the skills, knowledge and attitudes for developing a culture of peace through formal curriculum in school.

Muhammed (2020) described that we could make the change through Peace Education, because it calls for a deep-rooted shift in our philosophy of life and way of thinking. In formal school system peace education might be included as a subject, or as part of the hidden curriculum. Transformation of education system, school curriculum, or culture does not happen overnight, and may seem very disheartening. However, integrating peace education into classroom practices would reflect in our daily life immediately, and as an educator it would make an important contribution to promoting a culture of tolerance, respect for others and peace in community and in the whole world.

Imperatives of Peace Education

The process of teaching people about the threats of violence and strategies for peace,” may take place inside or outside a classroom. In the present Nigerian situation, which is constantly threatened by security challenges in different parts of the country, it is therefore germane that peace education be introduced into the curriculum of educational system. This calls for radical and urgent educational reform which is a necessary component of the peace process that could engender equity, justice and national unity (Omada & Mathew, 2015). Peace education, in the present circumstance, is inevitably necessary because every citizen should be educated so that he/she can understand the society and the dynamics of social harmony. Peace education should be inclusive because, educational inclusion is critical for maintaining peace as it can redress grievances that can motivate individuals to engage in conflicts/violence (Dupuy, 2011). He maintained that inclusive education here, especially within the ambit of “Education for All” perspective does not just refer to those with physical or mental disabilities and/or learning difficulties”, rather it should be seen from the systemic point of view which has to ensure that all pupils can have access to the whole range of educational and social opportunities offered by the school (so that they can) avoid segregation and isolation as well as prejudice.

In addition, education can only be seen as fully inclusive and able to perform its function of building peace if, it is codified as universal rights in national laws and policies, because peace entails the presence of social justice through the protection of

human rights including the right to education. Moreover, peace education is necessary for the evolution of a stable polity that would ensure a sustainable socio-economic and political climate needed for national development. In order to ensure equality and equity which can forestall direct or indirect violence, educational provisions and resources should be equitably distributed in terms of locations and numbers (Naboth, 2012). Where educational provisions are available to all, it will offer citizens ample opportunities to actively participate in the process of national development. This is because if educational opportunity in any country is not equal, invariably, it will create both immediate and long-term disparities that can metamorphose into conflict or violence that could be of high magnitude and dimension, or even result in full scale war (Omada & Mathew, 2015). For this reason, peace education cannot be divorced from moral re-orientation, which inclines everyone to do what is right and shun what is wrong. The individual's sense of what is right and appropriate must not be based on religious imperatives.

Conclusion and Recommendations

To solve our conflicts and problems, we must transform the culture of violence, conflicts and war into a culture of nonviolence, peace and respect for others which is the fundamental goal of peace education through emphasis that we teach and practice peace to reach peace. Many methods and approaches for the prevention and resolving of conflicts which generate into insecurity at various levels in Nigeria have been tried: the traditional and political methods, but none has adequately checked the upsurge of conflicts and violence. Instead, it appears that insecurity is increasing at an alarming rate and proportion in such a manner that it has not only threatened our national unity, our national development and importantly affected the growth of science education negatively. It is for this reason that peace education should be a veritable tool for the eradication of insecurity and the promotion of mutual relationships among Nigerians. Therefore the following were recommended that; Educational institutions should work in the direction of positive peace, The values of non-violence, cooperation, fraternity and patience should be taught at the school levels, government should support education reforms that bring about lasting peace rather than a surface touch approach leaving to upsurge in many instances and the inclusion of a model course in the curriculum on international and national understanding with reference to the cultural needs of the people.

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ROLE OF SCHOOL-BASED MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE ON PROVISION OF INSTRUCTIONAL FACILITIES IN JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL, KATSINA ZONAL EDUCATION QUALITY ASSURANCE, KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study evaluated the Role of School-Based Management Committee on provision of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary Schools, Katsina, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives, two answer to the research questions and two null hypotheses, which were tested to guide the study. Descriptive survey research design was used while simple random sampling procedure was adopted. Two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significant. The population of 1,668. Out of which 306 were selected as the sample size of the study. Adopted instrument was used for the data collection. Title "Evaluation of the provision and maintenance of Instructional facilities questionnaire" (EPMIFQ) designed by the researchers. The instrument was tested using split half method and Pearson Product Movement Coefficient (PPMC) statistical tool and reliability co-efficient of 0.899 was obtained Inferential Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to test null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant. Using statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 20.0 the two null Hypotheses tested were retained. Indicating that there is no significant difference regarding the role of school base management and producing of instructional facilities in junior secondary school. Therefore, no significant differences existed and the hypotheses were retained since P-Value of 0.076 is greater than the alpha value at 0.05 level of significant. Hypothesis 2 P-Value of 0.120 is greater than the alpha value at 0.05 level of significant, therefore the hypothesis was retained. No significant differences existed.

Key Words: School-Based Management Committee, provision, instructional, facilities and Junior Secondary School.

Introduction

The importance of Basic Education in educational system cannot be over emphasized apart from the serving as the link between primary and secondary education, it provides opportunity for a child to acquire additional knowledge, skills, and new traits beyond the primary level. Education is process of teaching and learning especially in schools to improve knowledge and development. It improves inculcation of worthwhile norms, values and right type of attitudes in an individual for the betterment of himself or herself as well as the society in which he or she lives. It is in view of this that the Federal Republic of Nigeria made in the National Policy on Education, provision of Basic Education for Children of School going-age which shall be “nine” years duration comprising “six” years in primary school and “three” years in Junior Secondary School Education comprises the Basic Education system policy in Nigeria.

The UBE programme was launched on (30th September 1999) by the then president of Nigeria, President Olusegun Obasanjo with the purpose of providing free and compulsory education for children in the primary and junior secondary schools in the country (Uyang, Ojong-Ejoh & Ejeje, 2017). To co-ordinate the implementation of the program at the States and Local Government levels, the acts called for the establishment of Universal Basic Education Commission (UBEC). The Universal Basic Education Commission was with the objectives of: developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion; reducing drastically the incidence of drop-out from the formal school system, through improved relevance, quality and efficiency; catering for young persons who for one reason or another have had to interrupt their schooling as well as other out of school children, adolescent through appropriate forms of complementary approach to the provision and promotion of basic education; and ensuring the acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy, manipulative, communicative and life skills as well as ethical moral and civic values needed for laying a solid foundation for lifelong learning.

The Junior Secondary Schools are educational institutions that occupy third stage or level of the basic education as far as Nigeria education system is concerned. They are designed for the Nigeria children that have completed their primary school education and transited to JSS either by examination or through the placement exercise as the case may be. This stage is a level in the basic education with duration of three good academic sessions. The National Policy on Education of Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) clearly stated that the objectives of Junior Secondary School education include to: provide the child with diverse basic knowledge and skills for entrepreneurship and educational advancement; develop patriotic young people to contribute to social development and the performance of their civic responsibilities; inculcate values and raise morally upright individuals capable of independent thinking, and who appreciate the dignity of labour; and inspire national consciousness and harmonious co-existence irrespective of differences in endowment, religion, ethnic and socioeconomic background.

The responsibility for funding the UBE programme rests in the three tiers of government, the federal, state and local governments. In spite of the shared responsibility, the funding of the programme remained an issue as what were estimated for renovating the existing school structures and building new ones are hardly disbursed

as such most schools have dilapidated structures with no libraries, laboratories and other support facilities (Ejere, 2011; Anaduaka and Okafor, 2013). As a capital-intensive project, education requires strict utilization and distribution of funds to make all the sectors function effectively. This point suggests the social relevance of education and, in a way the need for active participation of the relevant stakeholder in the sector. The increase in nation's population calls for the increased citizens' demand for education and as such education sector cannot easily and adequately be taken care of by the government alone. School as a social institution, the sustainability and success of education depend on the complementary participations of different forces, one of which is school-based management committee. In other words, to meet with and to achieve the objectives of JSS in Nigeria education system as stated above, there is need for active participation of SBMC to embark on school instructional facilities mobilization that serves as channels for a better academic performance of the Junior Secondary School (JSS) Students.

The Federal Government of Nigeria has recently introduced School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) in every primary and Junior Secondary School in Nigeria. This reflects a trend in international development for developed school management and increased parental/community participation in school management. This is a report of research conducted in March – April 2009 which sought to explore the implication of SMBC policy, with a particular focus on questions of gender, poverty and school governance through case studies of ten schools and communities in five states (Jigawa, Kaduna, Kano, Kwara and Lagos) as well as interviews at Federal, State and Local Government Education Authority (LGEA) levels.

The concept of School-Based Management (SBM) emerged from the recognition that a genuine collaborative approach to Basic and Secondary Education delivery is essential not only for the success of the education programme but, very importantly for sustainability of good practices. Indeed, the global reform of education of the 1990s and 2000s as a result of poor education delivery provided the impetus for the Nigerian Council on Education (NCE) at 52nd meeting directed that all schools should establish School-Based Management Committees (SBMCs) to ensure the participation of the communities in school decision making process. In very practical terms SMBCs are set up to ensure the success of community participation in Basic and Secondary Education and to the extent that school administration and mechanisms are decentralized thereby giving school constituencies viz: Principals, Administrators, Head teachers, teachers, parents, community members and Civil Society Organization (CSOs) greater control over the day-to-day activities in the school.

The SBMCs of Federal Ministry of Education are a statutory non-political committee of members who are ready to serve and actively support the schools and host communities. The main objective is to identify areas of challenges determine their effects on learners and how they prevent school administrators from effective performance of their roles. SBMCs provide good governance to the schools in line with Government plans and policies and in building good relationships with the communities. The institutionalization of SBMCs concept informed the need for the development of National School-Based Management policy (NSBMP) to fast-track the realization of qualitative education in Nigeria. Education Commission (UBEC) and

National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA). The initiative was supported by the Department for international.

Development – Education Sector Support Programme in Nigeria) DFID-ESSPION). The success of the policy was achieved due to broad consultations with professionals and experts in the field. The policy is to ensure that those entrusted with the responsibility and control of our schools have access to the information that is necessary for effective policy decisions and implementation. With his policy, the SBMCs will be better informed of our expectations of them, and act as a guide to other stakeholders on how to demand accountability from the committees. Community involvement in education has long been considered an essential component of pupils'/students' academic success. Parents, teachers, school administrators and policy makers all agree that community involvement boosts students' attendance and attitude towards learning, increase students' achievements and aspirations and decrease issues of indiscipline among students. The findings from this NSBMP will help in strengthening school-based management committees towards identifying school needs, design school development plans and mobilize resources for the achievement of the activities in the plan. The decentralization effort will help to improve the education sector in Nigeria as well as attain the sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by the year 2013.

School-Based management committee can be viewed as a formal alternation of governance structures, as a form of decentralization that identifies the individual school as the primary unit of improvement and relies on the redistribution of decision-making authority as the primary means through which improvement might be stimulated and sustained (Akinsolu & Onibon, 2010). In Nigeria, the School-Based Management Committee was set up to increase citizens participation in basic schools' management, as part of the efforts of school reform in Nigeria. Certainly, the intention behind School-Based Management committee is to implement democratic participatory decision-making. School-based management committees are group made-up of people within the school and the immediate members of the community which include pupils, teachers, parents and different personalities from different works of life in the community. The communities are to ensure quality both in educational inputs and outcomes and quality in learning environment for schools (Ogundele & Adelabu, 2010). This implies that SBMCs are meant to create a sense of community ownership in the development of schools and education centers and improve learning outcomes. School Based Management Committee (SBMC) are expected to meet regularly and organize activities to improve the way schools operate and support the state governments responsibility of ensuring quality education for all.

The roles of SBMCs in Nigeria are defined as what will take care of numerous challenges been faced in the planning and implementation of UBE programmes in primary schools. Undoubtedly, the SBMC is relevant at this time of Nigerian educational development (UBE, 2011). The need to provide, maintain and effectively utilize the school facilities bring about the involvement of School-Based Management Committee (SBMC) intervention in the school management affairs, to contribute toward the overall development of teaching and learning processes in the school system. SBMC are intended to contribute to the development, planning and decision making at the school level to improve learning outcomes.

In addition, for effective teaching and learning to thrive, there must be adequate provision and maintenance of infrastructural facilities such as classrooms, laboratory equipment, playground, hostel facilities, water and light supply. Adequate facilities in a school improve the quality of instruction and striving to create healthy school climate. School infrastructural facilities refer to buildings, equipment, textbooks, writing boards, laboratory equipment, as well as every structure that is required for effective teaching and learning. Therefore, the establishment of SBMCs becomes necessary as UBE programme placed serious constraints on school existing facilities and instructions that demand effective school management. Rhetorically, does SBMC contribute towards instructional development and for improvement education delivery in public junior secondary schools in Katsina State? The widespread systemic failure usually occurs in basic schools that make them unable to develop literate, numerate and self-reliant students (Pinnock, 2012). To this end, this study is set to find out the role of School-Based Management Committees on provision and maintenance of instructional facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Chester Bernard in his Co-operative Theory (1886 – 1961) stated that education for all is the responsibility of all therefore the responsibility of providing quality education to the younger ones is a duty of all community members as well as important stakeholders of education.

The importance of participation of organization and association in provision and maintenance of educational resources for effective management in schools cannot be overemphasized. Although the government allocations to education continue to rise in monetary terms, due to the increase in demand for education by the citizens, allocations have not really increased in per-capita term. Nigeria has consistently failed to allocate up to 20% of its annual budget to education as recommended (UNESCO, 2013). This underscores the need for well-to-do members of the communities where public schools are located to help source funds, material and physical resources for schools in their areas.

The effect of under-funding of public schools, provision and maintenance of available and relevant instructional facilities, coupled with the high rates of school enrolment, have taken their toll on schools' physical resources. The state of instructional decay in schools, school facilities badly dilapidated and inadequate. Physical structures for the teeming number of students are inadequate and there is a need for proper provision and maintenance of available resources to ensure their effective utilization, for school improvement. As such it becomes expedient to bring in the stakeholders in the communities such as the SBMCs, to play some active part in provision and maintenance of school physical resources in their local schools. Some authors have argued that some host communities are not informed of the role of SBMCs (Ayeni & Ibukun, 2013).

Hence, SBMC is a statutory management structure designed to empower members to oversee the management of schools in their respective communities and charged with the responsibilities which include monitoring of physical facilities for proper provision and maintenance and report to the local education authority on a

regular basis on development in the school (Muhammad, Agboola and Olugbenle, 2017). Thus, this implies that the formation of SBMC is with the sole aim of managing the schools in all ramifications, and also to encourage, philanthropic, politician, traditional rulers, business people and others to assist the school in the provision of educational facilities. Hence, this research is set to find out the role played by SBMCs in provision and maintenance of instructional facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to find out the role of SBMCs on provision and maintenance of Instructional facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, specifically, the study is to:

- 1) To determine the role of School-Based Management Committee on provision of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Nigeria.
- 2) Find out the role of School-Based Management Committee on maintenance of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following are research questions are raised for the study.

- 1) What is the respondents' opinion regarding the role of School-Based Management Committee on provision of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
- 2) What is the respondents' opinion regarding the role of School-Based Management Committee on maintenance of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used in the study. The data collected from the pilot test was used in testing the identified variables. Questionnaire was used as a means for data collection it also allows room for the small and larger samples. The advantage of using, survey it to obtain first-hand information by coming fact-to-face or in direct contact with the respondents. The population of the study is 1,668 out of which 306 were used as a sample size of the study. The population of the study is all teachers of Junior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Educational Quality Assurance and School-Based Management Committee. The research work was only limited to Katsina State, delimited to all Junior Secondary School teachers and all school-based management committee in the 25 Junior Secondary Schools in the Zone.

Stratified Random sampling technique was used and selected the sample of 306 by using recommended table for determining sample size by Morgan and Krcyies (1970). Out of which 1,193 teachers and 475 are school-based management comprised the sample size of the study 306. The instrument used for data collection was questionnaire designed by Sa'ad (2014) were adopted as an instrument for data

collection. The instrument was validated and tested as statistically fit for the conduct of the main study for testing of the reliability of the study the of the pilot test was subjected to reliability test using split half method and Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) statistical tool, reliability coefficient of 0.899 was obtained. The reliability coefficient was considered adequate for internal consistency of validity of the instrument using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Results

Hypotheses Testing

Hypotheses 1

There is no significant difference in the respondent’s opinion regarding the role of School Based Management Committee on Provision of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance Katsina State Nigeria.

Table: 1: One way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Role of SBMCs on provision of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Nigeria.

Status	sum Square	Df square	mean	F-value	Sig(p)	Decision
Between Groups	7.189	3	2.396	2.212	0.076	Retained
Within Groups	328.424303	1.083				
Total	333.215306					

From Table 1, the F-value is 2.212 and the P-value is 0.076 and alpha value at 0.05 level of significance. Since the P-value of 0.076 is greater than the alpha value at 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis is therefore retained. Thus, there is no significance difference in the opinion of respondents that School-Based Management Committee has role in the provision of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State;

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant difference in the respondents’ opinion regarding the role of School Based Management Committee on Maintenance of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance Katsina State Nigeria

Table 2: One way discussion of the result Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Role of School-Based Management Committee on Maintenance of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Nigeria

Status	sum Square	Df square	mean	F-value	Sig(p)	Decision
Between Groups	7.221	3	2.407	1.874	0.120	Retained
Within Groups	389.102303	1.284				
Total	393.931306					

From Table 2 above, F-value is 1.874 and the P-value is 0.120 and alpha value at 0.05 level of significance. Since the P-value of 0.120 is greater than the alpha value at 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis is therefore retained. Thus, there is no significance difference in the opinion of respondents that School-Based Management Committee has role in the maintenance of Instructional Facilities in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Discussion of the Result

Hypothesis 1 in Table 1 which states that there is no significant differences in the respondent's opinion that School-Based Management committee has role in provision of instructional facilities in Junior Secondary School in Katsina Zonal Educational Quality Assurance. The hypotheses therefore were retained since the P-value of 0.076 was greater than alpha-value 0.05 level of significant.

Hypotheses 2 Table 2 which stated that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinion that School-Based Management Committee has a role in maintenance of instructional facilities in Junior Secondary in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. Since the calculated P-value of 0.120 is greater than alpha-value at 0.05 level of significant therefore the hypotheses was retained.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers conclude that School-Based Management Committees played a very vital role on the provision of instructional facilities in junior secondary school through active engagement with the communities and other important stakeholders. The study also concludes that School-Based Management Committees play a very vital role in the provision and maintenance of instructional facilities in junior secondary schools through active community participation in maintenance process.

However, the study concludes that School-Based Management Committees played very important role in the Provision of Instructional facilities by participating actively in the provision of instructional materials in Secondary Schools, similarly the study concludes that school School-Based Management Committees play a very vital role in the maintenance of instructional facilities in junior secondary school through active community participation in maintenance process.

Finally, School-based management committees encourages Community participation in provision and maintenance of instructional facilities in junior secondary schools through active community participation in order to enhance effective teaching and learning in junior secondary school in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Nigeria.

Recommendations

In view of findings, the study recommends that:

1. School Based Management Committees should get more support from the community for ensuring provision of instructional facilities in junior secondary school to be sustained through active engagement with the communities and other important stakeholders.
2. School Based Management Committees should be encouraged by the government in ensuring mutual understanding between schools and host communities by organizing school-community campaign and orientation on the importance of active community participation on maintenance process of School instructional facilities in Secondary Schools.

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EDUCATION FOR CULTURE PRESERVATION AND CHANGE STIMULATION FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: A SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL DISCOURSE

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Abstract

This paper examined the socio-philosophical dialectic on education change stimulation in addition to culture preservation and the implications on national development in Nigeria. Obviously, preservation of culture is the primary desire of the society on education. However, since change is inevitable, education is also expected to function impeccably in the area of stimulating change for the sake of national development. These two areas of function are very important desires of the society but are at the same time, very conflicting responsibilities bestowed on education. Should education focus only on culture preservation while allowing social change to evolve by itself? Or, should education engineer change as an added responsibility for the sake of national development? How does education hang the balance scale in the centre without undermining the society? What are the challenges confronting education in performing these conflicting functions for the society, particularly, stimulation of change? This paper discovers that culture preservation and change engineering are both the manifest and latent functions which education must perform respectively for the society; that, the challenges of education in performing these conflicting functions, particularly, stimulating change include centrifugal forces, porous educational curriculum, political leadership factor and culture conflict, among others. One of the recommendations made is that Nigerians should shun centrifugal sentiments on issues bothering on social change if education must function impeccably in change stimulation as an added responsibility for the sake of national development in Nigeria.

Key Words: Education, Culture, Social Change and National Development

Introduction

Every tribal society in Nigeria has a way of life (culture) which must be learned and internalized by its members. The need to internalize the cultural heritage of any ethnic group is predicated on the fact that their culture has to be preserved and passed on to future generations as a legacy of the ethnic group. By such internalization and practice of their culture, they are able to maintain longevity. Culture preservation has been noted in most literature of sociology as the main function placed upon education by the society. Thus, education helps in providing socialization to societal members on the cultural norms, beliefs, customs and traditions of the society (Ibia, 2006). The performance of function in this manner makes education a conservative institution.

On the other side of the coin lies social change; social change necessarily occurs in human society as a result of constant human interactions with the environment (Ukpong, 2003). De-Wet (2003) viewed that no matter the level of conservativeness of any society, it is bound to experience change in so many ways including governance, economics, social inter-action and social inter-relationship patterns, among others. Thus, stimulating changes in the social structure and institutions of the society which inadvertently affect the patterns of social relationships and attitudes in the society obviously make education a pragmatic institution.

Udoh (2010) viewed that every society procreates and members are noted to be involved in constant interactions and inter-relationships with one another as members of the society in particular and, also with other people from other cultures in general. As such, the level of inter-actions and inter-relationship among members of the society in relation to the people of other cultures, by all intents, envisage expansions in the scope of the existing culture. Such expansion could be observed in the incorporation of new ideas and attitudes which manifest in industrialization, refined attitudes towards policies and policy implementation, good governance as well as incorporation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in every sphere of life particularly in this 21st Century. Such an expansion, as it were, therefore represents an index of progression of the society from one stage to the next. Therefore, whether the progression is slow, rapid, positive or negative, cyclical, vertical or horizontal, the fact remains that the society is not static (Udo, 2021). In other word, change is inevitable. Thus, the preservation of culture on the one hand and stimulation of change on the other hand, are all made easy in society as a result of education even though they appear to be very conflicting thereby making the nature of education to viewed by sociologists to be very ubiquitous.

As it could be observed, the Nigerian society has gradually progressed from the primitive state of its existence to the present industrialized and highly technologically developing state. Therefore, no matter the ubiquitous nature of the functions demanded of education, it is still evident that education makes the distinction between man and the lower-class animals. Udo (2021) said that the distinction between man and lower-class animals could be mirrored from man's level of rationality, consciousness, dexterity, knowledge and skills with which man maintains his culture and also creating enabling rooms for social change to occur for the sake of development.

Assumptions of the Study

This study assumes:

- i) That culture preservation and change engineering functions are two very important but, conflicting demands of the society on education;
- ii) That several challenges may underlie the performance of these conflicting functions, particularly, stimulation of change by education

Explanation of Terms

Education

Sociologically, education is often viewed from two angles – formal and informal. Informal form of education takes place in our homes, churches, peer-groups, mass media, among others, while, formal education takes place in a formally organized social setting, the school (Schaefer, 2005). The school is an instrument of formal education where individuals are trained and equipped with adequate knowledge and skills necessary for the development of self and the advancement of the society in all areas of considerations. Ezenwagu & Nwankwo (2020) described education generally as the aggregate of all the processes by which the individual acquires knowledge, skills and other forms of behaviours which of value to the society he lives. Udoh (2010) described formal education as the process by which the individual acquires the many physical, social, moral and technological capacities and competences demanded of him by the society for effective living and functioning in the society.

A closer assessment of education reveals that education is both individual and society centred. At the level of the individual, education strives to promote self-liberation by helping the individual to attain good and commendable positions on the social stratification and mobility ladders of the society. Yet, it should be rightly understood that education thus, serves to liberate the personality of the individual based on the extent to which the society permits (Joshua, 2013). The writer stressed further that the society does this by opening or closing opportunities for the individual's free participation within the value systems of the society which it uses the education to preserve; at the societal level, education serves to highlight and enshrine cherished values of the society. This it does by codifying the values of the society in question. Therefore, quite unlike in the traditional societies where the elderly family and community members were reckoned as people with high knowledge and moral virtue to act as teachers and leaders to the younger ones on the cultural tenets of the society, the case is different in modern times. Today, formal education has assumed the responsibility of serving as an agency of socialization on culture as well as change motivator for the society. Ofe (2005) stated that formal education provides consensus especially through teaching which makes use of a commonly acceptable lingual-franca (English language as adopted in Nigeria).

The use of a common lingual franca in school imbues a spirit of integration and unity among the growing children or learners who share a similar sentiment by thinking first of the Nigerian nation before self. It is also in the school where scientific and technological capacities are acquired by individuals whose high levels of techno-scientific reasoning abilities assist the Nigerian nation to attain the status of modernity and development (change). Ibe-Bassey (2013) noted that the high levels of growth and development (change) attained by nations of the world today have been the implications

of formal education. That is to say that formal education has eventually become an agency of culture preservation on the one hand and change stimulation on the other hand. Little wonder Mezieobi (2009) reasoned that social change engineering in society is a very serious responsibility of education though it is operated as a latent function.

Culture and Culture Preservation

Culture is the totality of socially transmitted customs, traditions, knowledge, material objects and behaviours, among others. Schaefer (2005) viewed that the culture of a people could be understood from the perspective of the people's ideas, religion, customs, values and artefacts. For example, DVDs, comic books, birth control devices, manner of worship, styles of building, farming, child rearing, gender roles, language, and so forth are all in line with specific cultures of different societies. Culture is very encompassing as its meaning goes beyond mere refined behaviour of a single individual or a fine art (dancing and drawing ability of an individual); but it includes all objects and ideas which are peculiar and commonly shared by the people of a group or society and which are generally accepted by them as ethical and normal (Udo, Udo & Ekanem, 2022). Thus, a society or ethnic group is defined by the fact that members share similar ideas and sentiments in relation to their culture (common ways of life). Education is therefore created and used by the society to shoulder the responsibility of preserving the society's culture through socialization. This to a great extent helps to protect the society's culture from damaging or going into extinction.

Social Change

Change as a concept is ambiguous and ubiquitous in nature because it occurs both in the culture and in the social structure of the society. And, just like education, social change can be manifest and can be latent; social change can be positive or negative, vertical, horizontal or cyclical; it can also be progressive or regressive. Okoth, Yambo & Onyagu (2016) opined that whatever is the direction social change follows, the fact remains that society is not static but, dynamic and always moving. In the light of this, Oruonye (2014) explained social change as the difference between what used to happen in the past and what is currently happening in the society. Following this manner of conceptualization of social change, there seems to be some levels of confusion regarding the way and manner which different people understand the term 'social change'. Udo and Ekanem (2020) said that to a lay-man, social change occurs when for instance, some college students or youths imitate the fashion of some western teenagers which perhaps they saw on the television; they also regard as social change when for instance when some male and female youths cohabit without being formally married as demanded by the cultural norms of their society. Sociologically, these are mere behaviour imitations; they do not constitute social change. The reason according to Udo, Emanu & Uyanga (2022) is because the behaviour of the campus students who imitate the western teenagers is just an adaptation or assimilation, while the male and female youths who cohabit without being married formally are rather acting in a way contrary to acceptable norms of marriage and matrimony of the (Nigerian) society. Sociologically, the behaviour of the couples constitutes deviancy.

Social change could be well understood from the sociological point of view as a significant alteration in social organizations such as power, stratification, division of

labour, act of God, among others that are not predictable on the basis of knowledge of pre-existing structures; it is a situation which tends to stimulate organizational adjustment in a given social system (Okeke, 2002). Udo & Udo (2022a) said that social change occurs when there are complete alterations in the ways of life and patterned network of rules and relationships within the structure of the society over time. This invariably means that there can be no real social change without cultural and institutional changes in which the whole community is involved. For instance, with institutionalization of western education in Nigeria since the early 19th century, much had changed in the Nigerian systems of religion, education, technology, transportation, farming, communication, family structure, marriage, social relations and social interactions among others.

Renowned structural-functionalists such as Bronislaw Malinowski, Radcliffe Brown, Talcott Parson, Coser (1956), and Robert Bale (1953) believed that the society is an organic whole. The scholars share a similar idea that as an organic whole the various parts of the society forming the whole are specifically functional for the survival of the whole (the society). This means that a change that results in an adjustment in one segment of the society must of necessity bring about an adjustment in the other segments or parts of the society. In this way, any change that occurs in the society becomes smooth and successful when all the parts or segments of the society agree or successfully adjust in line with the new change that occurs within the system. Udo & Udo (2022b) maintained that there is no true social change when some parts of the society find it difficult to adjust to a new change introduced, and when this happens, in the view of the writer, the society suffers a state of disorderliness, social dissatisfaction, social pressure and social disturbance.

Theoretical Overview on Why Change Occurs in Society?

The conflict school of thought led by Karl Marx (1917-1989) in their usual economic material dialectic binocular attributed most aspects of social change to economic factors. The conflict school holds that it is the unequal relationship and unequal distribution of economic resources and wealth of the society between the Bourgeoisie and the proletariat that always breed conflicts between the two classes. Karl Marx who is noted to be consistent in applying economic explanations to social issues argued that a change in the sub-structure of the society (economy) brings about a change in the super-structure of the society - politics, religion, government, philosophy, ideology and family as a resultant consequence of class struggle in the society. According to the exponent, while the Bourgeois class resists change in order to maintain its status-quo, the Proletariat strongly agitates and stands for change in their effort to break and dismantle the foundations of existing class structure in the society.

Education, Culture and Social change

Education is the instrument of socialization; in this case, the society influences education and its curriculum. This influence could be observed in the society's incorporation of its culture into education curriculum; the society funds and maintains the continuity of education by being open and certain in her demands which education is to pursue paramount of which is preservation of culture. In order to preserve the culture of the society, education teaches social mores, social norms, belief, ideas,

practices, customs and traditions and other aspects of the value systems that represent the social characteristics of the society. Should education also stimulate social change? Schaeff (2005) opined that education can help in change stimulation by creating awareness that helps society to achieve political, economic, social and technological development through propagating new patterns of behaviour, attitudes, ideas and practices such that position the society for reforms and adjustment necessary for national development.

Dialectic on the Role of Education in Change Stimulation

It is the role education should play in bringing about social change without undermining society by destabilizing the status of her culture that lies the variation in the positions of three renowned socio-philosophical schools of thought adopted in this study. The three schools of thought involved in the argument are the Conservative/Status-quo, the Pragmatic/Progressive school and the Neutral/Qua-Media/Reconstructionist school. Their arguments are summarized below:

The Conservative School

The Conservative school holds that education should not interfere with the process of social change. To the conservatives, education should only be reactive in its posture by not directly involving itself in bringing about change unless it is forced to do so by some external conditions and interventions. The conservative school believes that education is the most important institution which helps the society to preserve and transmit her cultural heritage which must be protected from the onslaught of modernization and Revolutionists who desperately agitate for change. The stand of this school is that the preservation of culture and transmission of same to the next generations is for the good of the society which is protected from either going into extinction or taking off from a negative and unproductive tangent. The school assumes that education should concentrate on teaching acceptance to established traditions, customs, rules, norms, institutions and authorities. It is the position of this school that education should not encourage innovations and social mobility. In other word, education should maintain a very slow pace if any, at encouraging social change which intermittently brings about the many trends of contemporary developments which the society fears as undermining its already established cultural structure and heritage.

However, a lot of scholars such as John Dewey, Jolly, John Locke, among others who are outward looking and change oriented have strongly criticized the position of the conservative school/status-quo on education and change in the society. The scholars hold that if formal education should stay without taking active part in stimulating change in the society it would make education a complete tool of the conservative class. According to the critics, the conservative class include traditional rulers, politicians and other people on the top echelon of authority positions in the society who may not want their structures, positions and statuses to be shaken or altered. Therefore, rather than seeing the involvement of education in social change from the standpoint of a necessity, the conservatives believe that education would be in complete control of the upper- and middle-class elites if allowed such freedom. The critics argued that since the conservatives have already assumed the control of the legal and political decision-making institutions of the society, it would be very difficult to have academic freedom

and expansions of growth in the area of knowledge by members of society, growth and development of education in particular and national development at large. Nigeria is of-course, a very good example of what is implied here.

The Pragmatic School

The socio-philosophical thinkers of the Pragmatic school hold that education should not only advocate or teach change but, should help to bring change in the society where and when necessary. According to this school, education should be the direct cause of change because its development has noticeable effects on ideas, levels of knowledge and the ways of life generally. The pragmatic thinkers see social revolution as the real function of education. In this case, education must be able to take active position on issues of change if it must help the society to come to terms with the complex situations of life particularly, in this contemporary time. Thus, the non-involvement in change engineering would rather make education to be reckoned as only serving the conservative motives of the elite class who control the policy making machinery in the society and would wish to maintain their status-quo only. The school advises that education should stand out of the conservative ideas which accordingly characterize backwardness, parochialism, stagnation, myopicism and utopianism; that, education should be pragmatically flexible to notice when change is necessary and introduce such accordingly for the progress and development of the society even for the future generations.

Accordingly, the pragmatic school's position on education and social change has been seriously criticized by members of the conservative school on the ground that it demanded too much power to be conferred on education. Thus, by demanding that education should be directly involved, agitate and initiate change in the society would rather mean giving too much power to education to operate without any control, checks and balances. This according to the critics would mean, selling the integrity of the society into the hands of revolutionists and agitators of modernity all of which can render the society insecure and unstable; that, the radicals and revolutionists, can with such powers, exert a tremendous influence and overthrow the society.

The Neutral/Qua-Media/Reconstructional School

The neutral school as the name implies holds that education should be neutral on issues of change. According to the school, education should neither help to bring change or hinders the introduction of change in the society. The school assumes that education should function in the direction of preparing societal members for change by increasing their level of knowledge. In this way, it is hoped that education would indirectly find solutions to society's problems one of which may be Change without undermining the society.

Critics seem to reason that the Qua-Media school has no direction. Critics particularly from the pragmatic school hold that the qua-media school has nothing to offer; that their argument is nothing but a vague and unrepresentative of either the society or education. The reason according the critics is because no matter what, education through the school must have a part to play in bringing about change in the society if not for any other reason, but for the fact that the cultural heritage of the society is institutionalized and must be transmitted from generation to generation using

education as an instrument. In an effort to do this, there is bound to be some alterations and modifications of some tenets of the culture that result to change.

Submission

From the foregoing socio-philosophical dialectic, it could be observed that there is heated argument, contention and disagreement among the schools as to the role education should play in social change stimulation in the society. However, it is obvious that education, culture and social change are virtually on the same social plain; one cannot do without the other. That is because while social change influences educational structures, organization and contents, education also in the same vein uses its structures, curriculum contents and organization to influence the structure and attitudes in the society. In this case, whatever social change the society brings forth can only be institutionalized through education. According to Udo et al (2022), the process of institutionalization helps to transform the general potentialities of change into historical realities. That means that education is a conserving institution seeking to mediate and to maintain the cultural heritage of the society; but, whilst seeking to conserve, education also ensures that as little cultural lag as possible occurs within the structures and institutions of the society. The implication is that education helps to create awareness such that enables the society to adjust or modify the contents of the old culture to accommodate new ideas, practices, behaviours and attitudes in tandem with the prevailing global technological, economic, political and social growth and development.

Challenges of Education in Stimulating Change for National Development in Nigeria

i) Centrifugal Forces

Nigeria is one of the nations in Africa that has so many cultures in line with the many ethnic groups. The people of these different ethnic groups in most cases, are observed to be reserving the greatest sentiment and loyalty for their ethnic cultures to the extent that people from these different ethnic groups always desire their cultures to be preserved and given a laudable attention and preference at the national level. Udo (2021) argued that the sentiment becomes a serious challenge to the Nigeria's education system that seems to be left on a cross-road with regards to change stimulation for the sake of national development in Nigeria. Such ethnocentric cum centrifugal sentiment influence the operations of the Nigeria's education system in almost all its ramifications. Mezieobi (2009) observed that the negative influence stems from the fact that most of the ethnic tribes with strong cultures often resist changes (incorporating new ideas and behaviours) that seem to be in contrary to their status quos in relations to their cultures and this directly affects national development in Nigeria. The author stressed further that this has been one of the serious challenges of education on change engineering for national development in Nigeria.

ii) Political leadership Factor:

Leadership in Nigeria is a political factor that has continued to dominate public discussions in recent times both at home and in Diaspora. Osioma (2011) accorded a credit to a purposive cum pragmatic leadership for its potentials in creating enduring impacts on education, socio-economic, political and technological advancement all of

which shape the future of a nation for change and national development. Udo and Atang (2014) agreed that promotion of human civilization, national consciousness and national development have been the propelling force of a purposive and vision-able leadership. The political leadership in Nigeria has not been able to protect the integrity of education particularly in the direction of engineering change. The fear might stem from their belief in the postulation of the conservative school that the elites and leaders must reject the idea of educational freedom and change as that may result to altering their positions of authority which they seek to maintain as a royalty. Political leadership factor as a challenge to education in stimulating change in Nigeria could be mirrored in the recent happenings where the educational sector (ASUU) has been on an elongated strike over funding of the University education in relation to other unfulfilled demands said to have been agreed between the ASUU and the FGN to be undertaken by the federal government of Nigeria which there are Memoranda of Understanding to that effect. Those at the top echelon of the Nigerian government are conservative elites who are exercising fear over the onslaught of modernization powered by education on existing political culture which might intermittently bring an end to their long reign and domination. The implication according to Ibe-Bassey (2013) is that when education which is supposed to drive change in all ramifications is played down on, national development may continue to elude Nigeria.

iii) Inadequate funding of the Education System:

Adequate funding is the pivot around which the wheel of success of any investment rotates. The Federal Government of Nigeria in her National Policy on Education confirms that education is a huge investment (FGN, 2013). This understanding might be the reason why the Federal Government of Nigeria had accepted the responsibility of seeing education as its responsibility for the sake of national development and economic stability. Besides, without adequate supply of funds it would be difficult to acquire the relevant human and material resources necessary to make the education sector effective. Against this backdrop, a closer assessment and evaluation of funding of the education system by the Federal Government of Nigeria reveals government's ineptitude tendency towards supplying funds for education. This is against the mandatory benchmark of the United Nations Education, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). The UNESCO mandated that countries should allocate at least 26 percent of their annual budget to education as a global hall-mark to fight illiteracy especially in developing countries which Nigeria is one (Akpan and Akpan, 2013 and Ekpe and Matthew, 2013). A review of national budgetary allocation to education from 2004 to 2018 could attest to the Federal government's failure to keep to the UNESCO agreement. Oweh (2013) affirmed that education sector in Nigeria still faces the problem of inadequate funding with regards to the benchmark advocated by UNESCO and this has a lot of implications on national development in Nigeria.

iv) Culture Conflicts resulting from the Multi-Cultural nature of Nigeria:

Nigeria is a multi-cultural nation. The multi-cultural nature of Nigeria, by every indication, has become one of the biggest challenging factors for the Nigeria's education system with regards to stimulation of change for national development. The challenge arises from the fact that every ethnic group in Nigeria expect their respective cultural heritage to be internalized, preserved and passed on to the next generations of the ethnic groups (Oruonye, 2014). A close observation reveals that in Nigeria, people of the

different ethnic groups often exhibit close sentiment and emotion for their cultures particularly, language, religion, customs and tradition. Ibia (2006) observed that culture consists of patterns, explicit and implicit of, and for behaviour acquired and transmitted by symbols constituting the distinctive achievements of human groups including their embodiments in artefacts. Thus, since the people of the different ethnic groups in Nigeria need their different cultures to be preserved and passed on to the future generations of their people, it therefore makes any change that is supposed to be positive nationally and propagated through education to be questioned more often by different ethnic groups that see such a change as undermining the safety of their cultures and continued existence of the ethnic groups. This cross road situation hampers the effectiveness of education in stimulating social change with a national outlook in Nigeria and this has enormous implications on national development.

Summary/Conclusion

This study was used to examine and evaluate the conspicuousness of the Nigeria's education system in performing the ubiquitous function of culture preservation and change stimulation for the sake of national development. The study found out that preserving culture only without stimulating change would make Nigeria to continue to wallow in under-development and stagnation. The role of education in causing change in the Nigerian society brought a serious argument and contention among schools of thought. While some of the school contended that education should fully be part of change stimulation, some contended that education should allow change to occur on its own; while, one of the groups contended that education should neither contribute play a role in causing change nor stay too far away from change engineering in the society. The study also examined some of the major factor that constitute challenges for education in stimulating change in Nigeria to include inadequate funding, poor political will and inconsistent policies as well as culture conflicts resulting from the multi-cultural nature of the Nigerian nation. However, the study concluded that education should be able to assist the Nigerian nation in stimulating change as an added responsibility to culture preservation if Nigeria must achieve national development.

Recommendations

1. Nigerians should shun centrifugal sentiments on issues bothering on education and its contents if education should be able to function effectively in change stimulation such that would bring about national development in Nigeria.
2. Political leadership factor has been a major challenge to the functionality of the nation's education. The nation's political leadership should begin to see education as a reliable instrument of change and national development in Nigeria.
3. Inadequate funding has been another serious challenge for effective functioning of Nigeria' education system. The Nigerian government should begin to take funding of education as a priority in her national budget if national development must be achieved through change stimulation.
4. Culture conflicts have been a very serious issue in Nigeria since every tribal group desires their culture to be given a place of priority in the national agenda. Thus, culture conflict has been observed to pose some negative impacts on change stimulation using education as a medium. Nigeria should therefore

develop a national cultural pattern which must be binding on all individuals and ethnic groups if education must be able to function as change stimulator for the sake of national development.

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INFLUENCE OF PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STYLES ON TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TO WORK IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ORON LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated influence of principals' leadership styles on teachers' attitude to work in private Secondary Schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The sample size of the study consisted of 302 respondents out of 1, 331 total population. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: Influence of Principals' Leadership Styles on Teachers Attitude to Work Questionnaire (IPLSTAWQ). The design used was cross-sectional, while the Mean, Standard Deviation and ANOVA were employed for analyses. The findings of the study revealed that there is a high significant influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The principals' autocratic leadership style had a moderate significant influence on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State and principals' laissez faire leadership style had a low significant influence on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The study recommended among others that the Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Education should mandate all principals to undertake refresher courses on leadership to improve their leadership skills. This will enable them to adopt the democratic leadership style and involve teachers in decision making in all matters regarding school administration in order to foster positive attitude to work by teachers.

Key Words: Leadership styles; Democratic; Autocratic; Laissez faire; Teachers' attitude to work

Introduction

The issues of teachers' poor attitude to work have been a thing of great concern in the educational sector in the entire country, different States including the secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, have been battling with these issues for long. Parents, government officials, and community leaders have attributed the causes to a variety of factors, which includes: absenteeism from school, attrition, high truancy rate, poor lesson planning, revolting against principal's choices,

inadequate dedication to teaching students, lateness to school, and frequent disagreement between principals and teachers (Adegbesan, 2013). Attitude is a mental or neural state of preparedness that has been developed over time and exerts a directive or dynamic impact on an individual's response to all objects. Attitudes assist to define how teachers see and understand circumstances, as well as how they act in them, particularly when it comes to school leadership (Vishal, 2014). Therefore, poor attitude of teachers to work can lead to low performance of students in class or may also bring down the name of the school because something is lacking in the students and in the entire school, which can be traced to the teachers' attitude towards their work.

Teachers are seen as an embodiment of knowledge; they have complete authority in the classroom thereby exercising certain power over effective teaching and learning in the school system. Poor attitude of teachers to work especially in Oron Local Government Area has contributed to the falling standard of education. With this falling standard, one is tempted to believe that teacher's attitude needs re-appraisal. Therefore, the focus of this study is to ascertain whether the leadership styles of principals play any role in influencing the attitude of teachers towards their teaching job.

Leadership is a means used in an organization for behavioral amendment. It regulates the goals of an organization and means of achieving them (Haruni and Mafwimbo, 2014). Therefore, leadership in an institution is seen as a motivator where one person who is the head motivates others toward the achievement of specific goals of the school. In the secondary school, a principal is the leader who coordinates, keeps balance and ensures the harmonious development of the whole institution by molding traditions for organizational goal achievement. As a result, school leadership involves a process of motivating and assisting teachers and students to work diligently toward the achievement of the schools' goals and objectives (Kane & Patapan, 2010). Therefore, the leadership style of a principal is the basis that defines a school's overall performance including the teacher's attitude. Principals' leadership style consists of a set of attitudes, attributes, and talents that are utilized in the management of the schools (Jalilizadeh, Abbasi, and Mohammadi, 2013). Principals' leadership styles indicate how they perform their responsibilities in a distinctive manner that distinguishes them from one another.

Leadership styles are the continuous patterns of behaviour that principals use with people at work. The leaders' pattern of communication with instructors is a blend of traits, abilities, and behaviour that is generally referred to as leadership style. There are various types of leadership styles, which include: transactional leadership style; servant leadership style; bureaucratic leadership style; Charismatic leadership style; Coaching leadership style; Collaborative leadership styles; autocratic leadership style; democratic leadership style; laissez-faire leadership style etc. Transactional leadership relies on a system of incentives and sanctions to inspire their followers. Autocratic and transactional leadership share a lot of characteristics (Assar Muhammad, and Kuchinke, 2016).

Servant leadership style prioritizes followers' needs and well-being, in other words these kinds of leaders put their organization, their team, and their community above themselves by adopting a serve-first mindset and growth approach. Bureaucratic leadership depends on the conformity of its followers, a clear chain of command, and rigid rules. As the name suggests, this is a type of leadership that is frequently used by

the government, the military, and other public and nonprofit organizations (Adeyemi, 2010). Charismatic leadership styles are characterized by a leader who persuades people with their appeal, communication abilities, and persuasiveness. In businesses that are going through a crisis or are having a hard time moving forward, charismatic leaders are especially beneficial because of their capacity to connect with people on a deep level. Coaching leadership is a manner that emphasizes cooperation, assistance, and direction. By guiding their teams through objectives and challenges, coaching leaders are committed to bringing out the best in their teams (Daresh, 2012).

Collaborative leadership styles encourage cooperation between individuals across organizational and functional boundaries. This leadership approach is meant to promote cooperation with other teams and departments in order to achieve common objectives. However, for the purpose of this study the focus is on the three most common leadership styles, which include democratic leadership style, authoritarian leadership style, and laissez-faire leadership style, which are the three major leadership styles (Kane and Patapan, 2010).

The democratic leadership style stresses collective engagement in policy development between leaders and followers. When making decisions about school matters, the principal must discuss and communicate with teachers. The principal makes every effort to make each teacher feel like an essential member of the school community. Teachers' morale and positive attitude toward work would be boosted under this leadership style because teachers would be inspired to work more since they are happy and have a strong sense of belonging as a result of being consulted by their principal (Adeyemi, 2010).

The authoritarian leadership style is also known as the autocratic leadership style. The autocratic leader wields power and makes decisions. The autocratic leader instructs group members on how to conduct themselves. The leader fails to keep a clear line of communication open between himself and his subordinates. He does not give authority to subordinates or allow them to participate in policymaking (Machumu and Kaitila, 2014).

The laissez-faire leadership style allows the group to make decisions without the leader's input. As a result, subordinates are free to behave as they choose. The leader's sole responsibility is to provide materials; the leader does not interfere with or engage in the group's decision-making process. Ajibade, Ajayi, and Shobawale (2017) highlighted that a laissez faire school principal has no clear objectives and does not provide professional leadership to his staff.

Nigeria, as well as Akwa Ibom State, is dedicated to the advancement of education standard throughout the country. However, some of the mechanisms used over time by the educational sector have proven abortive. Several conferences, workshops and seminars have been scheduled for principals and teachers towards effective leadership and teachers' attitude to improve their work, yet, there are still deficiencies. The importance of the various leadership styles in determining teachers' attitudes to work prompted the researcher to conduct this study, which aims at investigating the influence of principals' leadership styles on teachers' attitudes to work in secondary schools in Oron, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria (Omeke & Onoh, 2012).

Statement of the Problem

The Nigerian Government as well as Akwa Ibom State has severally organized workshops and conferences to improve the leadership styles of the school principals. Supervision has also been made in respect to this as a follow up of the conferences. Nevertheless, there have been challenges, which have reached the peak to an increase in poor leadership and poor attitude to work. Secondary schools in Oron are not exempted from these challenges, which is teachers' poor attitude to work. Some principals fail to recognize that the key to secondary school success is the commitment of teachers, which may be seen in their work attitude. Teachers' positive attitudes toward work could be influenced by their principals' leadership styles, which encourage proactive action in generating projects that motivate teachers to be highly devoted to their jobs. Teachers in Nigeria, especially those in Oron, are disgruntled, frustrated, uninspired, and unmotivated, according to the researcher.

The nature of principals' leadership approaches may be responsible for the truant behaviour of some teachers, laxity to work and playing hide and sick at work place. As a result, it is important to figure out the influence of principals' leadership styles on teachers' work attitudes. The focus of this study is therefore to assess how the principals' leadership styles influence teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools Oron, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

This study has general and specific purpose. The general purpose of this study is to determine the influence of principals' leadership styles on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Specifically, the objective of the study includes:

1. To determine the influence of principals' democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
2. To examine the influence of principals' autocratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.
3. To ascertain the influence of principal laissez-faire leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the influence of principal democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?
2. How does the principal' autocratic leadership style influence teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State
3. What is the influence of principal laissez faire leadership style on teachers' attitude to Work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁. There is no significant influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State

Ho₂. Principals' autocratic leadership style has no significant influence on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State

Ho₃. Laissez faire leadership style does not significantly influence teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State

Methodology

The study used cross-sectional survey research design. The research design is chosen for this study because the population of the study possesses different characteristics, which makes it diverse in nature. The total population of the study was 1,331 obtained from the nine private secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom. There are nine principals 381 teachers and 941 students from SS2 class at the time of conducting this study.

The sample size of the study consisted of 302 respondents drawn from the nine private secondary schools in Oron. In terms of the respondents, 9 principals, 196 teachers and 97 students from SS2 class of the nine sampled schools were chosen as a sample utilizing stratified proportional sampling procedures from the study's selected schools. A researcher's self- developed instrument titled Influence of Principals Leadership Styles on Teachers Attitude to Work Questionnaire (IPLSTAWQ) was used to collect data for the study.

The instrument was subjected to an expert's judgment for validation. The expert validated the instrument by checking for comprehensiveness, appropriateness and relevance of the items. The instrument was pilot tested on a small portion of the population that was not part of the sampled respondents but with the same characteristics of the sampled schools. The instrument was pilot tested on 30 teachers and 20 students in one of the schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State to determine the reliability of the instrument.

The researcher administered the instrument to the selected secondary schools with the help of two research assistants. Descriptive statistics, such as Mean and Standard Deviation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used in answering the research questions.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: What is the influence of principals' democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

The answer to the above question is shown in the Table 4.1 as elaborated below:

Table 2a: Mean analysis showing influence of principals' democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State as responded by Principals

S/N	Influence of Principals' Democratic Leadership Style on Teachers' Attitude to Work	\bar{X}	STD	Decision
1	Teachers develop good interest towards their jobs because they are involved in decision-making of the school by the principal	4.00	0.00	Agreed
2	Principal consults teachers regularly on issues that help them develop positive attitude to work	2.67	1.12	Agreed
3	There is exchange of ideas between principal and teachers which encourages teachers to work efficiently	3.44	0.53	Agreed
4	There is high sense of belonging among teachers, which induce them to work perfectly because of their involvement in the activities of the school by the principal	3.89	0.33	Agreed
5	The principal maintains a friendly working relationship with teacher which in turn makes them to be happy and undertake their assigned responsibilities effectively	3.67	0.50	Agreed
6	Disputes between principal and teachers that prevent effective attitude to work among teachers are eliminated because of their consultation by the principals	3.44	0.53	Agreed
7	The principal consults with teachers when faced with challenges	2.44	1.13	Disagreed
8	The principal listens receptively to teachers' ideas and suggestions	2.56	0.88	Agreed
Sectional Mean		3.26	0.63	Agreed

Scale Mean 2.50, n=9

Table 1a showed influence of principals' democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State as responded by Principals. From the table, it could be observed that the mean values of 4.00, 2.67, 3.44, 3.89, 3.67, 3.44 and 2.56 were in agreement with items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 8 respectively while the mean value of 2.44 was in disagreement with item 7. The sectional Mean of 3.26 was greater than the scale Mean of 2.50 which shown that some of the respondents agreed that teachers develop good interest towards their jobs because they are involved in decision-making of the school by the principal, principal consults teachers regularly on issues that help them develop positive attitude to work. There is exchange of ideas between principals and teachers which encourages teachers to work efficiently; there is high sense of belonging among teachers, which induce them to work perfectly because of their involvement in the activities of the school by the principal. The principal maintains a friendly working relationship with teachers which in turn make them to be happy and undertake their assigned responsibilities effectively. Disputes between principal and teachers that prevent effective attitude to work among teachers are eliminated because of their consultation

by the principals and the principal listens receptively to teachers' ideas and suggestions. However, the remaining respondents disagreed that the principal consults with teachers when faced with challenges as influence of principals' democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of principals' autocratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area in Akwa Ibom State?

The responses to the above question as shown in Table 2.

Table 3a: Mean analysis showing influence of principals' autocratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State as responded by Principals

S/N	Influence of Principals' Autocratic Leadership Style on Teachers' Attitude to Work	X	STD	Decision
9	Teachers undertake their job in a harp hazard manner because the principal does not consult them before certain decisions of the school are made	2.33	1.00	Disagreed
10	Principal imposes decisions on teachers that induce them to develop negative attitude towards their job	2.89	0.93	Agreed
11	Principal does not welcome ideas and suggestions from teachers, which discourage them from performing their high rate of enthusiasm	3.11	1.17	Agreed
12	There is apathy among teachers because they are not involved in the decision making of the school	2.00	0.87	Disagreed
13	The principal uses force and pressure on teachers and often emphasis on deadline and this lead to poor attitude to work by the teachers	3.11	0.78	Agreed
14	Principal does not allow any space for self-development of the teachers	1.56	1.01	Disagreed
15	The principals' strict insistence on teachers' absolute obedience and compliance to his/her dictate or directives sometimes lead to teachers' insubordination	2.44	1.01	Disagreed
16	The principals' style of not considering teachers' suggestions and ideas in decision making makes teachers to lose interest in their job	2.00	0.71	Disagreed
Sectional Mean		0.94	Disagreed	

Scale Mean 2.50, n=9

Table 2a showed influence of principals' autocratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom

State as responded by Principals. From the table, it could be observed that the mean values of 3.07, 3.10 and 2.92 were in agreement with items 1, 2 and 5 correspondingly whereas, the mean values of 1.96 and 1.91 were in disagreement with items 3 and 4 respectively. The sectional Mean of 2.44 was less than the scale Mean of 2.50 which indicated that some of the respondents agreed that principal imposes decisions on teachers that induce them to develop negative attitude towards their job. Principal does not welcome ideas and suggestions from teachers, which discourage them from performing their high rate of enthusiasm and the principal uses force and pressure on teachers and often emphasis on deadline and this led to poor attitude to work by the teachers. However, the remaining respondents disagreed that teachers undertake their job in a harp hazard manner because the principal does not consult them before certain decisions of the school are made. There is apathy among teachers because they are not involved in the decision making of the school. Principal does not allow any space for self-development of the teachers, the principals' strict insistence on teachers' absolute obedience and compliance to his/her dictate or directives sometimes lead to teachers' insubordination. The principals' style of not considering teachers' suggestions and ideas in decision -making makes teachers to lose interest in their job as influence of principals' autocratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools.

Research Question 3: What is the influence of principals' laissez faire leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State?

Table 4a: Mean Analysis-Showing Influence of Principals' Laissez Faire Leadership Style on Teachers' Attitude to Work in Secondary Schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State as Responded by Principals

S/N	Items	\bar{X}	STD	Decision
17	Principal's inability to supervise brings unconcerned attitude to work among the teachers	2.44	1.01	Disagreed
18	Principal allows the teachers to go about their work the way they want and this cause confusion in their job performance	1.44	0.73	Disagreed
19	Teachers tend to be happy in performing their roles because they do not follow any instruction from the principal	2.22	0.97	Disagreed
20	Teachers are not properly supervised to perform their responsibilities in an effective manner	2.33	0.87	Disagreed
21	Laissez-faire leadership style brings complete freedom to teachers due to principal's limited involvement in directing them	2.22	0.83	Disagreed

22	The principal works without focus which affect teachers' attitude to work	2.44	1.13	Disagreed
23	The principal's attitude of shying away from his/her responsibilities as the leader creates undesirable behaviour among the teachers	2.44	1.42	Disagreed
24	Principal's inability to take decision induces teachers' poor attitude to work	2.33	0.5	Disagreed
Sectional Mean		2.23	0.93	Disagreed

Scale Mean 2.50, n=9

Table 3a showed influence of principals' laissez faire leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State as responded by Principals. From the table, it could be observed that the mean values of 2.44, 1.44, 2.22, 2.33, 2.22, 2.44, 2.44 and 2.33 were in disagreement with items 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24 respectively. The sectional Mean of 2.23 was less than the scale Mean of 2.50, which indicated that all the respondents disagreed that principals' laissez faire leadership style does not influence teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Principal allows the teachers to go about their work the way they want and this cause confusion in their attitude to work. Teachers tend to be happy in performing their roles because they do not follow any instruction from the principal, teachers are not properly supervised to perform their responsibilities in an effective manner, laissez-faire leadership style brings complete freedom to teachers due to principal's limited involvement in directing them. The principal works without focus which affect teachers' attitude to work, the principal's attitude of shying away from his/her responsibilities as the leader creates undesirable behaviour among the teachers and principal's inability to take decision induces teachers' poor attitude to work as influence of principals' laissez faire leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools.

Findings and Discussion

The findings of the research hypothesis one revealed that there is a high significant influence of democratic leadership style on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The findings of the study agreed with Ada and Mkpa (2020) who found that there was a significant influence of democratic administrative styles on teachers' job performance in Aba Education Zone of Abia State, Nigeria. The democratic style of leadership emphasizes group participation in the making of policies between the leaders and the followers. Decisions about school matters are arrived at when the principal must have consulted and communicated with teachers. The principal attempts as much as possible to make each teacher feel that he is an important member of the school. Communication is multidirectional while ideas are exchanged between teachers and the principal. In this style of leadership, a high degree of teachers' morale and positive attitude to work would be enhanced because teachers could be motivated to work harder as they will be happy and develop a high sense of belonging for being consulted by their principals. Democratic school principal is a leader who stresses the school goals and objectives more and places importance upon conformity with general rules. This principal is more

concerned with the school than the personal benefits or comfort of his staff. A democratic principal imbibes the views of his teachers and makes the best out of them for easy attainment of school goals.

The findings of the research hypothesis two revealed that principals' autocratic leadership style had a moderate significant influence on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The findings of the study confirmed the position of Adeyemi (2010) who ascertained that teachers' job performance was found to be better in schools having principals using autocratic leadership style than in schools having principals using democratic or laissez-faire leadership styles. The autocratic leadership style is also known as the authoritarian style of leadership. Power and decision-making reside in the autocratic leader. The autocratic leader directs group members on the way things should be done. The leader does not maintain clear channel of communication between himself or herself and the subordinates. He or she does not delegate authority nor permit subordinates to participate in policy-making. Autocratic principal lay more emphasis on the attainment of the school's goals and objectives at the expense of the staff needs. An autocratic principal strictly follows the lay down rules and regulations to achieve the school objectives. An autocratic principal is task oriented in nature. Such principals take decisions and impose it on the teachers for implementation. Teachers under the control of autocratic principals may develop negative attitude towards teaching job because there is too much emphasis on job performance and decisions are always imposed on the staff. The non-inclusion of teachers in decision making of the school would make them feel discouraged and get tired of the job. Such discouragement would lead to poor attitude to work among teachers.

The findings of the research hypothesis three revealed that principals' laissez faire leadership style had a low significant influence on teachers' attitude to work in secondary schools in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The findings of the study disagreed with Upendo, and Demetria (2020) who maintained that teachers' attitude to work does depend on principals' laissez fair leadership style in Ogun State secondary schools, Nigeria. Laissez-faire leadership style allows complete freedom to group decision without the leader's participation. Thus, subordinates are free to do what they like. The role of the leader is just to supply materials. The leader does not interfere with or participate in the course of events determined by the group. Laissez fair type of school principal has no clear-cut goals and also gives no professional leadership to his staff. He does not plan out work schedule and has no known pattern of working or supervising or initiating actions. Laissez-faire leadership allows followers entire autonomy to make judgments about any topic in the organization and to address any difficulties they encounter without much supervision from their boss. Working on multiple activities and making various decisions on various subjects or themes without a leader, on the other hand, leads to low productivity and job satisfaction. Where there is laissez-faire leadership in the organization, employees receive no instruction from this type of boss. Subordinates are in charge of making decisions

Conclusion

The study concluded that principals' democratic leadership style influence teachers' attitude to work in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The

study also concluded that the principal's autocratic leadership style determines the nature of teachers' attitude to work in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. The study equally drew a conclusion that principals' laissez-faire leadership style exerts influence teachers' attitude to work in Oron Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Recommendations

1. The Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Education should mandate all principals especially those in Oron LGA to undertake refresher courses on leadership to improve their leadership skills. This will enable them to adopt the democratic leadership style and involve teachers in decision making in all matters regarding school administration in order to foster positive attitude to work by teachers.
2. The Ministry of Education in Akwa Ibom State should regularly organize workshops and seminars for principals working in Oron LGA to prevent them from becoming autocratic, which induce poor attitude to work by teachers through imposition of decisions on them by the principals.
3. The laissez-faire principals in Oron Local Government Area should be enlightened by the state ministry of education to understand that they should not delegate all their responsibilities to teachers except only the experienced ones.

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ASSESSMENT OF PRINCIPALS' DECISION-MAKING STRATEGY AND ITS IMPLICATION ON MANAGEMENT OF FUNDS AND FACILITIES IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study assessed principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of funds and facilities in public secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study had two objectives, two research questions and two null formulated hypotheses, one of which states that; principals' decision-making strategy has no significant impact on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. Descriptive survey design was adopted in the study. The population of the study was 1378 comprising 1193 public secondary school teachers, 175 PTA officials and 10 MOE officials in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. A sample size of 306 respondents was used. A stratified sampling technique was used in which the respondents were classified into 3 strata based on their homogeneity. The instrument for data collection was a researchers-developed (structured) questionnaire titled "Assessment of Principals' Decision-Making Strategy and its Implication on Management of Public Secondary Schools Questionnaire (APDMSIMQ)". The instrument was structured on five points likert scale. The instrument was validated; pilot tested and the reliability indices of 0.73 and 0.82 were obtained using Cronbach Alpha technique. Descriptive statistics of Frequency Counts, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviations as well as Inferential Statistics of ANOVA were employed for data analyses, which were processed with the aid of SPSS version 23.0. The findings revealed that; public senior secondary school principals in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance were effective in adopting suitable decision-making strategy; this enables proper management of funds for teaching-learning facilities. Therefore, the study made recommendations that; public secondary school principals in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance should be exposed to relevant seminars and workshops that could build their capacities more in decision making strategy for them to maintain effective management of facilities in their secondary schools; education stakeholders in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance should work together with the school principals to come up with more meaningful income generating decision making strategy so as to supplement merger school financial resources.

Key Words: Principals, Decision-Making Strategy, Management, Funds, Facilities.

Introduction

Secondary schools are formal organizations established to prepare students to become useful members in the society through the activities of teaching and learning (FRN, 2014). In Nigeria, secondary schools are headed by administrators called principals who always take the lead in planning, organizing, directing and coordinating both human and material resources by way of collaborative decision-making with other members such as vice principals, heads of departments, subject heads, heads of committees among others. The tasks involved are goal setting, deployment and coordination of human and material resources for effective curriculum planning, implementation, evaluation and review of both learning and administrative activities in order to achieve the set educational goals in secondary schools.

The principal is an administrative head of secondary school that performs academic, administrative or leadership functions for the attainment of goals. Principals are leaders entrusted with duty of ensuring adequate management of school resources in order to achieve the desired objectives. Heller (2012) outlines functions of school administrators as including management of instructional programmes, staff human management, students' human management, finance and physical resource management and community relationship management. Wilmore (2002) also points out some expected roles an effective principal plays in the school such as; setting school goals, guiding and encouraging staff performance, managing school resources in terms of finances and other property, monitoring students' progress, promoting staff development and positive relationships and harmony, and creating conducive school climate among others. If education system must achieve its national policies and goals, the school managers at all levels must ensure effective management of resources in the organizations. Essentially, effective school management entails sound knowledge of decision making in coordinating individuals or group members in specifying the nature of particular problem and selecting among available alternatives in order to solve the problem and produce a desired result.

Decision making begins with identifying a problem, mapping out activities and implementation strategies in needed time. The process involves participatory planning, participatory implementation, evaluation and feedback. Decision making process also involves policies (the definition of objectives), resources (people, money, materials and authority), and means of execution (strategies). In the school setting, the content value of decision-making process is concerned with the ability of the school principal to be able to identify policy decision that seeks purposeful action; and executing decision that ensures the best coordination of actions.

The success of any organization such as the educational institution depends largely on the ability of the educational manager to make effective decisions. This is why Oviwigbo (2004) stated that principals need to give considerable attention to key elements of managerial process: planning, organizing, staffing, directing, coordinating, reporting, and budgeting in making decisions (POSDCORB). Decisions are made daily in school about the individuals' roles, conduct of work, distribution of resources, and short-term goals. Decision making usually involves what is to be done, how is to be done, who to do it, and when and where is to be done. Effective decision -making in educational management is very important for the improvement of educational resources. This includes management of instructional materials, school funds, school

community relation, school facilities, and records in the school system. The managerial actions also require adjustment and modification of educational programs, activities and techniques for the purpose of improving the teaching learning process and achieve the set educational goals in secondary schools. As the school is made up of the principal, teachers, students, and other stakeholders, the level of their commitments goes a long way with the decision-making strategy put in place for effective management.

Decision-making has been defined differently by various authors focusing primarily on the process involved in choosing the best option among alternatives. Duze (2011) described decision making as the process by which educational managers (principals) choose the best action or most preferred course of action among alternative sources of action with the purpose of solving problem and achieving set goals effectively and efficiently. Decision making according to Dare (2006) is a process of making choice out of many other conflicting and pressing alternatives, and that a school principal's ability to make decisions on matters relating to the management of the school. Similarly, Ovwigho (2004) opined that decision making is the process of carefully selecting a course of action from various alternative measures. Hence, decision making requires careful and conscious considerations of the possible course of action which does not negate the organizational goal and that which is an extension series of interrelated communication among stakeholders. In addition, Nwachuku (2006) agreed that decision making process is the selection of alternative course of action from available alternatives in order to achieve given objectives. To him, decision making is a sequential process which culminates in a series of choice that stimulates moves or direct actions on a given problem. Decisions taken by organization may be classified under various categories depending upon the scope, importance and the impact that they create in the organization. The following are the different types of decisions according to Panpatte and Takale (2019):

Programmed decisions are normally repetitive in nature. They are the easiest to make. For example: making purchase orders, sanctioning of different types of leave, increments in salary, settlement of normal disputes, etc. Managers in dealing with such issues of routine nature usually follow the established procedures. On the other hand, non-programmed decisions are different in that they are non-routine in nature. They are related to some exceptional situations for which there are no established methods of handling such things. For example: Issues related to handling a serious industrial relations problem, declining market share, increasing competition, problems with the collaborator, growing public hostility towards the organization fall in this category.

Operational or tactical decisions relate to the present. The primary purpose is to achieve high degree of efficiency in the company's ongoing operations. Better working conditions, effective supervision, prudent use of existing resources, better maintenance of the equipment, etc., fall in this category. On the other hand, expanding the scale of operations, entering new markets, changing the product mix, shifting the manufacturing facility from one place to the other, striking alliances with other companies, etc., are strategic in nature. Such decisions will have far reaching impact on the organization.

Decisions taken by managers in the ordinary course of business in their capacity as managers relating to the organizational issues are organizational decisions. For example: decisions regarding introducing a new incentive system, transferring an employee, reallocation or redeployment of employees etc., are taken by managers to

achieve certain objectives. As against such decisions, managers do take some decisions which are purely personal in nature. However, their impact may not exactly confine to their selves and they may affect the organization also. For example: the managers' decision to quit the organization, though personal in nature, may impact the organization.

It is quite common that some decisions are taken by a manager individually while some decisions are taken collectively by a group of managers. Individual decisions are taken where the problem is of routine nature, whereas important and strategic decisions which have a bearing on many aspects of the organization are generally taken by a group. Group decision making is preferred these days because it contributes for better coordination among the people concerned with the implementation of the decision.

In educational institutions like secondary schools for instance, researches have been carried out on various areas pertaining to effective management in public secondary schools in the State. Various issues as academic performance, discipline, supervision, among others, have been captured but no one has been made in the area of principals' decision-making strategy as determinant of effective resources management. While some principals are effective in decision making and executing their duties as leaders, some are ineffective as decisions they usually make, seem worthless as such affect the outcome of the system directly or indirectly. This perhaps could be as a result of internal or external factors such as students' enrolment, overcrowdings, inadequate learning materials, poor funding, low staff strength and quality demands for quality instruction and better learning outcome by the stakeholders in education. Suffice to say that effective decision-making strategy helps in shaping the programs and policy in an organization. Therefore, for these reasons, the present study sought to assess the principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of public secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to assess principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of public secondary schools. Specifically, the study was set to:

1. assess principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State; and
2. assess principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Research Questions

In line with the research objectives, the following research questions are raised.

1. How effective is the principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance Katsina State?
2. How effective is the principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?

Hypotheses

Based on the research questions raised, the following null hypotheses are formulated for the study:

- H₀₁:** Principals' decision-making strategy has no significant impact on the management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
- H₀₂:** Principals' decision-making strategy has no significant impact on the management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Decision-Making and School Management

Decision making pre-supposes the existence of alternative form which the decision maker selects as that which will yield the desired results (Nwachukwu, 2006). This entails the existence of some criteria for measuring or comparing the desirability of the alternatives in relation to the purpose. To him each alternative could have desirable and undesirable aspects but the alternative that appears to have the most desirable result based on the decision criterion is the one to be selected. This is so because every decision is based on a probability that the anticipated event will occur. Thus, the course of action that maximizes the final desirability is the rational decision.

Donnelly, Gibson and Mancervich (1995) posited that decisions are means rather than ends as well as processes by which a school administrator seeks to achieve some desired results. This implies that, decision making is the outcome of a dynamic process influenced by many forces including the organizational environments, leadership style adopted and the principals' knowledge, ability and deliberation with management staff which results in a decision. School administrators at the secondary level of education are concerned with and are responsible for day-to-day performances of both teaching and non-teaching staff members in the realization of the schools' objectives (Olubadewo, 2007). Therefore, the secondary school principal is posed with issues dealing with curriculum and its mode of instructions, negotiations and compromises, physical facilities, finance, pupils' administration, evaluation, supervision and public relations with both members within and outside the school environment. Thus, the cyclical decision-making process is essential not only in each of these task areas but also in the broader functions of secondary school administration, (Musaazi, 1992). Furthermore, Edem (2006) categorized administrative functions at the secondary level to include policy, resources and execution. He further stressed that policy involves a statement of objectives that guides and directs the action of the school principal which becomes a major function in shaping the character and activities of staff members towards the realization of the stated objectives of the school. Policy therefore becomes the channel and process through which decisions are made based on stated rules and regulations. Such policies according to Abdullahi (2007) refers to that which is made on reward and punishment of staff and students, levity and fairness in the dealings with members of staff with regards to late coming, absenteeism, malpractices etc.

School Funds (Financial Resources)

Financial resources are the funds required for the smooth operations of a school and are regarded as the life-wire of any system. It is indeed a more critical facet with which other factors of administrations are created, maintained and sustained. In school management, funds are necessary for the procurement of facilities, equipment, electronics and communication gadget needed for its effective performance. Apart from this, funds are needed to pay the salaries of administrative, academic and non-academic staff. A robust financial allocation for school management would not only enhance goals attainment but its sustainability. Plan and policy implementation are responsive to funds availability. Funds are needed for the acquisition of fixed and current assets and to settle current liabilities and expenditures incurred in the course of organizational management. There are two ways through which school organizations source funds as identified in the manual for head-teachers capacity building by National Institute for Educational Planning and Administration (NIEPA, 2011):

- a. Funds received from government: - government finances education in a number of ways; for instance, paying educators' salaries, providing physical resources, constructing and maintaining school buildings, and transfer payment (funds allocated to the education departments).
- b. School fees and other sources of income: - government funding meets only the most basic needs of a school. To be able to provide learners with quality education, it has become imperative that the school management should supplement the funds provided by the state through; school fees paid by the parents, sponsorship and donations from interest and community groups as well as internally generated income.

School Facilities (Material Resources)

Material resources are tangible resources that can easily be seen and observed in any institution. Material resources include the structures, the machines, raw materials, vehicles, school yards and other tools, which can facilitate organization's activities and processes. As mission and vision statements of organizations differ, hence the material resources they operate with differ as well. In a school system for instance, the material resources are both physical and non-physical facilities like buildings, laboratories, library, e-learning facilities, instructional materials, furniture, classrooms, offices, school records, and sport facilities among others that augment teaching and learning process. In other words, they are materials with valuable nature which include; the classrooms/lecture rooms, staff offices, vehicles, dispensary, garden/farms, library, laboratory, and workshops and so on, which directly or indirectly contribute to the achievement of schools' goals. Others include materials related to curriculum consists of core and elective courses; it is an overall structure for courses that focus on specific skills and knowledge (Topi, Valacich, Wright, Kaiser, Nunamaker, Sipior & De Vreede, 2010). It is simply the content or knowledge conveyed by particular school subjects (Kirk, 2014). The curriculum may be confirmed by the use of curriculum guides, syllabuses, programmes, and packages in schools that display as a prominent feature a body of knowledge that is to be taught to learners. Johnson (1967) posits that a curriculum includes all activities planned and directed by the school, whether it is carried on in groups or individually, inside or outside the school. According to Kerr

(1968), a curriculum is any effort to connect the important principles and structures of an educational proposal in such a form that it is open to critical scrutiny and capable of effective translation. To Patt (1980), a curriculum is a programme of activities (by educators and learners) designed so that learners will attain so far as possible certain educational and other schooling ends or objectives. Wise and Busher (2001) and, Sigilai and Bett (2013) stated that a curriculum has to do with syllabus, teaching, learning, assessment and progression; it involves all that is taught at school, subjects and aspects of life, all activities performed at school, as well as the time allocated to individual subjects.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. Afolabi (2013) posited that descriptive survey design is that survey design that involves gathering data about a target population from a sample and generalizing the findings obtained from the analysis of the sample to the entire population. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 1378 comprising 1193 public senior secondary school teachers, 175 PTA officials and 10 MOE officials in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. A sample size of 306 respondents was used. A stratified sampling technique was used in which the respondents were classified into 3 strata based on their homogeneity. A researchers-developed (structured) questionnaire was used in the study as instrument for data collection. The instrument was structured on five-points likert scale. The instrument was validated and pilot tested and the reliability index of 0.806 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha technique. Descriptive statistics of Frequency Counts, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviations as well as Inferential Statistics of ANOVA were employed for data analyses, which were processed with the aid of SPSS version 23.0.

Data Presentation, Interpretation and Discussion

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of the Respondents' Opinion of Principals' Decision-Making Strategy and its Implication on Management of Funds in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	STD
11	The principal's good decision-making nature enables proper management of funds generated through Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) levy in the school	66	97	11	42	22	3.60	.7427
		5	31	2	8	2	3.28	.6621
		1	7	0	2	0	3.90	.6963
12	The open-minded nature of the principal in decision making process enhances management of funds donated to the school by School-based Management Committee (SBMC).	48	82	8	64	36	3.17	.7088
		3	32	1	7	5	3.43	.6676
		2	5	1	2	0	3.70	.5967
13	The transparent nature of the principal in decision making process enables proper management of funds donated to the school by philanthropists and wealthy individuals in the community.	27	104	14	58	35	3.12	.7760
		1	31	3	9	4	3.33	.5676
		0	6	1	3	0	3.30	.5312
14	The principal's ability to welcome the subordinates' financial initiatives during the decision-making process enables proper management of funds donated to the school by the Old-boys association.	33	96	21	51	37	3.15	.7183
		4	28	4	7	5	3.39	.5216
		0	8	1	0	1	3.60	.7013

15	The principal's ability to involve the subordinates in decision making process enables proper management funds generated through school fees and other sources internally.	46	101	24	42	25	3.42	.6035
		2	31	2	10	3	3.39	.5162
		1	5	0	3	1	3.20	.4532
16	The principal's effective use of decision-making strategy enables proper management of funds generated from Ministry of Education.	51	97	22	52	16	3.48	.7493
		6	25	1	11	5	3.33	.7378
		0	6	1	0	3	3.00	.7438
17	The principal's ability to consult the subordinates' opinion during decision making process enables proper management of funds generated from within and outside the school environment.	29	107	33	46	23	3.30	.6127
		2	29	4	13	0	3.41	.5121
		1	4	1	2	2	2.90	.6612
18	The principal's effective use of decision-making strategy enables proper management of funds generated from SBMC, PTA, school fees and other sources internally.	48	98	18	52	22	3.41	.7115
		2	22	5	9	10	2.93	.0748
		2	6	0	1	1	3.70	.0645
19	The principal's effective use of decision-making strategy enhances proper management of funds generated from the school facilities.	57	88	24	49	20	3.47	.5463
		5	34	1	6	2	3.70	.4265
		4	4	0	2	0	4.20	.6544
20	The principal's effective use of decision-making strategy enables proper management of funds generated from school farms and gardens.	61	92	14	39	32	3.46	.6543
		2	26	2	12	6	3.12	.5634
		2	4	0	4	0	3.40	.7634

The result in Table 1 indicates that each of the items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 of principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance obtained means whose scores was above the decision Mean score of 3.00. The results show that the respondents rated principals' decision-making strategy in items 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19 and 20 as having positive implication on management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. The Grand Mean score is 3.38, which is above the Criterion Mean score of 3.00 set for the study. The result therefore, shows that decision-making strategy used by the principals enables proper management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of the Respondents' Opinion of Principals' Decision-Making Strategy and its Implication on Management of Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	STD
1	The principal's ability to involve subordinates in decision making process enhances management of ICT facilities in the school	88	81	11	37	21	3.74	.7927
		17	18	6	5	2	3.89	.6721
		3	4	0	2	1	3.60	.7463
2	Principal's nature of open discussion at a meeting ensures proper management of laboratory equipment and facilities in the school	92	87	7	42	10	3.87	.7088
		14	24	2	5	3	3.85	.6676
		2	6	0	1	1	3.70	.6967
3	Principal's ability to welcome subordinates' initiatives during decision making process enhances management of workshop facilities in the school	79	82	8	50	19	3.63	.7760
		8	22	4	8	6	3.37	.7676
		1	7	1	0	1	3.70	.6312
4	Principal's welcoming nature for constructive criticism in decision making process enhances management of water facilities in the school	88	99	13	32	6	3.97	.7183
		6	23	9	7	3	3.45	.5216
		2	5	0	2	1	3.50	.7013
5	Principal's ability to adopt corporate decision-making evaluation of performance strategy enhances management of light facilities in the school	64	97	6	55	16	3.57	.6035
		8	29	2	6	3	3.68	.5162
		1	4	1	3	1	3.10	.6532

6	Principal's ability to form group committees during the decision-making process enhances management of games or sport facilities in the school	71	106	4	41	16	3.73	.7493
		6	22	3	14	3	3.29	.7378
		0	6	2	1	1	3.30	.7438
7	Principal's goals-setting collaborative nature in decision making process enhances management of recreational facilities in the school	57	104	8	46	23	3.52	.7456
		3	27	0	15	3	3.25	.8165
		0	6	1	2	1	3.20	.6453
8	Principal's nature of authority delegation to the subordinates for decision making enhances management of library materials or facilities in the school	72	85	5	49	27	3.52	.7584
		7	19	4	14	4	3.22	.5676
		1	6	1	1	1	3.50	.4937
9	The collegial decision-making strategy of the principal enhances management of immovable facilities in the school	34	111	4	56	33	3.23	.5242
		6	17	3	15	7	3.00	.7542
		1	6	0	2	1	3.40	.5645
10	Principal's effective use of decision-making strategy enhances management of staff lodge facilities in the school	37	100	15	59	27	3.25	.7634
		7	15	8	17	1	3.20	.6353
		1	6	0	3	0	3.50	.7542

The result in Table 2 indicates that each of the items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 of principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance obtained means whose scores was above the decision Mean score of 3.00. The results show that the respondents rated principals' decision-making strategy in items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10 as having positive implication on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. The Grand Mean score is 3.38, which is above the Criterion Mean score of 3.00 set for the study. The result therefore, shows that decision-making strategy used by the principals was effective as such it results in positive management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Principals' decision-making strategy has no significant impact on impact management of funds in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. In testing this hypothesis, inferential statistics of ANOVA was employed and processed on SPSS (Version 23). The detail of the result was presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Summary of ANOVA of Differences in the Respondents' Opinion of Principals' Decision-Making Strategy and its Implication on Management of Funds in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance

Source of variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	52.692	2	26.896	1.375	.258	Not sig.
Within Groups	6178.019	294	21.799			
Total	6230.711	296				

The Table 3 presents Analysis of Variance of difference in the respondents' opinion on principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of funds in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. The result indicated that the sum of square between the groups is 52.692; sum of square within the group is 6178.019. While, mean sum of square within group is 21.799 and between the groups is 26.896. The F-value recorded was 1.375 and P-value observed at 0.05 level of significance is .258. Therefore, P-value is greater than Alpha value. Since the observed P-value is greater than Alpha value, the null hypothesis is hereby retained. Thus, this implies that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinions on principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of funds in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Education Quality Assurance Zone.

Hypothesis Two: Principals' decision-making strategy has no significant impact on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. In testing this hypothesis, inferential statistics of ANOVA was employed and processed on SPSS (Version 23). The detail of the result was presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA of Difference in the Respondents' Opinion on Principals' Decision-Making Strategy and its Implication on Management of Facilities in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	231.487	2	101.64	7.192	.734	Not Sig.
Within Groups	4086.710	294	14.61			
Total	4318.197	296				

The Table 4 presents Analysis of Variance of difference in the respondents' opinion of principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance. The result indicated that the sum of square between the groups is 231.487; sum of square within the group is 4086.710. While, mean sum of square within group is 101.64 and between the groups is 14.61. The F-value recorded was 7.19 and P-value observed at 0.05 level of significance is .734. Therefore, P-value is greater than Alpha value. Since the observed P-value is greater than Alpha value, the null hypothesis is hereby retained. Thus, this implies that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinion of principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Discussion of Findings

The finding revealed that public senior secondary school principals in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance were effective in adopting suitable decision-making strategy through their ability to involve and welcome their subordinates' financial initiative as well as their good decision-making nature. This by implication fosters effective management of funds in their schools as the respondents' Grand Mean of the cluster was 3.38 which falls above the criterion mean score of 3.00. This implies that the principals adopt effective decision-making strategy in the management of funds generated through different sources for the schools. This is similar to Victor (2017) findings which revealed that secondary school principals in Anambra State prioritize financial allocation according to school needs, keep accurate financial information of the school, ensure accountability in all the school expenditure, carry out periodic audit of school budget and adopt cost-saving strategies.

The finding also revealed that public senior secondary school principals in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance were effective in adopting suitable decision-making strategy through their ability to welcome the subordinates' initiatives, their welcoming nature of accommodating constructive criticism during decision making process, their nature of authority delegation to the subordinates for decision making among others. This by implication triggers proper management of teaching-learning facilities in the schools. The respondents' Grand Mean of the cluster was 3.49 falls above the criterion mean score of 3.00, and this indicates that the principals adopt effective decision-making strategy in the management of school facilities. This finding is in line with view of Asiabaka (2016) who stated that the actualization of the goals and objectives of education require the provision, maximum utilization and appropriate management of the facilities, as such, school manager should adopt modern methods of facilities management as this improves the quality of teaching and learning.

Conclusion

The study assessed principals' decision-making strategy and its implication on management of public secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study concluded that principals' use of effective decision-making strategy enhances management of funds and teaching and learning facilities in public senior secondary schools in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State;

Recommendations

In line with the findings of this study, it therefore recommended that the:

1. Public secondary school principals in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance should be exposed to relevant seminars and workshops that could build their capacities more in decision making strategy for them to maintain effective management of facilities in their secondary schools; and
2. Education stakeholders in Katsina Zonal Education Quality Assurance should work in synergy with the school principals in coming up with more meaningful income generating decision making strategy so as to increase school financial resources.

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ISSUES AND PROSPECTS OF EMIS IMPLEMENTATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract

The paper appraised the issues bedeviling the implementation of educational management information system (EMIS) and designed prospects and recommendations that are capable of promoting implementation. The study was necessitated from the growing non-implementation of EMIS in secondary schools in Nigeria. The non-implementation of EMIS in secondary schools is occasioned by poor and inadequate funding, absence of expertise, weak monitoring and enforcement of approaches to promote the implementation of the programme. It was also noted that the unwillingness of the public and private secondary schools to adopt the technique is also as a result of staff and school administrators that lack the requisite knowledge to manipulate the software packages. As a result, manual approaches are used in the management of information. Obviously, the manual approach is unlikely to satisfactorily meet up with current trends. Prospects were designed that will promote implementation. These include the need to ensure that the principals are informed on the need to promote EMIS, the need for partners/PTA to recruit staff and collaborate with partners in the provision of ICT equipment among others.

Key Words: EMIS, Issues, Prospects, Implementation, Secondary School.

Introduction

Generally, education can be formal, informal or non-formal. While other educational forms can be carried out at home and other informal places, formal education takes place in schools. In most countries such as Ghana, Nigeria and Cameroon, formal education starts from primary, through secondary and higher educational institutions such as Colleges, Polytechnics, Monotechnics, Universities etc. (Valery, 2020; Tambo, 2012). For the schools to be arranged in an organized way for smooth daily running at various levels, there is need to ensure proper management and administration. This suggest that school management variables need to be put in place and equipped with appropriate management strategies, techniques and approaches.

Specifically in schools, the management is largely engaged in planning, organizing, directing, controlling, coordinating, and evaluating the daily running of the

school system to ensure the achievement of the goals and objectives of the institution. Among others, schools desire to train, impart and prepare students with requisite academic to be able to accomplish tasks and attain educational goals (Valery, 2020). Such goals include ability to perform well in academics, apply academic knowledge in solving societal problems as well as sustain goals of the society.

The need to ensure adequate management of the school system stem from the fact that there are complexities and difficulties that have to be tactically arrested and put under control in the school environment. It is against this backdrop that Onifade, (2004) posited that the school management describes the process in which human and non -human resources are employed and expected to work collaboratively towards ensuring the achievement of school goals. For the above and more to be achieved, room has to be created for proper and adequate planning, controlling, organizing, staffing, leading, coordinating and directing of available human and material resources in the goal achievement process.

The management of the school system typically require the employment of techniques and data storage packages such as the Educational Management Information System (EMIS). Even more, schools need to be equipped with computer rooms, ICT equipment, and good terms of service. Like other organisations, schools are likely to perform better in the presence and effective application of EMIS which entirely depends on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in schools. According to Ejimofor and Okonkwo (2022), EMIS is useful in ensuring proper communication networks in school. Notably, EMIS is a potent tool for solving issues that are related to planning, future-oriented goals and objectives of the school as well as decision-making process that incorporates all stakeholders.

In Nigeria particularly, EMIS is not fully implemented in secondary schools due to paucity of funds, unwillingness of government to release funds, corruption, poverty, data unavailability and so on. Being that EMIS have the capabilities of enhancing data management thereby promoting productivity, it is obvious that it is a potent tool that need to be adopted and implemented at all levels of education and in schools. However, there are problems, issues and challenges that are limiting the implementation of EMIS. It is on the basis of appraising the issues with a view to making recommendations and designing a path that will promote sustainable implementation that this paper was built.

EMIS: The African Experience

According to UNESCO (2012), EMIS seeks to create ICT readiness and utilisation in school curriculum implementation. However, several developing countries have long initiated EMIS as a strategy for information storage, management and analysis, it is faced with diverse challenges such as lack of technology applications, computer infrastructure and clear ICT policy system (Mangal, 2009). In South Africa particularly, Mentz and Mentz (2003) assert that MIS is facing serious obstacles and setbacks in terms of complete application and implementation due to inadequacy in the numbers of the computers which is occasioned by poor funding, inadequate man power, poor knowledge about system operation, weak management by school administrators among others

Menjo and Boit (2005) observed that in Kenya, educational institutions at various levels are in serious need of EMIS. In fact, there is need for the penetration,

adoption and implementation of ICTs in both public and private secondary schools. Menjo and Boit specifically noted that the level of adoption in South Africa is very low and as such, students lack the ability to manipulate the system. Even then, the absence of EMIS poses threat to data storage, maintenance and analysis. EMIS allow retrieval of data that are stored at any time. Even more, there is a growing disparity in ICT infrastructure such that schools in urban areas have access to ICT and EMIS facilities more than schools in rural areas. Most schools in rural areas only store data manually and not electronically. (The Standard, 2010).

In Ghana, Nigeria and Liberia, there are serious inadequacies in the provision of EMIS facilities. These result in poor information management and difficulties in data assessment. Students are also disadvantaged in the process of being exposed to data manipulation and analysis.

Conceptual Clarifications: Management Information System (MIS) and Educational Management Information System (EMIS)

Conceptually, MIS is an integrated machine system for providing information to support the operations, management, and decision-making functions in an organization (Tasafaye, 2017). Basically, information is made up of processed data which becomes useful to users. Equally, system refers to various components that operate together in order to make conversion of data into information possible. Converted data further guide informed decision making within and outside the organization.

On the other hand, EMIS is very important in the education sector. This is because, it informs administrators and managers in the education process. EMIS therefore guides informed decision making as it requires the availability of accurate and timely information. EMIS provide the nexus between resource input, education, teaching and learning. According to Tesafaye (2017), EMIS provide the basis of management, planning and evaluation of the education system. Furthermore, EMIS suggest a demand responsive approach that translates to serving consumer needs while providing useful information to decision and policy makers.

There are three key determinants to the success of EMIS. The measures of EMIS are timeliness and reliability in production of data and information, data integration and data sharing among various EMIS offices and efficient use of data and information for policy decisions (Jiu, Young-yong, and Dan-hond, 2007). In many countries, the rapid increase and dependence in the use of the internet, integration accessibility, dissemination and usability of timely and accurate data largely influences the use of the EMIS. Through EMIS, the totality of the information in the school environment is made readily available. For instance, the number of students, teachers, gender composition of both staff and students, class sizes, number of desks, building types within the school environment, performance of students and grading and so on are stored in the EMIS. Therefore, the EMIS is an inevitable feature of the school. In public schools, the information provided in the EMIS can be useful in guiding the government on project development, project identification, job performance, academic performance, quality and quantity of teachers among others. Through the information provided in EMIS, decision on employment/engagement of new staff can be made since the available staff strength can be ascertained in line with their areas of specialization. As well, areas where students are lacking can be easily determined due to data provision.

In secondary schools, EMIS plays a very sensitive role. It should be noted that education at the level of secondary school need to be handled with serious supervision and monitoring especially due to the fact that students at this level are only being groomed mentally, physically and otherwise. Equally, the level of performance of students in the secondary schools is largely determined by the information that is made available in the EMIS. The EMIS provides areas of lack, attendance and areas of strength for the student. Data on facilities and school plants are made available in the EMIS.

Importance of EMIS in Secondary School

EMIS is significant in several ways as evident in available studies. Hooda and Malik, (2012) in a study in India showed that EMIS positively influences human resource management by way of biometric attendance system. Hooda and Malik specifically explained that the influence of EMIS on human resource management is useful in solving the problem of absenteeism by teachers and students hence prioritizing accountability and discipline by teachers and staff as well as students.

EMIS further aids computerization of student attendance which can be useful in the identification of students and their level of attendance in classes and other academic exercises. The available information on the attendance of students is basically useful in assisting school management in steps to take and measures to apply towards penalizing students that are not available in classes. The information that are available can trigger school management towards informing parents about the inability of students to take academics seriously. EMIS is also useful in the increase of transparency and accountability finance budgeting, management, revenue mobilization and expenditure in learning institutions (Althobeti, 2013). Blandford (1997) also explained that the computerization of accounts system helpful in the reduction and management of finance in secondary Blandford also noted that EMIS assists in the maintenance of accurate records as well as systematic and timely information management. This suggest that EMIS can help in track money owed to the school, generate receipts for all money collected, authorize valid payments; provide accurate, up-to date financial information on budget commitment and actual expenditure and produce financial statements and other statements needed by schools to meet their statutory obligations.

In a study by Odhiambo (2017), the influence of the use of Education Management Information System (EMIS) on the management of secondary schools in Nairobi City County was investigated. The author adopted the descriptive research design while approaching the study. He specifically used a population 1980 which was made up of 220 principals, 220 deputy principals and 1540 heads of department. He selected a sample size of 259 applying simple random, stratified and purposive sampling techniques. His analysis was done using frequencies, simple percentages, means, standard deviation, t-test, chi-square test and Cramer's V statistical approaches in carrying out analysis. This imply that both descriptive and inferential statistics were used in the analysis. His findings indicated that the application of EMIS module for curriculum and instruction, human resource, school-community relations and finance have positive significant influence on the management of secondary schools. This is because it was useful in the reduction of time and routine tasks thereby speeding up time for other school engagements by management. Based on their observations, they

suggested that serious attention be paid to record keeping. Electronic storage, retrieval and analysis of information should be prioritized.

In Uganda and Botswana, the studies of Kereteletse, Selwood and Visscher (2008) which was based on information technology in education management identified that EMIS and MIS in the electronic and computerized forms are still far from being fully implemented in both countries. They showed that both Uganda and Botswana are very backward when it comes to the implementation of EMIS particularly in secondary schools. This is due to poor funding, weak implementation strategies and poor monitoring and evaluation of the process of EMIS. Furthermore, governments of both nations have not prioritized setting up of computer laboratories and setting up digital laboratories in the school. Their study further showed a disparity in the level of use and implementation of EMIS in urban and rural areas. They therefore noted that in urban area of both Uganda and Botswana, students have more access to digital processes than in rural areas. Also, EMIS tends to be made available more in urban areas than in rural areas thus, information management, storage, retrieval and analysis appears easier, effective and faster in urban secondary schools than in schools within rural regions. They further noted a positive effect in the use of technology in the management of personnel records of teachers in Botswana and thus cases of 'missing' files was minimized.

In a related study in Israel, Telem and Pinto (2006) assessed the influence of information technology on the management of school-community relations. Specifically, they analysed the interrelations that exist between parents and school as well as parents and their children in terms of their learning, behaviour and attendance. Their study highlighted that school management information system introduction manifested in obvious changes in the interactions between parents and school and between parents and their children. The changes in form of qualitative information regularly and automatically provided to parents resulted in changes in the nature and frequency of parents and school functionaries dealing with learning, behaviour and attendance issues as well as in the interaction between the latter and between parents and their children.

In another secondary school in USA particularly the Union City School District which is a high density area, Haddad and Jurich (2002) noted a distortion in the school-community relations identifying that the school-community relations is affected when computers were installed in schools and homes of teachers and parents in a pilot project on ICT in education leading to improved messaging within stakeholders such as schools, parents, central decision makers and businesses thus fostering accountability, public support and connectivity.

Problems and Issues of Educational Management Information System

Particularly in secondary schools in Nigeria, there are several factors that are posing various levels of challenges in the implementation of EMIS.

- i. **Inadequate funding:** Funding for the development and maintenance of EMIS is a serious challenge especially at the secondary school level in Nigeria. Mostly in public secondary schools, governments are mostly not willing to invest in the development and maintenance of ICTs and EMIS. Even in private secondary schools, most schools lack the funds to invest in

the development and maintenance of EMIS. Even more, more, inadequacies in funds and finances in Nigeria remains a very big challenge that is faced by both private and government institutions. Inadequate funding has prevented most schools from having well equipped computer laboratories, absence of sufficient computer systems and lack of funds to update and purchase software for the management of educational data. In such schools, the manual approach is used in data management.

- ii. **Inability to integrate data and data systems:** there are serious inability in Nigeria to integrate data and data systems in the management of secondary schools in Nigeria. Shooebridge (2006) observed that the data integration challenge is basically concerned with organizational constraints. In countries such as Chile, Mexico, Argentina, Brazil which are regarded as EMIS leading countries, the extent to which EMIS is used is relatively higher than in Nigeria. Therefore, there is glowing neglect in the implementation of EMIS in secondary schools in Nigeria especially in rural areas. In few public secondary schools in urban areas, there are attempts to implement EMIS yet, there are quite inadequate. Haiyan and Herstein (2003) maintained that the development and maintenance of an integrated EMIS requires a high degree of coordination and collaboration at all levels in the educational system as well as with other ministries and with external agencies. This is not an easy task as organizations are as complex as educational systems tend to resist change. More timely integration of data across units will only be possible if standard definitions and coding schemes are developed and put in place across the system
- iii. **Inadequate development of skills in data use at all levels:** Considerable knowledge and skills are required to build, maintain and use an EMIS. Lack of available human resource capacity significantly limits EMIS development. Building human resource capacity has long been known as a critical factor in the success of EMIS development. Limited capacity for more effective use of data in management and decision making, particularly at the school levels is often cited by local educators and external evaluators as a critical factor limiting the development of EMIS in Nigeria.
Several categories of knowledge and skills are often referenced as deficient:
 - a. knowledge and skills to lead and manage EMIS development;
 - b. knowledge and skills to use technology; and
 - c. knowledge and skills to use data effectively for decision making, policy analysis and planning (AEPM, 2007).
- iv. **Inability to capture expenditure and budget data in EMIS:** The lack of access to desegregate data on educational expenditures or even education budgets is often cited as a major constraint to more informed dialogue on education policy. The lack of budget transparency has been cited as a serious limitation to wider citizen participation in policy debates in Nigeria.
- v. **Inability to develop student-record based EMIS:** The debate in Nigeria is about whether, or not, to pursue the development of individual student-based EMIS. Proponents of such systems often point to the need for individual student records to monitor the progress of all students and to support student-

based financing schemes, which are emerging in a number of countries. The implications for EMIS in the decision to build a student-based EMIS and maintain student records at state and federal levels are considerable. The development of a student-based system is conceptually straight-forward and not particularly difficult to accomplish technically. The challenge, when building and maintaining a national EMIS based on individual student records is how to manage the complexities involved with tracking and updating student records from year to year. The administrative management demands of such a system are considerable. Maintaining national level student record based EMIS requires a level of administrative and management discipline that is often beyond the means of current administrative-bureaucratic-management systems. Most systems are not disciplined enough to sustain such systems for a long time (AEPM, 2007). Experience in other countries suggests that the decision to build an EMIS up from individual student records should be weighed carefully against existing management capacities, administrative-bureaucratic discipline and available resources (Stephen and Cummings, 2009).

Prospects of EMIS implementation in Secondary Schools

The following strategies can be used to bring about implementation of EMIS

i. Training principals to use ICTs:

The school principals being the administrators should be trained on the use of ICTs. It should be noted that EMIS is basically an offshoot of the ICT. Therefore, if the principal is vested in the usability, importance, significance and relevance of ICT and EMIS, he/she will not only see the need to implement EMIS in the school but will go on and supervise the use of the strategy. Therefore, there is need for the principal to be given both electronic and manual trainings that are related to EMIS.

ii. Development of a common EMIS:

Data systems differ from school to school and from organization to organization. As similar as secondary schools remain in the country, there are peculiarities that suggest the common development of EMIS in the secondary school. Therefore, the school administrators with the use of teachers, parents and students should ensure the design of EMIS containing the peculiarities of the system that it intends to solve.

iii. Provision of ICT tools to each school by government

Whether in public or private schools, EMIS can be fully implemented if the government provide ICT tools to students in each schools. It should be done such that in private schools, the government through it agencies should ensure supervision and implementation of the ICT technique by the school. In public schools, the government should purchase ICT tools and equitably distribute it to the students with utmost supervision and monitoring. In this case, the students should be educated on how to manage computer systems, manipulate the software and approach computerization of information. The students should also be encouraged to remit data relating to them.

iv. Provision of ICT tools to each Staff

The teachers should be provided with tools, techniques and systems that will equip them with requisite computer knowledge. For EMIS to be implemented, teachers that are at the fore front of imparting knowledge on students should be appropriately given the

avenue to use software. This is because, the world is fast changing from the traditional approaches of manual data storage to electronic approaches. Furthermore, when teachers are invested with the knowledge of manipulating the system, they will be able to translate same to their students and sustainability will be guaranteed.

v. PTA/Partners recruiting an information manager

The level to which the government is willing to implement EMIS has always been intertwined by setbacks relating to the paucity and insufficiency of funds. Hence, PTA and partners should be involved in the process of purchasing ICT systems and recruit experts to train students and staff. This can be about the recruitment of part time staff, contract staff and ad-hoc staff.

vi. Educating all staff on management of school information

Staff should be retrained and equipped with requisite knowledge on the manipulation. The training of staff on information management of educational information will go a long way in helping the staff to communicate, store, retrieve and analyse educational information in secondary schools. Obviously, most staff lack the knowledge to handle digital processes in the data management process. However, ability of staff to manipulate data at this level will also have impacts in the students' ability to handle similar tasks as they will be equipped by staff.

vii. Provision of information management experts to develop a situational EMIS for each school

Based on the peculiarities of EMIS across schools, there is need to develop EMIS that will be conditioned to accommodate situational issues in each secondary schools in Nigeria. The EMIS need to be developed and designed in such a way that peculiarities such as class sizes, number of students, facilities, staff and all other issues will be ascertained.

viii. Purchasing a standard EMIS

EMIS has fast gone beyond the manual approaches especially in developed countries. This suggest that there is need for computerized software to be developed and purchased. As noted in the literature, there are countries of the developing world that are already using improved and enhanced software in the computation and management of data thus, the school management should purchase such and empower experts.

Conclusion and Recommendations

EMIS plays a very intricate role in the provision of data and information that has the capabilities of guiding decision/policy makers. In fact, EMIS makes data readily available for retrieval. Its implementation in secondary schools will be useful in curbing several problems. However, it is facing several issues and challenges in the real implementation of the programme. For instance, it was observed that factors such as poor funding, inability to integrate data and data systems, inadequate development of skills in data use at all levels, inability to capture expenditure and budget data in EMIS and inability to develop student-record based EMIS. T

The inability of the government to implement EMIS in public schools and the private sectors to implement same in the private schools negatively impact on the existence of EMIS in schools. It should be noted that the achievement of the goals of quality, equality and equity requires new knowledge and skills at all levels and in all job categories from teachers and principals to state and national-level educators. Based

on these findings, it is recommended that adequate funding should be provided for EMIS development, data should be integrated into the data system, skills in data use should be developed at all levels, budget data and capturing of expenditure should be encouraged, and finally, student record based for EMIS should be developed.

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EDUCATION MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM: IMPLEMENTATION ISSUES

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Abstract

This paper discusses Education Management Information System implementation in secondary school. Education is considered to be a key instrument of human, economic and national development. Education Management Information System is a system that help to drive innovation and enhance administration in school system. Education Management Information System (EMIS) provide a powerful management tool capable of contributing to the improvement of educational performance. It enables decision makers to identify problem areas, reduce operational costs and provides a systematic way of addressing educational challenges. This paper examines some of the concepts of Education Management Information System, objectives, Education Management Information System in education management and planning, issues militating against achieving effective implementation of Educational Management Information System. The paper also elaborates on the advantages and concept of implementation of Educational Management Information System and also the issues relating the implementation. This therefore calls for certain repositioning that would perhaps bring about some improvement in effective implementation of education information system in the management of secondary education system. The paper recommends that education management information system should be designed through an inductive process that includes stakeholders from all levels of the organization to take ownership of the system and actually use it while all stakeholders in education sector should be deeply involved in finding lasting solution to effective implementation of Education Management Information System in secondary schools.

Key Words: Education Management, Secondary School, Management Information System, Implementation, Issues

Introduction

The effectiveness and efficiency of management functions have been a topical issue on the entirety of the sphere of education. The effectiveness and efficiency of management function is relying heavily on the acceleration of the use of education management information system; particularly in secondary schools (Campbell, 2017). Because of the level of success recorded in management functions as a result of

introduction of education management information system in such areas like comparative analysis, forecasting, decision making, planning, organizing, accounting, data storage and management; it has triggered off the attention of school management to the need of hiring the services of management information system compliant personnel in order to swiftly achieve organizational goals. Educational management is the process by which educational goals and objectives are achieved through collective and collaborative human efforts in suitable environment. Educational management has to do with controlling and coordinating the activities of education to achieve educational goals and objectives (Campbell, 2017).

According to Idungafa (2021), educational management is the system of control, regulation or supervision in its attempts to effectively and efficiently organize available scarce resources through cooperative efforts when establishing institutions of learning, enrolling learners, attracting best staff, conducting teaching, learning, and research, as well as graduating learners at all levels of education. The effective management of educational institutions helps in the implementation of policies and programmes aimed at realizing envisaged educational targets. Effective implementation of Educational Management Information System in secondary schools by school management helps in developing school systems for administration and easing management tasks. According to Granville (2018), effective implementation of educational management information system helps made administrative work easier with regard to accounts, attendance data, and the sharing of confidential information.

Since the present day is based on technology and information, success in organizing information systems for the development of education depends on the effective use and implementation of Education Management Information Systems (Wako, 2019). Therefore, educators must understand that efficient information management is an important condition for continued social and economic development (Chapman, 2021). Not using accurate educational information for monitoring development activities and in decision making may result in unexpected problems and hold back development (Wako, 2019). The Educational Management Information System (EMIS) is an information system utilized to systematically collect educational data from schools. According to Cassidy (2020) Education management information system is a system for the collection, integration, processing, maintenance and dissemination of data and information to support decision making, policy-analysis and formulation, planning, monitoring and management at all levels of an education system.

The integration of an education management information system (EMIS) is becoming less of an option and more of a mandatory requirement in educational institutions. One of the few things all educational institutions have in common is their reliance on numerous software tools and data storage systems (Adinno, 2019). To achieve maximum efficiency and enhance productivity, each of these systems needs to be connected. An education management information system allows just that, serving as a central 'hub' for all essential data and communications. Traditionally, only the most affluent institutions have been able to afford education management information systems, or extensive enterprise resource planning software suites. In addition, the functions and benefits of such tools were strictly limited by the rudimentary nature of cloud computing at the time (Adinno, 2019). Cloud hosting and high-speed internet access have since become the norm for educational institutions in most developed

nations. Consequently, the adoption of educational management information system solutions is now a realistic possibility for almost all schools and colleges. But how does an educational management information system work, and how can an organisation benefit from educational management information system integration?

Working of an Education Management Information System (EMIS)

The education management information system creates a central data repository for a school. This subsequently enables the institution to store, access and manage all important data from a single central dashboard. Authorised personnel can also access the system from anywhere in the world, using any connected device. It is essentially a productivity tool for streamlining a long list of essential admin tasks, while simplifying complex data analysis and reporting (Idungafa, 2021). The versatility of an education management information system (EMIS) is such that it can be used to help an educational institution accomplish almost any immediate or long-term goal. Just a few examples of which include heightened profitability, improved success rates for students, better staff retention rates, ensuring prompt payments of fees and facilitating distance learning. In a sense, an educational management information system is to a school or college what an operating system is to a computer. It has simplified, centralised and unified dashboards, which provide quick and easy access to the information, functionalities and facilities needed. A significantly more efficient and user-friendly option than running a series of separate tools in unison, which are not designed to communicate or integrate with one another.

Concept of Education Management Information Systems (EMIS)

An Education Management Information System (EMIS) is an institutional service unit producing, managing, and disseminating educational data and information, usually with Ministry of Education (Hua, 2019). Education Management Information System is further defined by Hua (2019) as a set of formalized and integrated operational process, procedures, and cooperative agreements by which data and information about schools and schooling, such as facilities, teachers, students, learning activities, and evaluative outputs, are regularly shared, integrated and analyzed. Education Management Information System (EMIS) is a system of people, technology, models, methods, processes, procedures, rules and regulations that function together to provide education leaders, decision makers and managers at all levels with a comprehensive, integrated set of relevant, reliable, unambiguous, and timely data and information to support them in completion of their responsibilities. It is an institutional service unit which produces, and manages educational data and information. It is normally established within a national Ministry or department responsible for education.

An Education Management Information System (EMIS), according to Tegegne (2019), is a comprehensive system that brings together people, process, and technology to provide timely, cost effective, and user appropriate information to support educational management at whatever level is needed. The term information management was first used in 1980s. It covers subjects ranging from library services to data-based management. It is thus the economic, efficient and effective coordination of the production, control, storage, retrieval and dissemination of information from

external and internal sources in order to improve the performance of an organization. The essence of effective management revolves around acquisition and protection of sound, vital information and knowledge. This is what makes it possible to staff, direct, coordinate, report and budget or, in other words to manage (Ouma, 2019). Information is the basis of management, planning and evaluation of an education system.

The main purpose of an EMIS is to integrate information related to the management of educational activities, and to make it available for the decision makers, as well as the other parties, to use in helping them to make the correct decision (Connal, 2019). In other words, the purpose of an EMIS is to provide the necessary information to the right person, at the right time, for use in management decisions (Yuen, 2019). There is evidence that the EMIS can potentially provide a powerful management tool capable of contributing to the improvement of educational performance. It enables decision makers to identify problem areas, reduce operational costs and provides a systematic way of addressing educational challenges. If effectively implemented, the EMIS is capable of raising educational awareness, motivating employees to search for innovative solutions and increasing educational efficiency (Gunam, 2017).

The focal functions of Education Management Information System (EMIS) are the collection, processing, utilizing and dissemination of educational data and information and avail it to educational stakeholders on a timely, routine, reliable and predictable basis via uncomplicated and user-friendly interfaces. In its normal operation it employs both manual and ICT through computerized systems. Education Management Information System (EMIS) also includes a set of formalized and integrated operational processes, procedures, and cooperative agreements by which data and information about schools; educational resources and infrastructure; other learning activities, and evaluative outputs are regularly shared, integrated, analyzed, and disseminated for educational decision making at each level of the educational hierarchy (Bodo, 2019). Educational goals and objectives in many educational systems have shifted from focusing on access, expansion, maintenance and control to quality, development, efficiency, effectiveness, equity and performance; this shift offers a more complex collection of policy choices. Understanding these choices requires data which come from multiple sources and from multiple levels. Collecting, organizing, integrating and analyzing these data will require more cooperation with other agencies

An emphasis on quality, equality, equity, performance and development requires significant changes to the functioning of education systems, how they are managed, and the kinds of data and information that education leaders and managers need to fulfill their responsibilities. Therefore, monitoring a system's progress against this set of goals, and adjusting education policies to assure successful attainment of goals and objectives, requires access to much more detailed data and information. These data and information need a comprehensive system that can analyses and process the data for decision making purposes (Cassidy, 2020). The objective of an Education Management Information System (EMIS), however, is not only to collect, store, process, analyses, manage and disseminate information but also to help education policy making by providing relevant and accessible information. The Education Management Information System (EMIS) is gradually being recognized as an indispensable tool and support for the formulation of policies, management and evaluation in the education system (Carrizo., 2018).

According to Bado (2019), under current practice, Education Management Information Systems (EMIS) are typically limited to centralized databases containing basic, school level data, pupil data (enrollment, age, repetition), teacher data (experience, placement) and school inventory data (location, number of classrooms, equipment etc.). An Education Management Information System (EMIS) is a comprehensive system that brings together people, practices, and technology to provide quality education statistics in a timely, cost-effective, and sustainable manner, at every administrative level, and to support selected operational functions. Although many Education Management Information System issues remain as they were almost 10 years ago, donors' and the world's attention recently have refocused from access to quality in education and the advent of newer technologies. Their rapid and thorough adoption in the second and third world was hardly foreseen ten years ago and has had an impact on the direction of educational management information system. The fundamentals about educational management information system includes:

- educational management information system data need to be accurate.
- educational management information system data need to be timely.
- educational management information system data need to be reliable.
- educational management information system data need to be understandable.

Most existing systems are some compromises of the above four factors. Accuracy can require more time than is allowed. Timeliness may require some relaxation of complete accuracy. Reliability is affected by external factors like funding, manpower, and political events. Turning data into information creating meaning from “facts” is a constant challenge of making data, then information, then knowledge useful for decision making. According to Moses (2019) the repeated lesson is that creating a sustainable, workable educational management information system depends on three factors:

- i. The right PEOPLE, motivated to perform and skilled in their work
- ii. The right PROCESSES that reduce duplication and reinforce accuracy and accountability
- iii. The right TECHNOLOGY, appropriate to the state of education, and the reliability of its infrastructure.

Education Management Information System for Educational Management

Educational management, like all management branches can be described as a process of preparing a set of decisions about the educational system in such a way that goals and purposes of education will be sufficiently realized in future with the available resources. The focus of educational planning is the application of rational and systematic analysis of the education production function with a view to suggesting what actions or measures would make the production education more efficient and effective (Idungafa, 2021). This is based on the nature of goals of the society and the students. The need to gather data, to undertake sector research and thematic studies, to assess and evaluate the efficiency of current programs, to explore the future in order to facilitate a wider debate on these issues is more than ever a determining factor in guiding decision-making and elaborating education policies.

Education management is an exercise, which requires not only specific skills, but also the availability of reliable and relevant information, which reflects the exact

situation of education in the country. In this way, education management information system can feed reliable data to different simulation models allowing reflection on objectives defined for the medium and long term. To analyze the situation is a necessary and fundamental step in the management process. In fact, how could one define objectives; formulate policies and strategies without knowing the present and past situations? In other words, for school management to be effective, it should be based on a detailed and critical analysis of the situation, identifying the problems and causes, on which new policies and programs to be implemented are supposed to act (Johnson, 2021).

Consequently, the choice in matters of education policy and planning should imperatively be made in the light of a solid information system which makes precise, relevant, reliable and updated information available to education managers and planners, and more conclusively for decision makers (Bado(2019). Because of a weak information system, most education planning efforts still have little impact and do not always guide the fulfillment of their objectives in an efficient way. One of the reasons often put forward is the absence of a link between the established diagnostic and the defined strategic policies and choices. But more frequently, the explanation could be found in the inadequacy, indeed in the lack of relevant data and information on which decision-makers can base their policies upon. Therefore, other than the collection of information, its storage, and processing, one other major function of Education Management Information System (EMIS) is to facilitate the detailed analysis and synthesis of data in order to draw the most salient and relevant information to help in educational planning and policy decision-making.

Issues and prospect of Education Management Information System

To support Education Management Information System (EMIS), Computers are a basic requirement. Computer consists of hardware and Software. The hardware refers to the parts that one can touch, hold and move. These include the monitor, keyboard, mouse and peripheral devices such as printers, disc drivers and scanners. A computer is useless unless it is given instructions that come inform of software. Software is the programme that instructs a computer to process data and how the programme should be used. There are three main types of computer software utilized by administrators. These are; word processing and communication, data base management and spread sheet systems. (Bluennet, 2019) in addition, noted that the ability to connect computers through networks provides a data sharing platform between principals and teachers. Networking allows for an elaborate system of technology such as using email instead of mail box. Email is enabled by the Internet which is an information gathering tool utilizing the world –wide web using search engines and http address electronic mail or e-mail refers to the procedure of sending messages from one person to another using internet facilities.

A personal computer can be connected to the network through internet to send and receive messages and other bulk mail electronically. Network infrastructure connects the access devices in school to the required tools, services and digital resources. It comprises of; internal computers and associate computer storage devices, environmental management equipment, operating software for server computers and related hardware (Idungafa, 2021). Tucano (2020), states that lack of adequate

electricity was a barrier to the operation of EMIS in Nigeria. Most states had Generators but usage was limited because fuel was not always available. According to Idungafa (2021), most technical issues on EMIS that are based on what infrastructure is available. The issues include available power, computer soft and ware and their maintenance, security of equipment and air conditioning facilities in areas of high temperatures and humidity (Candy, 2019).

Other issues to the effective implementation of education management information system are limited use of computers in data management due to inadequate supporting infrastructure such as electricity and telecommunication in rural areas and insufficient funding to ensure maintenance of Information Communication Technology equipment (Brown, 2020). Use of very old equipment and lack of limited access to the Internet are also an issue to the implementation of educational management information system. Issues associated with the use of education management information system (Nenty, 2020) also includes:

1. Infrastructure related issues
2. Lack of skills with particular applications;
3. High running and subscription costs;
4. Lack of good publicity and incentives to attract potential users;
5. Identification of information sources that meet the needs of users;
6. Poor Quality of Service of the internet and telecommunication services;
7. Effective management of network traffic and infrastructure

The solution strategy towards bridging the digital device demands an aggressive human capacity building in ICT through training workshops, seminars and courses in collaboration with local and international institutions. Education Management Information System ensures good planning that takes into cognizance the number of managements required for quality education, among other things. If productive resources are put to their best uses, the level of output will be high, but if resources are inefficiently allocated, production will be low.

Conclusion

Based on the reviewed of the paper, it is concluded that the use of the Education Management Information System (EMIS) influences positively on the management of secondary schools' system as it helps to reduce time in administrative work. Education Management Information System ensures good planning that takes into cognizance the number of managements required for quality education, among other things

Recommendations

Based on the above, the following recommendations have been offered.

1. Seminars and workshops on ICT should be organized regularly by academic staff union in the tertiary institutions as part of in- service training to make academic staff develop positive attitude towards the new technology.
2. Education management information system should be designed through an inductive process that includes stakeholders from all levels of the organization to take ownership of the system and actually use it.
3. It should also focus on finding ways of enhancing its use by school principals and administrators.

4. Appropriate training and effective leadership should be adopted to help escalate the benefits of EMIS in the area of school management.
5. It is important for the school authority to cooperate with teachers by providing sufficient time to implement new technology in the classroom. This can be achieved by reducing excess workload or increase length of lecture time to accommodate ICT practical acquisition.

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RELIGIOUS LITERACY AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF MORALS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN UYO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

This study Examined the relationship between religious literacy and the development of morals among Secondary School Students in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State. Four research questions and four null hypotheses were formulated to guide this study. The research design adopted for the study was correlational. Population of the study comprised all the SS2 students selected from 4 public Secondary Schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. 212 students were sampled using simple random sampling technique. A researchers-developed instrument entitled "Christian Religious Studies and Students' Moral Development Questionnaire (CRSSSMDQ) was used for data collection." The instrument was face-validated by validates and were used to gather data. Internal consistency reliability was carried out and was subjected to cronbach's alpha which yielded reliability coefficient of 0.74. The data generated from the field were coded and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation to test the null hypotheses at 0.5 level of significance. The finding for the study reveals that there is a significant relationship between the teaching of Trustworthiness, Justice, Civic Virtue and respect in Christian Religious Studies and Students' moral development. It was recommended that teachers should not only focus on teaching the students to pass exams, they should also pay attention to inculcating good values on the students so as to enable them live in accordance with the norms and tradition of the society.

Key Words: Religious, Literacy, Development, Morals, Secondary, School

Introduction

Today, Nigeria is grappling with moral decadences among our children and youths. A proper understanding of moral decadence requires first a meaning of morality. The term morality is derived from the Latin plural 'Mores' meaning manner, moral which means generally accepted code of conduct in a society. The Oxford Advanced

Learners Dictionary defines morality as principles concerning right and wrong or good and bad behaviors. Morality can be seen as a standard set by a society which members of that society are expected to adhere strictly, any break in rules and regulations accords punishments. From the above, one can deduce that morality has to do with what is good and striving to do what is right. Moral decadence is therefore seen as the deviation from the value system of the society which differs from one society to another. In this sense, violation of societal values and all forms of unacceptable behaviors are very high in practice. Murrain and Ugwumba (2014) asserted that moral decadence is a process of behaving in a way that shows low moral standard, it means gross reduction in the moral values in a particular society or nation.

There are different forms of immoral acts ranging from cultism, examination malpractice, prostitution, bribery, indecency, dishonesty, kidnapping, corruption, impatience, disrespect to non-caring attitudes which secondary school students and youths engage in and it has been of great concern to parents, schools, government and the general public at large. Hence, there is a need for moral development among our children and youths.

Christian Religious Education is a subject that deepens the faith and beliefs of the Christians and also teaches them good morals. It is taught at primary, secondary and tertiary institutions in different countries of Africa. In Nigeria, it is viewed as a subject that helps to streamline students thought, Character, morality and aspiration. It fosters morals among students, teaching them to live in the world guided by moral ideas of loyalty to God, charity and justice to their fellow human beings. It inculcates in students' positive attitudes and moral values such as humility, respect, love, kindness and spirit of forgiveness (Ilechukwu & Ugwuozor, 2014).

Christian Religious Studies is one among the religious subjects taught in secondary schools in Nigeria today and has been proven to have taken the central position in ensuring moral and spiritual well-being of individuals in the society (Essien & Bello 2006). Christian religious studies play vital roles among secondary School students, youths in Nigeria and beyond. It equips them and helps them in ensuring high level of morality in the society. This subject provides them with more opportunities to learn more about God and there by develop their faith in God. Christian Religious Studies stands as manual students, youths hold on to, for assistance in developing their Christian attitude and moral values (e.g., humility, respect, love, and justice, etc.). To instill in students, youths, the spirit to combat corruption, the spirit of tolerance, reconciliation, peaceful co-existence and non-violence as well as to develop and foster in the students/youths, the spirit of respect for all people and human life.

Without effective teaching of religious studies in secondary schools, Nigeria as a nation will likely end up in conflict, religious crisis, insurgencies and social unrest among other things. Christian religious studies are viewed as one of the means to restore moral and social order in the society. For example, after a long description of the moral decay in Nigeria which is portrayed in rampant fraud, evidence of corruption in high and low places, bribery, stealing and robbery with violence scandalous nepotism and political patronage and abuse of power, excessive materials and general indiscipline, Iheomia (1995) concludes that: "in the final analysis what matters most to a nation's well-being is spiritual and moral health and this can be achieved through the impartation of good morals on students through the teaching of Christian Religious Studies at all

level. Everything else which a nation struggles for depends on this whether it is national integration, political stability, economic development or educational, scientific and technological progress.

On the other hand, moral development is defined as the process through which children develop proper attitude and behaviour towards other people in the society based on social and cultural norms, rules and laws. Moral development focuses on the emergence, change and understanding of morality from infancy through adulthood. There are factors affecting students' moral development such as family, school, peer group, society, culture, gender and age (Simon 2012). In school, what the students see and hear from teachers and school mates affect their moral development. The teaching of Christian Religious Studies and the level of morality displayed by the teacher in their day-to-day interaction with the students largely influences the moral development of the students. In essence, the greatest asset of a nation's education system would be its teachers of sound moral character who are instrumental to shaping, future leaders' moral character.

Contrary to this, it has been observed from complaints of the students, parents, school administrators and scholars that there seems to be immoral or demolished character among students in schools. It seems moral character is no longer given a priority in the school system. Students seem to engage in premarital sex, examination malpractice, they lack respect for elders, involve in cultism and other social vices. Probably the immoral character displayed by their peers, parents and teachers influence the students' moral development negatively.

The complaint is likely that this moral indiscipline result in students developing immoral character such as rape, kidnapping, disrespect for elders and constituted authorities, irresponsible and non-caring attitude, unjust and unfair to one another, malpractice and school community unrest, resulting in students' cultism. All these problems of immoral character have become a societal problem and have been a source of concern to researchers and scholars. Several researches have been conducted to proffer solutions to the problem. For instance, Bello and Yusuf (2017) carried out research in Ilorin, Nigeria to investigate the teaching of Christian religious studies as the predictor of Junior Secondary School Students moral character. The study revealed that students live by examples hence the teaching of good values strongly influence students' moral development, In the same vein, the work of Signe Moller (2009) on moral development revealed the influence of Christian religious studies on the students' moral development despite the researches so far reviewed.

Statement of the Problem

It is generally believed that the inculcation of sound moral character in students is not only important but also necessary for the building and wellbeing of our society. The moral decadence among Nigerian youths' overtime has been a source of major concern. The lack of effective teaching of these youths' moral and religious values have regrettably led to the eventual collapse of moral values and has increased social vices like fraud, corruption and immoral tendencies among youths especially Secondary School students. Corruption has curiously been noticed among Nigerian youths and this doesn't speak well of the future of Nigeria as the youths of today would eventually be

the leaders of tomorrow. And if corruption is not checked among youths, it would be nearly impossible to eradicate corruption and other social vices in the country.

The aim of Christian religious studies was to inculcate good morals on students there by nurturing them to become useful and responsible members of the society. Contrary to this, it has been observed from complaints of students, parents, school administrators and scholars that there seems to be immoral or demoralized character traits among students in schools ranging from examination malpractices, raping, disrespect, dishonesty, robbery non-caring attitude among the students. This problem has become a great concern to the society and this study sought to address it by assessing the roles of Christian Religious Studies on students' moral development in Uyo Local Government of Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to examine the relationship between Christian Religious Studies and students' moral development in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. This study specifically sought to:

1. Examine the relationship between the teaching of trustworthiness and students' moral development.
2. Examine the relationship between the teaching of justice and fairness and students' moral development.
3. Examine the relationship between the teaching of civic virtue and students' moral development.
4. Examine the relationship between the teaching of respect and students' moral development.

Research Questions

To guide the study, the following questions were raised:

1. To what extent does the teaching of trustworthiness relate with students' moral development?
2. To what extent does the teaching of justice and fairness relate with students' moral development?
3. To what extent does the teaching of civic virtue relate with students' moral development?
4. To what extent does the teaching of respect relate with students' moral development?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the teaching of trustworthiness and students' moral development.
2. There is no significant relationship between the teaching of justice and fairness and students' moral development.
3. There is no significant relationship between the teaching of civic virtue and students' moral development.
4. There is no significant relationship between the teaching of respect and students' moral development.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory Propounded by Albert Bandura in (1977)

This theory is based on the idea that we learn from our interaction with others in a social context. Separately by observing the behaviour of other people develop similar behaviour. After observing the behaviour of others, people assimilate and imitate that behaviour especially if their observations and experiences are positive ones or include rewards related to the observed behavior. According to Bandura, imitation involves, the actual reproduction of observed motor activities. Bandura's theory has often been called a bridge between behaviorist learning theories and cognitive learning theories because it encompasses attention, memory and motivation. However, on the regard Bandura believes that direct learning could not account for all types of learning for this reason in his theory he added a social element arguing that people can learn new information and behavior by watching other people.

Thus, this theory has a wide-reaching implication for students' moral development in the setting, as teachers are moral models to students. This theory is relevant to this study because school administrators and teachers must be sensitive to their moral roles while interacting with both the students and colleagues as this affect the moral development of their students.

Neoklibergians Developmental Theory by James Rest (1984)

James Rest was an American psychologist specializing in moral psychology and development. Together with his Minnesota group of colleagues including Darcia Narudez. Muriel and Stephen Thoma etc, developed Neokoliberian theory in 1984.

Rest extended Koliberigia approach to researching moral reasoning. He observed that the conventional division of labour in moral psychological research has been tripartite depending on theoretical orientation, one study of either moral thought, moral emotions or moral behavior. He proposed instead that we think of moral functioning as it involves four inner processes or components all of which must perform adequately to produce moral behaviour and all of which involve cognitive affective interaction (Rest, 1984). Rest model which provides a theoretical moral perspective on moral development includes four functional components namely, moral sensitivity, moral judgment, moral motivation and moral character, Rest and Narvaez, (1994). Moral sensitivity refers to the ability of the individual to interpret a particular situation in terms of possible cause of action, determine what could be affected by the action and understand how the affected party would regard the effect. Moral judgment refers to the ability of the individual to judge which action is right and ought to decide what to do in a particular situation. Moral motivation refers to the ability of an individual to choose moral values over personal value. Moral character deals with sufficient ego, strength and implementation of skills. An individual has to follow his or her intentions.

The model might be effective in promoting moral motivation and moral behaviour in students. Hence, from the perspective of this moral development, teacher as moral models can significantly promote moral development particularly the development of moral motivation and moral character of the students.

Concept of Christian Religious Studies

Christian religious studies is a subject that explains the Holy Bible and also defines the moral virtues of the religious adherents known as the Christian. It is aimed at educating, correcting and also injecting some moral characters into a child which would help him to be useful to the society (Mapp, 1999). But this aim would not be easily achievable without the parent's or family playing their foundational roles.

Religious training and moral instruction were considered as fundamental to the development of sound education. The essence of teaching Christian religious education includes academic, moral; civil and spiritual objectives. In Christian religious education it is obvious that students are taught the way of life. Thus, the teaching of the subject instills discipline and obedience in the products. The study of Christian Religious Studies enables the students to learn the tenets of the faith and to live a life that is pleasing to God. CRS therefore is aimed at producing (training) persons who will be fit or equipped for religious and social responsibility. Thus, the focus of Christian Religious Studies curriculum among other things is for pupil's moral training and academic pursuance. From the above observations, it is understood that Christian Religious Education is not only a subject to learn, but also a way of life, but what is not clear, is whether the teaching of this subject has made any meaningful impact on the students who learn it and on the Nigerian society as a whole. Moreover it can be seen that there is little relationship between what is learned in C.R.K classes and the C.R.K. graduates' lives at home, as now one hears of so much evil, indiscipline and moral decadence in Nigerian society. George (2000) lament on the Moral decadence in our institution as a result of religious Education.

Students' Moral Development

American (Webster) defines moral as being able to distinguish between right and wrong. According to Buzzelli & Johnson (2001:874-876) morality constitutes a set of person's beliefs and understanding which are evaluative in nature: that is which distinguish whether consciously or unconsciously, between what is right and what is wrong, what is good and what is bad. Buzzelli & Johnson further stated that teaching itself involves moral action and teachers are moral agents (models) and education a whole. Thus, classroom interaction is particular is fundamentally and inevitably moral nature.

Berkowitz (2002) identified seven psychological components of the "moral anatomy" and urged scientists and educators to begin reconstructing the "complete moral person:

1. Moral behaviour (prosocial, sharing, donating to charity telling the truth).
2. Moral values (believed in moral good).
3. Moral emotion (quilt, empathy, compassion).
4. Moral reasoning (about right and wrong).
5. Moral identity (morality as an aspect of self-huge).
6. Moral personality enduring tendency to act with honesty, altruism and responsibility.
7. "Meta-moral" Characteristics meaning they make morality possible even when they are not inherently moral". (Page 43).

Pritchard (2002) focused on moral development as a personality construct “of a complex set of relatively persistent qualities of the individual person and the form has a definite positive connotation when it is used in discussion of moral education. Bertowitz (2002) stated that moral development is an individual's set of psychological characteristics that affect the person's ability and inclination to function morally. Liekona (2003) attempted to connect psychological and moral component when he stated that morality consists of knowing the good, desiring the good, and doing-habits of the mind, habits of the heart and habit of action. While for Huitt (2002) moral character incorporates the underlying qualities of person's moral or ethical knowledge, reasoning, values and commitment that are routinely displayed in behavior.

Eisenberg (2000) identifies several basic emotions that play a fundamental role in morality. These include compassion, empathy and sympathy. These should be considered essential emotion for moral motivation. Borba (2001) suggested that empathy courtesy, kindness, tolerance and fairness, confirmed Hottman's identification of empathy as a critical emotion, in that it is foundational to others.

Seligman (2002) identified 25 positive identity traits which he labeled “signature strength” and grouped them in five categories: wisdom and knowledge, courage, love and humanity, justice and temperance, spirituality and transcendence. To Vessels (2004), people with moral character are predisposed to:

1. Show kindness and compassion with empathetic understanding.
2. Show the courage to be honest and principled irrespective of circumstance.
3. Acquire a wide range of abilities that enable them to independently resolve problems, analyze situation where moral values and principles will be in a personal and social constructive manner.
4. Display a high level of effort in their daily work and a high level of commitment to individual and group goals and standard with respect to the norms of the society.
5. Show an interest in and concern to others in the spirit of friendship and brotherhood and act on those concerns routinely.

Following the preservation of social institution and improvement of both self and Community as civic duties walker (2000) also identified cluster of attributes which include: honesty, truthfulness and trustworthiness secondly include care, compassion and integrity or the Connection of thought to action should be emphasized.

Moral Development is defined as a process through which children develop proper attitude and behavior towards other people in the society based on social and cultural norms, rules and laws. According to Bandura (2000), moral development occurs gradually from interaction with the environment including the application of consequences, the observation of models and acculturation by social agents. This implies that student (individual) developed morally through application of consequences, the observation of moral and aculturation by social agents which teachers impact on students through the teaching of Christian religious studies is among. Reviewed in Kolibergia (2005), Hetman (2001) viewed moral development as the particular aspect of socialization involved in internalization, this implies the inner yielding to relies in situation that may result in wrong doing even without monitoring and sanction. Conclusively, moral development is the gradual progressive development, grasping of wrong and right principles, conscious ethical religious values, social

attitudes and their behaviours. It is the emergence, changes and understanding of morality by the students through their observation and teaching that enhance the students' moral development.

Trustworthiness and Students' Moral Development

Trustworthiness is the ability to keep promises, to be honest, reliable and principled while never inappropriately betraying a confidence. Trustworthiness relies on the integrity and character of the person. Meyer (2008) refers to trustworthiness as a characteristic of a trustee that is responsible for trust. Hardin is one of the few authors who explicitly distinguished trust from trustworthiness. He defines trustworthiness with reference to trust by saying your trustworthiness is your commitment to fulfill another trust in you (Hardin 2009). He proceeds to offer three general categories for fulfilling such a commitment, (i) A mixture of internal and external inducements where he adopts the relevant disposition out of habit or character (bald and moral disposition), (ii) external inducements through interest alignment, (iii) A mixture of internal and external inducements by norms that motivate and sanction behavior. Deductively, trustworthiness is the commitment and ability to be relied on as an honest and truthful person. A teacher's honesty and attitudes toward truth is integral to his/her character and professional integrity. Socket (2005) asserted that truth telling is a moral dispositions and professional expertise is manifested by teachers' pursuit of the truth. Hence, the teaching of trustworthiness in schools has greater effect on students' moral development.

Justice and Students' Moral Development

The term "just" as used by Aristotle has two separate meanings. First, it is principally used to describe a conduct in accordance to the law. It is used to describe a conduct that conforms with the constitution. In this sense, justice denotes moral disposition which render men apt to do things that are just and what cause them to act justly and to wish what is just. It refers primarily to the observation of certain authorities' rules of human conduct and should rather be called the virtue of righteousness or of moral justice. Oxford Advance Learners' Dictionary defined justice as a moral justifiable apportionment of rewards or punishment, each person being given what he/she is due. Just and fair in apportioning rewards or punishment to their students will unconsciously influence their attitude towards justice, fairness and equity. Elibaz (2001) argued that the quality of attentiveness is what keeps the teacher oriented in the present lives of students and prevent them from forgetting that those lives are of value to their own right. On the other hand, caring has to do with fairness and justice, lacking those qualities, falling into despair, inattentiveness and becoming indifferent to question or fairness and equity undermined the work of a teacher.

Civic Virtue on Students' Moral Development

According to Oxford Advanced Learners' dictionary civic virtue is the cultivation of habits important for the success of the community. Closely linked to the concept of citizenship, civic virtue is often conceived as the dedication of citizens to the common welfare of their community even at the cost of their individual interest. Sara Bosin (2008) defined Civic virtue as a morality or a standard of righteous behavior in

relation to a citizen's involvement in the society. Putnam defined it as active participation in public life, trustworthiness and reciprocity that is acquired through social connectedness (Putnam & Robert, 2008). Hence, civic virtue is the moral underpinning of how a citizen relates to the society, civic virtue helps people to understand their responsibility within it. The teaching of civic virtue has high sense of communal involvement and value for the oneness and development of the community will positively influence the students' moral development thereby developing patriotism in them.

Respect and Students' Moral Development

Merriam Webster dictionary (2005) defines respect as a positive feeling on action shown toward someone or something considered important, or held in high esteem or regards, it conveys a sense of admiration for good or valuable qualities and it is also the process of honoring someone by exhibiting, care, concern of consideration for their need and feeling. Fernandez (2012) defines respect as a moral value that teaches indigenous individuals about their culture in other word, honouring and hold in high esteem the elders, constituted authority and even the younger ones are expressive of respect and cultural values. Respect is due regard for feeling, opinion and right of others. Interactions that occur within the require mutual respect, respect each other in order to avoid conflicts feeling. Mutual respect is manifested in the form of readiness of the heart to see the differences with other. Disregarding another person's mutual right is something that can reduce the person's excessive individualistic nature towards others (Johnson, 2014). Friendly attitude or manner constitutes acceptance of others with a good heart consciousness does not blame other and always use the proper approach in communicating with others.

The teaching of respect in Christian religious studies helps the students in decision making and expose them to ethical principles which will enable them to live in accordance to the norms and tradition of the society (Johnson and Amanda, 2007). Christianity believes in the law of karma which is synonymous to the golden rule which states "do unto others what you wish them to do you" this teaching has great effects on the decision of students in engaging in immoral acts.

Summarily, respect beholds positive effect in helping the students to abstain from social vices by stating its dangerous implications. Most times, students do not respect other people's feelings because of its effects, but because of the religious teachings imbedded on them particularly on salvation (Jaiyeoba, 2002). So, if teachers stress the dangerous manifestation of disrespectful character, it will develop the students moral reasoning thereby reducing the rate of social vices to its barest minimum (Peter and Erickson, 2014).

Empirical Studies

Considering the importance of Christian Religious Studies topics such as trustworthiness, civic virtue, justice, violence and students' moral development, researches have been carried out by different scholars to examine the effects of these variables on students' moral development. For instance, Bello, Yusuf and Amadi, (2017) investigated on Teachers' trustworthiness as predictor of Secondary School Students' Moral Character in Ilorin South Local Government Area of Kwara State. The

aim of the study was to examine secondary school teachers' level of trustworthiness and how they influence students' moral development, the population of the study was public secondary school in the area, with a sample of 106 teachers and 318 students from 20 secondary schools. Data collected were analyzed using means scores, standard deviation and multiple regressions. The study revealed that teachers' character of trustworthiness predicts secondary school students' moral character.

Lisa Wagner, Willibald Ruch (2015) examined the influence of Christian religious studies on students' moral behaviour between character strength and achievement with the aim of presenting that Christian Religious Studies is indeed an important subject at school and it helps in developing morality among students. The sample of student consisted of 179 German-speaking primary school students (48.6% female) attending the fifth and sixth grade. The sample of teachers consisted of 7 homeroom teachers (77.8% men). The findings of the study revealed that a large number of character strength were linked to teachers who reported positive classroom behavior and school achievement, and that many relationships with achievement were full mediated by positive classroom behavior.

Shoukat, Alifa, Ashiq (2017) was on moral development in private schools and Madrasah in urban and rural area of the District of Lahore. It was a casual comparative retrospection research with the 3x3 factorial designs the stratified sample comprised 900 students of 3-6years boys and girls from private schools and Madrasah. The researchers used Moral Development Interview Inventory (MDII) for collection. The data were analyzed using t-test and ANOVA for finding the significant mean and difference among group. The analysis of data revealed the significant increase in the mortality on every age level of student both private and Madrasah than that of Madrasah sectors. The result show that the students of private school have better moral development than that of Madrasah students in the age stage of early childhood, childhood and adolescence. The study infers that the difference might have occurred due to the different in institutional atmosphere, socio-economic status of students and curricular activities in both sectors. It concluded that students in Madrasah were not provided awareness about moral rules and norms through the teaching of civic virtue in Christian religious studies.

Research on environmental factors influencing the moral behaviour of secondary school students in Owerri Municipal Area, Imo State, Nigeria was carried out by Ngozi R, Ugochi Njoku (2015), the sample size was made up 450 secondary school students sampled randomly from nine (9) public secondary schools purposively selected from the Area of studies. The data collected were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient (PPMC) and mean score standard deviation and t-test statistics. The result showed how school and culture are some of the environmental factors that strongly influence the moral behaviour of the secondary school students. The study recommended that parents should provide adequate and proper guidance to their Children once they are age, students should be ready to take instruction from the teachers, and teachers should be dedicated to carrying out their civic responsibilities.

Research on young people's perception of moral values and kind of influences that shape their behaviour was carried out by Bang Haut (2018) in England at the point of transition from primary to secondary school. The study was based on the 1997 children data collected from interviews, questionnaire surveys and documentary

analysis. The findings of the study revealed that young people have a good understanding of moral value. They value trust, honesty, tolerance etc. It also reveals that young people also demonstrate a high level of moral awareness and an understanding of what makes a good person. It reveals that students trust their elders and see them as important moral against specially student who came from home where these is a lack of positive role models.

This means that schools and the teaching of Christian Religious Studies play importance roles in the moral character development of students, therefore, effort has been made to build that trust and respect. And teachers themselves could help by modeling sound moral character they want their student to cultivate through the teaching of moral instruction.

Area of the Study

This study was carried out in Uyo Local Government Area, Uyo is the capital of Akwa Ibom State, it is made up of 4 clans these are; Ikono clan, Etoi clan, Oku clan and Offot clan with 61 Villages. It covers a land space of 5°1'60N and 7° 55' 36E sharing boundaries with Ibesikpo Asutan, Etinan, Nsit Ibom and Uruan and Itu Local Government Areas. It has estimated number of 436,873 people according to 2006 population census. The people of Uyo predominantly speak Ibibio language fluently. Their major occupation includes trading, farming, oil palm processing etc, reasonable number of the working population are public or civil servants. Tertiary institutions in Uyo Local Government included; University of Uyo, trinity Polytechnic, Uyo City Polytechnic, Uyo Metropolitan Polytechnic, etc. according to Akwa Ibom State Secondary Education Board, Uyo, there are 13 public secondary schools, in Uyo Local Government Area

Design of the Study

The research design for this study was a non-experimental, correlational design utilizing a quantitative survey. Correlational research measures two or more variables for each participant in order to determine the strength and nature of the relationship between those variables. The statistical analysis was conducted to identify patterns in those relationships, but no attempt was made to describe the relationship (Gravetter & Forzano, 2012). The rationale for this study was to determine if there was a relationship in the teaching of Christian Religious Studies and students' moral development.

Population of the Study

The population for this study comprised of all public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. According to State Secondary Education Board (2017), Uyo has a total of 13 public secondary schools with the population of 6,276 male, 9,427 female students making it a total of 15,703 students in public secondary students in Uyo L.G.A for 2017/2018 academic session.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size of this study is 212 senior secondary school students, the simple random sampling technique was used in the study. Simple random sampling with simple piloting was used to select 4 schools from the area. In each of the schools, 53 students

were selected making it a total of 212 students. The names of the schools in the local government were written in a piece of paper and folded, then the method of hat and draw was used to select the schools. The selected schools were used for the study. This method was used because it gives all the schools equal chance of being selected.

Research Instrument

The instrument, the researchers used, was questionnaire entitled "Religious Literacy and Students' Moral Development Questionnaire" (RLSMDQ). Instrument was designed to obtain information from students on their moral development. The questionnaire had an introductory letter and two sections A and B, section A was designed to collect demographic data of respondents while section B had four sections based on research questions consisting of 20 items. Also, 15 Achievement test questions were used to determine the effect of the teaching of Christian religious studies on students. The responses were rated using a four-point rating scale. (SA) Strongly Agreed 4 points, (A) Agreed 3 points, (D) Disagreed 2 points, (SD) Strongly Disagreed 1 point. Negative Skewed items (SD) 1 point, (D) 2 points, (A) 3 points (SA) Strongly Agreed 4 points.

Validity of the instrument

To ensure the validity of the instrument, the initial draft of the instruments was subjected to face validation. It was done by two validates in Department of Curriculum Studies, Educational Management and Planning, and Department of Religious and Cultural Studies, Faculty of Education and Arts. These validates were requested to critically examine the instrument in terms of relevance of the content and clarity of the statement.

Reliability of the instrument

To determine the reliability of the instrument, it was trial tested on 20 students who had the same characteristic of those selected for this study but was not part of the study. Crombach Alpha was used for the reliability of the instrument. This resulted in the reliability coefficient of 0.74 and 0.77. There were considered high enough for the instrument to be used for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

The Pearson Product Moment Coefficient was used to answer the four research hypotheses at 0.5 significant levels. This instrument was considered appropriate for the measurement of relationship of the variables.

Results

Research Questions One

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between trustworthiness and Students' moral development

N = 203					
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	Cal.-r	Remark
	ΣY	ΣY^2			
Trustworthiness	3021	60474	7015	.329	Weak Relationship

Moral Development	3994	84336
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The report in Table 1 shows the nature of relationship between trustworthiness and students' moral development. The result revealed that the calculated r-value of .329 is weak in nature and in a positive direction. This therefore means that there is a positive relationship between trustworthiness and students' moral development.

Research Questions Two

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Justice and fairness and Students' moral development

N=203					
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	Cal.-r	Remark
	ΣY	ΣY^2			
Justice and fairness	2967	59498	9982	.363	Weak Relationship
Moral Development	3994	84336			

The entering in Table 2 reveals the nature of relationship between justice and fairs and students' moral development. The result indicates that the calculated r-value of .363 is weak in nature and in a positive direction. This outcome therefore means that there is positive relationship between trustworthiness and students' moral development.

Research Questions Three

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between civic virtue and Students moral development

N-203					
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	Cal.-r	Remark
	ΣY	ΣY^2			
Respect	2927	58569	12908	.342	Weak Relationship
Moral Development	3994	84336			

The outcome in Table 3 reports the nature of relationship between civic virtue and student's moral development. The result revealed that the calculated r-value of .342 is weak in nature and in a positive direction. This result therefore means that there is a positive relationship between civic virtue and students' moral development

Research Questions Four

Table 4: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between respect and Students moral development

N=203					
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	Cal.-r	Remark
	ΣY	ΣY^2			
Respect	2974	59478	29905	.310	Weak Relationship
Moral Development	3994	84336			

The outcome in Table 4 reports the nature of relationship between respect and student's moral development. The result revealed that the calculated r-value of .310 is weak in nature and in a positive direction. This result therefore means that there is a positive relationship between respect and students' moral development.

Hypothesis 1

Table 5: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between trustworthiness and students' moral development

N=203						
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	r.crit	r-cal	Decision at P-0.05
	ΣY	ΣY^2				
Trustworthiness	3021	60474	7015			
Students' Moral Development		3994	84336	.138	.329	rejected

*significant at P<.05

The entry in Table 5 reports that the calculated r-value of .329 is greater than the critical r-value of .000 at 05 level of significant with 1 and 203 degree of freedom. The result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims a no significant relationship between trustworthiness and students' moral development is rejected. This result reveals that there is a significant relationship between trustworthiness and student's moral development.

Hypothesis 2

Table 6: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Justice and fairness and students' moral development

N=203						
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	r.crit	r-cal	Decision at P-0.05
	ΣY	ΣY^2				
Justice and fairness	2967	59498	9982			
Students' Moral Development		3994	84336	.138	.363**	rejected

*significant at P<.05

The entry in Table 6 reports that the calculated r-value of .363 is greater than the critical r-value of .000 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 203 degree of freedom. The result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims a no significant relationship between justice and fairness and students' moral development is rejected. This result reveals that there is a significant relationship between justice and student's moral development.

Hypothesis 3

Table 7: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between civic virtue and students' moral development

N=203						
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	r.crit	r-cal	Decision at P-0.05
	ΣY	ΣY^2				
Civic virtue	2926	58569	12908			
Students' Moral Development		3994	84336	.138	.342**	rejected

Students' Moral Development 3994 84336

*significant at $P < .05$

The outcome in Table 7 reports that the calculated r-value of .342 is greater than the critical r-value of .000 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 203 degree of freedom. The result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims a no significant relationship between civic virtue and students' moral development is rejected. This result reveals that there is a significant relationship between civic virtue and student's moral development.

Hypothesis 4

Table 8: Pearson Product Moment Correlation of the relationship between Respect and Students' Moral Development

N=203						
Variable	ΣX	ΣX^2	Σxy	r.crit	r-cal	Decision at P-0.05
	ΣY	ΣY^2				
Respect	2974	59478	29905			
Students' Moral Development	3994	84336		.138	.310**	rejected

*Significant at $P < .05$

The entry in Table 8 reports that the calculated r-value of .310 is greater than the critical r-value of .000 at .05 level of significant with 1 and 203 degree of freedom. The result is significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis which claims a no significant relationship between respect and students' moral development is rejected. This result reveals that there is a significant relationship between respect and student's moral development.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study were based on the purpose, research questions and the Hypotheses of the study.

The result of the research question one and the analysis of null hypothesis one revealed that teaching of trustworthiness in Christian Religious Studies has a great relationship with the students' moral development. Hence, the null hypothesis, which speculated a non-relationship between the teaching of trustworthiness and student's moral development is rejected and the alternative is retained. This result may be attributed to the fact that if the Christian religious studies teacher teaches the students to be honest in their dealing with fellow students, making and fulfilling their promises, it will develop their moral reasoning. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Bello, Yusuf and Amadi (2017) who researched on the teaching of Christian religious studies as emotional intelligence and character predictor of secondary school student's moral character in Ilorin south Local Government Area of Kwara State. The study revealed that secondary school teachers' moral character predicts secondary school student's behaviour. Therefore, teachers need to be enlightened on the moral role through character education which will not only educate them but will also help to cultivate sound moral character in them.

The result of the research question two and the analysis of null hypothesis two revealed that the teaching of Justice in Christian Religious Studies has a great

relationship with the student's moral development. Hence, the null hypothesis, which speculated a non-relationship with teaching of justice and students' moral development is rejected and the alternative is retained. This result may be attributed to the fact that teacher who inculcate high level of fairness, impartiality and self-discipline on students through the teaching of Christian religious studies will invariably influence the students' character of passing judgment and ensuring discipline among his student. The finding of this study is in agreement with Nelson (2012) who conducted a qualitative study of effective school discipline practice: reception of administrators, tenured teachers, and parents in 20 schools in East Tennessee, data was collected from administrator and tenured teachers through an open-ended interview. The result of the study concluded that teachers are responsible for carrying out the school discipline practice to foster appropriate behaviour.

The result of the research question three and the analysis of null hypothesis three revealed that the teaching of civic virtue has a great relationship with the student's moral development. Hence, the null hypothesis, which speculated a non-relationship with the teaching of civic virtue on students' moral development is rejected and the alternative is retained. This result may be attributed to the fact that teachers who teach the students how to law abiding and impacting positive values on students will invariably influence the student's civic character there by helping them to live according to the norms and tradition of the society. This is in accordance research conducted by Bang Haut (2018) on young people's perception of moral values and kind of influences that shape their behaviour in England at the point of transition from primary to secondary school. The findings of the study revealed that young people demonstrate a high level of moral awareness and an understanding of what makes a good person. This means that teachers play importance role in the character development of students, therefore effort have to be made to build that virtue and sound moral character they want the student to cultivate.

The result of the research question one and the analysis of null hypothesis four revealed that teaching of respect in Christian Religious Studies has a great relationship with the students' moral development. Hence, the null hypothesis, which speculated a non-relationship with the teaching of respect on students' moral development is rejected and the alternative is retained. Furthermore, a teacher who teaches the students to show respect to the national pledge, anthem etc. will unconsciously influence his students' sense of patriotism and invariably impacting good morals on them for collective wellbeing of the community and the nation at large. This finding is in agreement with the finding of Ngozi (2015) on environmental factors influencing the moral behaviour of secondary school students in Owerri municipal area of Imo State, Nigeria. The result of the finding revealed that school and culture are some of the environmental factors that strongly influence the behaviour of secondary school students. The study recommends that teachers should provide adequate and proper guidance to the students once they are of age in the approved pattern of behavior while student should be ready to take instruction from their teachers and show dedication to their duties and responsibilities.

Conclusion

Students' moral development is always important to the teachers, the family and the society at large. Every teacher expects their children to abstain from immoral

behaviour so as to become useful to the society as such they should endeavor to show concern to their physical, emotional, social and academic wellbeing. The result from this study has revealed that there is a significance relationship between the teaching of religious literacy in order to shape the moral development of students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings from this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should not only focus on teaching the students to pass exams, they should also pay attention to inculcating good values on the students so as to enable them live in accordance with the norms and tradition of the society.
2. They should also endeavor to attend seminars called by the educational policy makers to keep abreast with the programmes of the schools to help the students abstain from immoral acts.
3. School authorities are advised to firmly enforce disciplinary measures so as to discipline any students who engage in social vices such as cultism, examination malpractice, premarital sex, robbery etc. This will help in developing morality among the students.
4. The government should state the importance of teaching Christian religious studies in schools and also stress the dangerous outcome and punishments of moral decadence among students through the mass media, handbills, putting it in our educational sector etc. this will reduce the rate of immorality among the students.

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TRENDS IN EDUCATION MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM (EMIS) IMPLEMENTATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Education is seen as the bedrock of any sustainable development in many countries. This importance necessitated this paper on trends in Education Management Information System (EMIS) implementation in secondary schools in Nigeria. It streamlined the conceptual meaning of EMIS and its conceptual relationships. The paper drew the line of importance and issues militating against the implementation of EMIS. In the end, the paper, through prospects, showcased the future of EMIS, while concluding that the implementation of EMIS will allow for effective management of the schools.

Key Words: Trends, Education Management Information System (EMIS), Implementation, Secondary Schools.

Introduction

It is generally agreed that education is the bedrock of sustainable development. The education system in Nigeria is designed such that Secondary schools serve as the bridge between Primary and Tertiary institutions with the broad goals of preparing people for useful living in the society and for higher education and this has made it imperative that it should, among others, supply trained manpower in the applied science, technology and commerce at sub-professional levels; inspire its students with the desire for self-improvement and achievement of excellence; raise a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others; and respect the dignity of labour (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2004).. In order to enable stakeholders, make informed decisions on sustainable educational development. Ministry of Education and other stakeholders need unambiguous and timely data and information to support them in completion of their responsibilities (UNESCO, 2008). The importance of accurate information for decision making cannot be over emphasized. However, it has been noticed that implementation of Education Management Information System (EMIS) has not been satisfactory, with plethora of arears that

require urgent revamp and improvement. This research work serves to highlight those areas and proffer solution to them.

Education Management Information System (EMIS)

Many agree that education is a purposeful activity directed at achieving certain aims, especially the transmission of knowledge as well as fostering skills and character traits (Chazan, 2022). Education management is a herculean task. The school system and auxiliary systems that support it must all work efficiently together for a robust educational system in Nigeria. Babalola (2006) opined that education management is conceived as being able to handle carefully and un-wastefully what happens in the process of educating people so that everything works out according to plan.

It is important to note that Education Management Information System is subset of Management Information System. According to Baltzan et. al (2008), Management Information Systems is a business function just as marketing, finance, operations, and human resource management are. He further defines Management Information Systems (MIS) as the function that plans for, develops, implements, and maintains Information Technology hardware, software, and applications that people use to support the goals of an organization. The goal at this instant is Education.

(Extracted from Nganjiozor, (2016))

Explanation of EMIS Conceptual Relation

- (i) National EMIS is located with the Federal Ministry of Education.
- (ii) Directives, guidelines and demands for information are sent to schools through schools’ management boards.
- (iii) Reports from schools flow back through the same channel to the top for decision making.

- (iv) The three bold rectangles indicate major sources of information that need greater attention.
- (v) At each point of administrative channel – State, Local Government School Authorities – not only receive and pass information, but processes, analyses and uses the information.
- (vi) In all directions are arrows pointing inwards and outwards signifying information exchange and feedback at all levels. (Nganjiozor, 2016).

There is no general consensus as to how Education Management Information System could be defined. Nganjiozor, 2016) defines Education Management Information System (EMIS) as a system for the collection, integration, processing, maintenance and dissemination of data and information to support decision making, planning, policy-analysis, monitoring and evaluation of all levels of education system. In other words, it comprises of important components, different units that make up the entire system. He further defined it as a system of people, technology, models, methods, processes, procedures, rules and regulations that function together to provide comprehensive, integrated set of relevant and timely education data to planners, decision makers and managers of education at all levels. Anderson (2014) describes EMIS is an organized group of information and documentation services that collects, stores, processes, analyses and disseminates information for educational planning and management.

It would not be wrong to surmise that EMIS is an educational database. A database is any collection of data, or information, that is specially organized for rapid search and retrieval by a computer. Databases are structured to facilitate the storage, retrieval, modification, and deletion of data in conjunction with various data-processing operations. (Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2022). However, there more to EMIS than a database.

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2020), elaborated EMIS as, in its most basic sense, constitutes a school census conducted annually to collect information on pupils, teachers, facilities, finances, and other issues relating to institutions such as schools and higher education facilities. It must be noted, however, that earlier conceptions of EMIS were primarily (perhaps exclusively) administrative systems, rather than systems that inform planning, policymaking, and monitoring and evaluation.

Importance of EMIS

Just like in other business functions, coupling Education with Management Information Systems, was aimed at ensuring that accurate information is generated to help improve effectiveness and efficiency of education system. In his paper, Nganjiozor (2016), highlighted the importance of EMIS to include amongst others; Allows for setting of new policies and revising old ones based on evidence instead of self-perceptions. Strengthens capacities in collecting, processing, storing, analysing management, planning and dissemination of information at all levels of the education system. Stakeholders such as parents require information about education institutions and student outcomes in order to make decisions about education choices and opportunities. It is noteworthy that the quality and experiences to which a student is

exposed largely determine the quality of the output and the extent secondary school achieves its goal of educating the student (Ejimofofor & Okonkwo, 2022).

UNESCO (2010), stressed that EMIS' main purpose is to integrate information related to the management of educational activities, and make it available in comprehensive yet succinct ways to a variety of users. Nwankwo (2020) suggests these users to include teachers, principals, curriculum planners, inspectorate officials, financial controllers, planners, policy advisers and political leaders, as well as parents and students. Thus, integrating the various sources of educational management information into one coordinated system to serve the entire country is the sole aim of EMIS (UNESCO, 2008)

Logically, every country has some kind of functioning EMIS no matter how limited and rudimentary the data collected may be. (UNESCO, 2010). Nwankwo (2020) argues that in some poor countries, EMIS is highly manual, in other words, an annual statistical report may be the principal manifestation for general public consumption. The nominal roll of teachers which includes their discipline, and other biodata, the attendance register of students and teachers, are all forms of EMIS. Since EMIS is very important for sustainable educational development, how has its implementation in Nigerian schools faring.

Issues of EMIS Implementation in Secondary Schools in Nigeria

In modern age, accurate data and information is very important for planning and decision making. Lack of accurate and timely data has long been the bane of policy formulation and planning in all sectors of the Nigerian economy, according to Nganjiozor (2016). To buttress this point, he further stated that an International Labour Organization (ILO) Mission to Nigeria in 1981 noted that "policy making in Nigeria, given the present state of statistics, is like trying to run through the forest in dark without a torch light."

Despite this gloomy spotlight, Nigeria has attempted to address the inadequacies in accurate data gathering by the establishment of the National Data Bank (NDB) in 1986 and the Nigeria Education Management Information System in 1988. (Nganjiozor, 2016). Meanwhile, in 2007 the National Council on Education (NCE) approved EMIS to support the effective management of the education system at the Federal, State and Local Government levels to improve the performance of the education system as a whole and of students in particular (Nwankwo, 2020). However, data and observations have shown that the data management situation is chaotic as operators in the system have different set of data for such indicators as enrolments, number of teachers and lots more.

During the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD, 2016), some issues were identified as common hindrances to the implementation of EMIS in schools, especially so in developing countries. Data quality is the paramount of them all, exacerbated by other factors some peculiar to some countries. Nwankwo (2016) focused his attention on this matter by stating a unique Nigerian problem – States and Local government authorities and schools from which data originate have the tendency to falsify or inflate data in anticipation of more Federal funding or funds from international donor agencies, further complicating the data management situation. This have given rise to terms as ghost teachers and ghost students. This particular problem

leads to confusion and non-availability of accurate and reliable data for policy makers and stakeholders in the sector.

In summary, the main obstacle for accurate data gathering and implementation of EMIS in Nigerian secondary schools are:

1. **Lack of accurate and reliable data:** Data must be accurate and should sufficiently reflect in totality the stable and consistent collection processes at all time. UNESCO (2020) observed that as discussed during the 2018 EMIS conference, most countries (more than half) reported that the accuracy and reliability of data were among the challenges with many countries reporting lack of adequate mechanisms for data validation. Moreover, in some cases, there are virtually no repercussions for falsifying or tampering with data; where there might be laws supposed to safeguard against data falsification, there are no mechanisms to ensure the enforcement of those laws, as such, availability of accurate data is a problem.
2. **Coverage of EMIS:** UNESCO (2020) further observes that in terms of availability, countries cited challenges in obtaining data and information from Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), primarily owing to generally weaker data systems in these kinds of organizations. With private organizations, countries cited difficulties obtaining data as well, for various reasons. In some cases, private organizations are unregistered and thus difficult to track. In other cases, private organizations are not willing to release data. Furthermore, these private organizations are often not within the purview of the Ministry of Education, and thus have no regulatory authorities that can require them to release data.
3. **Decentralized structures:** A more decentralized system would improve the planning, management and decision-making allowing for more efficient and accurate data collection and increase accountability (UNESCO, 2017). As with any type of governance structure, whether centralized or decentralized, a system can only function properly under the appropriate enabling environment. Developing an effective decentralized structure for EMIS data requires engaging in several decision-making processes. These include: 1) identifying the right balance between direct government control over education institutions and staff, and the degree of autonomy given to them, which depends to a large extent on existing organizational and institutional capacities; and 2) developing effective tools for monitoring and evaluation, which are often in the form of school inspection or supervision systems (IIEP UNESCO, 2012).
4. **Fragility and conflict:** Where there is conflict, unrest and displacement caused by natural phenomena or humans like in the North-East by Boko-haram or recent flooding in the South-South, gathering data is always a challenge if not impossible. EMIS must be able to collect data on learners in displaced and vulnerable population to allow the education system to identify their needs and how best to address them (UNESCO, 2020). children in emergency situations are the most vulnerable, and yet they are often excluded from EMIS. While sometimes included in datasets, they are often not indicated as refugees or internally displaced people. According to UNESCO (2020) there are several issues at play: for instance, some conflict areas are no longer controlled by the

government and data can therefore no longer be sent to the centralized institution. Generally, data quality is low in crisis-affected schools, and data take longer to be collected, as well.

5. Inadequate or lack of Infrastructure: A fully functional EMIS requires not only accurate data collection, human resources and the community but also Information Technology (IT) infrastructure. Policy makers in Nigeria pay lip services to these needs. Many schools have computers, but how many them have constant electricity supply, needless to mention that this necessity is not even available in some. In some cases, lack of access roads or other means of transportation for getting to isolated settlements has also contributed to issues and challenges of EMIS in Nigeria.

Prospects of EMIS Implementation in Secondary Schools in Nigeria

EMIS implementation would strengthen the education statistical system in Nigeria by linking and assembling different existing information systems, integrates and synthesizes them in one single system of all education data both the quantitative and qualitative, and produce more relevant, reliable and timely data needed at every tier of government for strategic planning, policy formulation and decision support initiative in education (Nganjiozor, 2016).

Secondary school education will be more efficient as here are some factors that enable a conducive environment for EMIS to be functional, effective and efficient (UNESCO, 2020). UNESCO (2020) further highlights these as;

- (i) An education data policy or legal framework: A policy or legal framework mandating education data can have a significant influence on the effectiveness and credibility of an education management information system. However, there is currently no international agreement on what the content of such policy should look like, and it can therefore achieve as little or as much as policy-makers want to make of it (UNESCO,2020). Some principles have been identified that should be inherent in an education data policy. According to the World Bank (2016) These include technical independence in data collection, free of external interference and following ethical standards, so as to increase data credibility. This needs to be of course accompanied by high-quality standards in all data functions. Data openness and transparency are other guiding principles, which will allow an easy access to the public, which in turn will foster a stronger sense of accountability on the part of authorities (Lovely, 2011). Conversely, data restriction hinders collaboration, innovation, and service improvement (OECD, 2011) Finally, an education data strategy must be flexible enough to cover different technological, managerial, and institutional solutions to EMIS challenges, and should be drafted with a medium- or long-term vision in mind.
- (ii) Technological infrastructure and capacities: There are technological solutions that can improve education management information systems effectiveness. For instance, as mentioned by Burundi in the 2018 EMIS conference (UNESCO, 2020), electronic transfer of information from schools to the Ministry of Education through mobile devices (including computers,

tablets and smartphones), can help transition from a paper-and-pencil system to an automated one, which will in turn reduce the time and costs associated with data collection and processing. Data validity checks with specialized software can improve data quality and harmonization by removing errors originated in manual data aggregates. A cohabitation of technologies is a potential solution, wherein manual and automated methods are both used.

- (iii) Adequate human resources: A functional EMIS does require skilled staff, with qualifications and basic training in statistics, coding, data analytics, data analytics, data visualization, data collection methods, IT engineering and Computer programming amongst others. Competencies become even more specialized and precious in areas in conflict or emergencies (UNESCO, 2020) UNESCO further highlights the need of developing the appropriate skills within Ministries of Education which can help reduce dependence on external technical providers, and strengthen the capacity to engage and manage external providers. For this, it is important that countries dedicate sufficient budget to train and update EMIS staff.
- (iv) Sufficient financial resources: when financial resources are not available, implementation of EMIS will not and cannot be successful. It is important to note that, according to UNESCO (2020) funds are required to amongst others; (1) Recruit and pay personnel dedicated to EMIS tasks at various administrative levels (national, regional, district and school level). (2) Procure ICT infrastructure and technology that include hardware and equipment (computers, mobile devices, data servers, etc.), software, internet connectivity, physical space needed; (3) Service costs involving recurrent costs such as IT license renewal fees, technical support for hardware and software, and technicians to repair connectivity issues, etc.; and (4) Data collection and reporting of annual school census, involving costs for printing and copying, logistics for distribution and collection of forms, publication of statistical reports, the list is endless. Thus legislating and approving funds for EMIS implementation at all levels of government is important.

The future development of EMIS in Nigeria will depend largely on the successful integration of multiple kinds of data, from multiple sources within and external to the education system, and from multiple levels in the education system Integration will only be possible if there is compatibility across multiple subsystems and ability of data generating agencies to cooperate with each other to have a single Data collation, processing, Analysis and Dissemination centre (Nganjiozor, 2016). Without considering and implementing the four main factors above, our secondary schools will still be lagging behind in the modern age due to lack of accurate data for policy makers.

Conclusion

Implementation of Education Management Information System (EMIS) will allow for efficient education management in all spheres of the education. It affords stakeholders accurate and up-to-date information on students' enrolment, status of infrastructure, attendance of both teachers and student and other necessary information. It therefore makes allocation of funds and addressing other needs arising from analysis of this timely information easier and accurate. It is important and a matter of urgency

for government and stakeholders in education sector in Nigeria to address the need to fully implement EMIS in our school system, especially at secondary school level.

Recommendations

As agreed by many authors, implementation of EMIS in Secondary Schools in Nigeria is ongoing, but not at an efficient level. For stakeholders to ensure complete implementation of EMIS and reap its benefit in planning, the following recommendations must be implemented as a matter of urgency:

- (1) Laws mandating accurate data collections and penalties for falsifying data should not only be made but implemented because accurate data is the foundation of EMIS and planning.
- (2) Government, non-governmental organizations, communities and individuals must synergize in providing electricity, computers and other mobile devices, and other infrastructure required for accurate data collection, analysis, storage and retrieval so that stakeholders can have access to accurate data at all times.
- (3) Funding of education should be prioritized by the government. It has been observed that Nigerian government at all levels may dedicate a chunk of their annual budget to the Education Sector, but actual releases and implementation becomes a far cry. Government policies and funding is important for EMIS implementation.
- (4) Training and re-training of personnel at all levels of EMIS implementation is as crucial as all other factors mentioned above. Putting a square peg in a round hole will complicate issues. There is need to consistently train personnel on how EMIS could be efficiently implemented in Nigerian Schools, especially at the Secondary School level.

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IMPACT OF INSECURITY ON THE IMPLEMENTATION AND ATTAINMENT OF UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION GOALS' PROGRAMME IN KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA (2018-2019)

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Abstract

The study investigated impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of Universal Basic Education goals' programme in Katsina State, Nigeria from 2018 to 2019. The study is guided by two objectives hence two research questions and two null formulated hypotheses. The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 8769 comprising 8673 public primary school teachers and 96 LGEA officials in the eight (8) affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State. A sample size of 370 respondents was used. A simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of the respondents. A self-developed (structured) questionnaire was used in the study as instrument for data collection. The instrument was structured on four points rating scale. The instrument was validated and pilot tested where the reliability index of 0.71 was obtained using Cronbach Alpha technique. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentages as well as inferential statistic of t-test for independents sample were employed for data analyses, which were processed with the aid of SPSS version 23.0. The study revealed that the presence of kidnapping, banditry and cattle restlessness constitutes negative impact towards the attainment of UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy in public primary schools; and attainment of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory Basic Education for every Nigerian child of school age has negatively affected public primary schools due to insecurity challenges facing some Local Government Areas in Katsina State. Therefore, the study recommended that Katsina State Government, school authorities, community leaders and parents should ensure that adequate security measures be put in place to curtail the menace of insecurity in order to provide secured-enabling learning environments for the successful implementation and attainment of appropriate literacy and numeracy for human capital development in the state; and that the Katsina State Government should continue to provide free and compulsory education to all children in the State in order to address problem of dropped out and pupils' access to education in IDPs, this will enhance their continuous schooling.

Key Words: Insecurity, Implementation, Attainment, UBE Programme

Introduction

Education has been described as a veritable tool for socio-economic growth and technological advancement of a nation. Education is a process by which individuals are assisted formally through proper direction and guidance to develop their capacities not only for their own benefit but for the society at large (Okeke, 2003). This is to say that the essence of education is to develop individuals so that they can become effective and efficient in what they do, and also contribute to the advancement of the society where they live. It is in realization of the importance of education of the child that the government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in its 1999 constitution made a declaration on the right of every Nigerian child to education, irrespective of gender, tribe, religion or race. It makes sense to state that the lofty vision of education as enunciated in the constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria would be realized in a serene and conducive school environment. Lehr (2014) stressed that the noble goals of education can never be achieved in a vacuum, but rather in a conducive and peaceful school environment. In any education system, peace and tranquility is an antidote for a successful teaching and learning. Whenever there is a feeling of insecurity within and outside the school environment, both students and teachers are likely to be deterred and this may inhibit academic performance of the students.

The concept of insecurity connotes the state or quality of being insecure. In support of this, Imam (2014) defines insecurity as the state or condition of not being free from danger or threat in the daily activities of human beings. Security in simple terms means protection of lives and properties from destruction. According to Onifode, Imhonopl and Uorim (2013), security is the dynamic condition which involves the relative ability of a state to counter threats to its core values and interest and their primary beneficiaries are the citizens. In addition, sharing this view, Abraham Maslow states that “an insecure person perceives the world as a life-threatening jungle, feels unsafe, unhappy, rejected, hostile, and pessimistic, shows a sign of tension, conflict and guilt, and tends to be neurotic and generally egocentric”. It therefore seems that when students study in an environment that is characterized by insecurity, they may suffer socially, mentally and emotionally and it makes sense hypothetically to state that all these are likely to affect not only their behavior and psychosocial adjustment but may also affect their academic performance.

Universal Basic Education according to National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (NPE, 2014) is the type of education received at primary school level up to junior secondary school level. According to the Universal Basic Education Commission (2004), the objectives of the Universal Basic Education include provision of scholarship to drop out of school children through the basic education program; ensure the acquisition of the appropriate levels of literacy, manipulative and life skills (as well as the ethical, moral and civic values needed for laying the foundation for life-long learning); develop the entire citizens with a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its education; provide free, compulsory, universal basic education for every Nigerian students of school age group, and reduce drastically, drop outrage from the formal school system through improved relevance and efficiency curriculum.

Universal Basic Education implies transmission of basic knowledge to all children in Nigeria from generation to generation. It has two main components—

Universal and Basic Education. 'Universal' means a programme that is meant for all arms of the society such as the poor and the rich, the physically challenged and all the school dropouts. While 'Basic Education' means the beginning of acquisition of desirable skill, knowledge and attitude in a formal school system. Sadiq (2013) asserted that an educated population is an asset to a nation due to the fact that education promotes national security as it inculcates desirable human traits like honesty, sincerity, hard-work, punctuality, productivity, innovation, patriotism, selflessness, brotherhood, friendship. In a similar vein, Fahd al-Qudah cited in Ekpo and Is'haq (2014) submits that when a nation is successful in developing (educating) its people as strong and complete individuals, it will be able to realize a glorious future for herself, promote peace within her boundary and defend her sovereignty. However, whenever a nation fails to develop (educate) its citizenry and make them deficient in carrying out some of the activities of life effectively, then that nation is doomed to weakness, destruction and obscurity. Thus, as the menace of insecurity continues to loom into many societies in the state, it's believed that all human endeavors particularly educational activities may come to halt. Students' life and right to education could be neglected or deprived leading to societal degradation.

Various researchers such as Abdurashheed, Onuselogu, Obioma (2015) and Aja, Egwu, Aja-okorie, Ani, Amuta, (2018) emphasized that; lack or inadequate instructional resources, poor infrastructures, poor management, corruption and government policy as the possible factors militating against failure in U.B.E program in Nigeria. These perhaps were the possible causes of poor quality of education in Nigeria and students' academic performance. This to state that students perform poorly in their academic work not because they do not possess the mental ability to do well, but because of many factors such as the poor state of learning environment (schools). Learning environment is an essential requirement for smooth teaching and learning process to take place because students' study habits are to a large extent tied to it. A good learning environment presents learning as a lifelong enterprise and enables students to discover appropriate value system that can be their compass for self-awareness and national consciousness. Security may be among the leading factors that favor students' learning appropriateness. Disappointingly, schools in Nigeria especially in the northern region have been experiencing great operational closure as a result of incessant cases of banditry, cattle rustling, armed robbery, kidnapping, bombings, abductions and rape, among others.

Katsina State is one of the States in the North-West zone of Nigeria presently being affected by the activities of arm-bandits, cattle rustling and kidnapping. This affects mainly the eight frontline Local Government Areas (LGAs) namely Jibia, Batsari, Safana, Danmusa, Kankara, Faskari, Dandume and Sabuwa. The situation becomes so bad and terrifying as even the incumbent Governor of the state confessed that the state was under serious siege by bandits and kidnappers. This calls for the rise of so many questions as; do schools operate in this devastating condition? Do students attend learning sessions as usual? Could UBE program goals be achievable? Thus, a gap exists which needs to be filled, therefore, the present paper investigated the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goals program implementation in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019).

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to find out the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goals programme implementation in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019). Specifically, the study is set to:

1. find out the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019); and
2. determine the impact of insecurity on the implementation and attainment of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education for every Nigerian student of school age group among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina state, Nigeria (2018-2019).

Research Questions

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. What is the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of the appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019)?
2. What is the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian student of school age group among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019)?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses are formulated for testing at significance level of 0.05.

- Ho₁** There is no significant impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019).
- Ho₂** There is no significant impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian student of school age group among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina state, Nigeria (2018-2019).

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 8769 comprising 8673 public primary school teachers and 96 LGEA officials in the eight (8) affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State. A sample size of 370 respondents was used. A simple random sampling technique was used for the selection of the respondents. A self-developed (structured) questionnaire was used in the study as instrument for data collection. The instrument was structured on four points rating scale. The instrument was validated and pilot tested with the reliability index of 0.71 obtained using Cronbach Alpha technique. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts

and percentages as well as inferential statistic of t-test for independents sample were employed for data analyses, which were processed with the aid of SPSS version 23.0.

Data Presentation, Interpretation and Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis of the Respondents' Opinion of the Impact of Insecurity on Implementation and Attainment of UBE Goal of Ensuring Acquisition of Appropriate Levels of Literacy and Numeracy among Primary Schools in the Affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State (2018-2019)

S/N	Statement Item	Respondents	SA	A	%	D	SD	%
1	Prevalence of insecurity threat affects UBE goal of pupils' acquisition of literacy in basic science subject in primary schools.	Teachers	57	201	81	40	19	19
		LGEAs	04	11	58	07	04	42
2	Insecurity problem negatively disrupts schools' activities and hence undermines pupils' acquisition of foreign languages literacy in primary schools.	Teachers	89	182	85	28	18	15
		LGEAs	06	13	73	06	01	27
3	UBE goal of pupils' acquisition of literacy in civic education is negatively affected due to the challenge of insecurity.	Teachers	78	133	67	94	12	33
		LGEAs	07	09	62	07	03	38
4	Insecurity problem ravaging the schools' hosting communities does not disrupt pupils' acquisition of permanent numeracy and literacy in mathematics.	Teachers	25	76	32	193	23	68
		LGEAs	02	06	31	09	03	46
5	Prevalence of insecurity threats has negative impact on UBE goal of pupils' acquisition of literacy in physical and health education subject in primary schools.	Teachers	33	192	71	72	20	29
		LGEAs	05	12	65	07	02	35
6	Acquisition of UBE literacy goal in vocational education among primary school pupils is not hampered due to insecurity.	Teachers	06	30	11	187	94	89
		LGEAs	02	04	23	12	08	77
7	Insecurity problem affects UBE goal of acquisition of literacy in local languages among primary school pupils in my area.	Teachers	61	208	85	38	10	15
		LGEAs	03	15	69	06	02	31
8	Insecurity problem has negatively impacted on UBE goal of acquisition of literacy in religious subject among primary school pupils in my area.	Teachers	32	185	68	82	18	32
		LGEAs	06	08	54	07	05	46
9	Supervision exercise as strategy for ensuring quality of in primary school education is being carried out in spite of insecurity challenges in this local government area.	Teachers	12	52	20	204	49	80
		LGEAs	01	04	19	18	03	81
10	Insecurity threat undermines teachers' quality towards accomplishment of UBE goal of acquisition of appropriate level of literacy among primary schools in this local government.	Teachers	68	203	80	31	15	20
		LGEAs	08	11	81	05	02	19

The Table 1 presents teachers' and LGEA officials' responses to item 1-10. The items attempted to survey their opinion of the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy among Primary Schools in the Affected Local Government Areas from 2018 to 2019 in Katsina State. The result showed that the respondents have agreed with (very high per cent response rates) that insecurity challenges have negatively impacted pupils' acquisition of literacy in; basic science subject, foreign languages, civic education, permanent numeracy and literacy in mathematics, physical and health education, vocational and skills education, local languages, religious subject, conduct of

supervision exercise by the education authorities, and undermining quality of teachers’ instructional activities towards implementation and accomplishment of UBE goal of acquisition of appropriate level of literacy among primary schools in the Local Government Areas.

Table 2: Descriptive Analysis of the Respondents’ Opinion of the Impact of Insecurity on Implementation and Attainment of UBE Goal of Provision of Free and Compulsory Universal Basic Education among Primary Schools in the Affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State (2018-2019)

S/N	Statement Items	Respondents	SA	A	%	D	SD	%
11	Insecurity problem affects UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to nursery schools’ pupils in this local government area.	Teachers	68	206	86	35	08	14
		LGEAs	02	14	62	08	02	38
12	Insecurity threat in this local government area affects UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to primary schools’ pupils	Teachers	66	219	90	25	07	10
		LGEAs	02	16	69	03	05	31
13	Insecurity challenge is a key factor responsible for primary schools’ pupils drop out in this local government, thereby affects UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education.	Teachers	80	221	95	06	10	05
		LGEAs	06	09	62	07	04	38
14	Insecurity threat necessitates primary school pupils stay at home in this local government area and this greatly affects UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education.	Teachers	82	216	94	13	06	06
		LGEAs	03	14	65	06	03	35
15	Bandits’ invasion to educational institutions necessitates parents’ withdrawal of their wards from primary schools in this local government and this cause woeful failure to UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education.	Teachers	67	211	88	29	10	12
		LGEAs	02	18	77	06	00	23
16	Insecurity threats necessitate people’s migration and thus undermine UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to pupils in this local government area.	Teachers	55	246	95	12	04	05
		LGEAs	05	19	92	02	00	08
17	Insecurity challenge is not a key factor responsible for teachers’ low turnout primary schools and this affects UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to pupils in this local government.	Teachers	12	21	10	198	86	90
		LGEAs	01	02	20	20	03	88
18	The UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education is undermined because of teachers’ incessant transfer due to insecurity	Teachers	38	235	86	34	11	14
		LGEAs	06	14	77	05	01	23
19	Teaching and learning facilities necessary for the implementation of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to primary schools’ pupils in this local government were not adequately provided due to insecurity threats.	Teachers	17	41	18	195	64	82
		LGEAs	04	04	31	12	06	69
20	Infrastructural facilities necessary for the implementation of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to primary schools’ pupils are not in deplorable condition despite the presence insecurity threats in this local government area.	Teachers	76	170	78	56	18	22
		LGEAs	05	11	62	07	03	38

The Table 2 presents teachers’ and LGEA officials’ responses to item 11-20. The items attempted to survey their opinions on the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of provision of free and compulsory universal basic education for every

Nigerian student of school age group among primary schools in the affected Local Government Areas from 2018 to 2019 in Katsina State. The result showed that the respondents have agreed with (very high per cent response rates) that insecurity challenges have negatively impacted UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to; nursery schools' pupils, primary schools' pupils, increase pupils' drop-out rate, pupils stay at home, parents' withdrawal of their wards from schools, people's migration, teachers' low turnout schools, incessant rate teachers' seeking transfer and shortage of facilities and infrastructures necessary for the implementation of the programme.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis one: there is no significant impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina State, Nigeria (2018-2019). In testing this hypothesis, inferential statistics of t-test for independent sample was employed and processed on SPSS (Version 23). The detail of the result was presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Result of t-test Analysis of Difference of Respondents' Opinion of the Impact of Insecurity on Implementation and Attainment of UBE Goal of Ensuring Acquisition of Appropriate Levels of Literacy and Numeracy among Primary Schools in the Affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State

Respondents	N	Mean	Stand. Deviation	Stand. Error	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Teachers	317	21.2361	3.86854	.25344	2	-.672	.176	Retained
LGEA officials	26	21.6182	3.45602	.46601	341			
Total	343							

The result in Table 3 shows that the computed t-value (-.6721), (df =341) and P-value =1.76 which is greater than the Alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinion regarding the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy among primary schools in the affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State retained. This is because, the first group (teachers) obtained a Mean score of 21.2361 with corresponding Standard Deviation, 3.86854 which is almost the same Mean scores of 21.6182 and corresponding Standard Deviation, 3.45602 obtained by the second group (LGEA officials).

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian student of school age group among primary schools in the affected local government areas in Katsina state, Nigeria. In testing this hypothesis, inferential statistics of t-test for independent sample

was employed and processed on SPSS (Version 23). The detail of the result was presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Result of t-test Analysis of Difference of Respondents' Opinion of the Impact of Insecurity on Implementation and Attainment of UBE Goal of Provision of Free and Compulsory Universal Basic Education among Primary Schools in the Affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State

Respondents	N	Mean	Stand. Deviation	Stand. Error	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Teachers	317	18.2876	3.14021	.20572	2	0.914	0.340	Retained
LGEA officials	26	19.0545	2.97781	.40153	341			
Total	343							

The result in Table 4 shows that the computed t-value (0.914), (df =341) and P-value =0.340 which is greater than the Alpha value of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the respondents' opinion regarding the impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory universal basic education for every Nigerian student of school age group among primary schools in the Affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State retained. This is because, the first group (teachers) obtained a Mean score of 18.2876 with corresponding Standard Deviation, 3.14021 which is almost the same Mean scores of 19.0545 and corresponding Standard Deviation, 2.97781 obtained by the second group (LGEA officials).

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that most of the respondents agreed that presence of kidnapping, banditry and cattle restlessness has negatively affected the attainment of UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy in basic science, foreign languages (English, French and Arabic), civic education, mathematics, physical and health education, vocational education, local languages, religious subjects, supervision exercise, teachers' quality in public primary schools in the Affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State. This finding lends credence to the finding of Ojukwu (2017) who reported that as a result of insecure school environment students are afraid and feel insecure, skip school, miss certain lessons, lose interest in school and academic activities which affect them during their examinations leading to truancy on the part of the boys while girls drop out and settle for married life because they feel insecure within their school environment. The finding is also in line with Ojukwu and Nwanma (2015) who found that as a result of insecurity of the school environment many a time female staff and students complain of being raped or impregnated leading to their being dropped out of school.

The finding of the study also revealed that the respondents were of the opinion that insecurity problem affects UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education to nursery and primary schools' pupils. This situation necessitates, people's migration leaving their homes, pupils' drop out, parents' withdrawal of their wards from primary schools, children staying at home, inadequate provision of teaching and

learning facilities necessary for the implementation of UBE goal of provision of free and compulsory basic education in the affected Local Government Areas in Katsina State. The finding is in line with Joshua and Ibeitan (2016) submission, that inability of a good number of youths to live a decent life as a result of either lack of education or quality education is responsible for their joblessness and poverty, making crime attractive to them, and as such becoming agents of insecurity. It is therefore not surprising that havoc might engulf the society when government fails to provide free and compulsory quality education to its citizens. This assertion is in line with Radda (2013) who opines that education, when well-imparted and utilized, has the potency of promoting national security because most uneducated jobless and educated jobless youths are easily attracted to crimes, thereby, constituting insecurity in a country.

Conclusion

This paper surveyed impact of insecurity on implementation and attainment of Universal Basic Education goals' programme implementation in Katsina State, Nigeria from 2018 to 2019. The result showed that: UBE goal of ensuring acquisition of appropriate levels of literacy and numeracy; and provision of free and compulsory Basic Education in most of the public primary schools in Jibia, Batsari, Safana, Danmusa, Kankara, Faskari, Sabuwa and Dandume were not successfully attained due to the insecurity challenges in the areas.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) that Katsina State Government, school authorities, community leaders and parents should ensure that adequate security measures be put in place to curtail the menace of insecurity in order to provide secured-enabling learning environments for the successful implementation and attainment of appropriate literacy and numeracy for human capital development in the state; and
- 2) that the Katsina State Government should continue to provide free and compulsory education to all children in the State through provision of scholarship for continuous education to all other dropped out and pupils' access to education in IDPs, this will enhance their continuous schooling.

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INNOVATION IN ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY: A PANACEA FOR ECONOMIC DIVERSIFICATION IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The emergence of a great nation as an economic power depends on her level of economic development which could be anchored on economic diversification. Economic diversification ushers in a vibrant economic stability, transformation and overall economic turn-around of any nation. Innovations in environmental Science and Technology have evolved to aid and stimulate economic development and diversification. Any nation that wishes to develop and drive its economy scientifically and technologically must adopt and adapt innovations that will rapidly change the structure and framework of the existing economic mechanisms put in place (Okonkwo, 2015). This paper is phrased and articulated to showcase the impact of application of modern innovations in Environmental Science and Technology on economic development and diversification in Nigeria and how it can be aligned to accelerate Nigeria's economic development and diversification. It highlights various innovations used to move the economy positively. It examines challenges facing the nation's economic development and diversification. It concludes by recommending remedial and palliative measures aimed at surmounting these challenges for accelerated economic development and diversification.

Key Words: Economic power, Economic diversification, Economic development and Innovation

Introduction

The innovations infused into environmental science and technology related courses have considerably impacted positively in the nation's economic development and diversification. There is no doubt to believing that the modern technological innovations which have been integrated into the courses taught to students in tertiary institutions have had behavioural and attitudinal change in their skills acquisition. The National Economic Empowerment and Developmental Strategy (NEEDS) of Nigeria

recognized technological innovations in environmental science and technological based courses as tools that can trigger off diversification of a nation's bid to diversify her economy National Planning Commission (NPC, 2004) observed that through skills acquisition, youths' unemployment could be a thing of the past in that graduates turned out every year with the right skills and value could establish small scale enterprises (SMEs) and run them. Collective individual contributions in an economy point at economic diversification (Okonkwo, 2015).

Nigeria's economy has been characterised as mono economy due to her dependency on oil. The discovery of abundant petroleum resources in our continental shelf which was meant to be a blessing suddenly became a curse. Nigeria was afflicted with "Dutch disease". Given the oil boom, Nigeria witnessed structural changes in virtually all facets of her economy as a result of development and export of oil. The effect of this development was that Nigeria gradually jettisoned other sectors of the economy that were equally generating incomes that together increased Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and per capital income of individuals (Okenkwo, 2004 and Onwumere, 1990). The recent economic malaise Nigeria found itself has shown clearly that an economy based only on oil (petroleum resources) at the expense of other sectors has made Nigerian economy mono-economy which could be unstable. The fluctuations of oil price are liable to be violent, giving rise to unpredictable change in the size of the national income from year to year and to the over-present menace of large-scale unemployment (Okoro and Ibaim, 2015). However, diversification of this economy has become a topical issue of national importance. Government has shown a great concern to this and has made various efforts to diversify the nation's economy. Therefore, this paper looks at the impact that the scientific and technological innovations incorporated into environmental science and technological based courses could have on the nation's economy development and diversification.

The Concept of Diversification

The portfolio theory of investment portfolio by Harry Markowitz in 1959 clearly defined the scenario of economy diversification. Markowitz Likened it as a situation where eggs are put in one basket, there is the possibility of having the eggs getting broken if the basket containing all the eggs drops hard on the floor but argued that if the eggs were spread all the eggs would not have been broken.

The same scenario applies to a macro-economic system involving sectors of the economy vis-a-vis.

- Cultural and tourism sector
- Agricultural sector
- Transport sector
- Industrial sector
- Manufacturing sector
- Engineering sector
- Music and entertainment
- Construction sector
- Building sector
- Mining sector, etc.

According to Gregory (1926) and Okonkwo (2014), economic diversification becomes effective and realistic when all the sectors in the economy are stimulated and all the operators and individuals contributing in one way or the other for economic growth, transformation and sustainability. The distortion of the economy created so that one sector is given attention to perform optimally at the detriment of other sectors brings about economic monopoly” which brings about mono economy (Buefon, 1970).

Nations today must develop, maintain and exploit technology from an international view point. Worldwide science and technology (S&T Commitments are now so great that no country – not even the United States can internally develop all the technology it needs for all its purposes. integration and incorporation of scientifically and technological innovations into the environmental science and technological related courses would enhance the diversification of any nation’s economy.

The Concept of Innovation

The idea of development in environmental science and technology education or its curriculum is closely related to the concept of innovation. This is so because one purpose of environmental science and technology curriculum is to improve entrepreneurial skills acquisition. For any innovation to succeed, it has to be systematically executed. To Unrub and Alexander (1974), and Okoro and Ibiam (2014) innovation is defined as the introduction of a novel factor perceived as new by a given society supported by a driving force and implemented as a practical advance that deviates from established or traditional forms. Reinforcing the view, Chauham (1979) noted that to innovate is to create something new, which clearly deviates from the traditional practices, which have been followed for a long time to impart education at all levels. Here, both innovation and transformation can simultaneously be used in any situation but transformation seeks to improve an existing concept unlike innovation that creates something new. Miles (1964) looked at innovation as a deliberate, novel, specific change which is thought to be more efficacious in accomplishing the goals of a system. To Morris (1976), innovation is merely something introduced which is new and different. Innovation is a creative selection, organizing and utilization of human and material resources in new and unique ways which result in the attainment of a highest level of achievement for the defined goals objectives. Print (1995) saw innovation as a technology, which improves educational outcomes, improves working relationships or processes within the school system or reduces the cost of education without significantly reducing the quality and quantity of desired ones, a departure from the status quo, but adds the dimension of cost benefits.

Generally speaking, an innovation seeks to transform or alter a condition of practice, which is known to be somewhat deficient and to introduce something better, that accommodates the identified deficiency. The driving force for an innovation is the need for improved conditions, and an innovation is sustained as long as this driving force remains potent. Innovation is not an “accident” affair but a deliberate, well-conceived undertaking with a definite purpose, which is beneficial to the society. It may involve more efficient utilization of human and material resources as well as novel techniques in any practices. The ultimate end of this, is improvement in level of achievement of the goal of innovation. In addition, a worthwhile innovation should

improve the quality of existing practice while at the same time reducing costs. The process of innovation is demonstrated diagrammatically below:

Courses that make-up Environmental Science and Technology

Environmental Science and Technology courses are basically concerned with the management of the physical environment. Graduates of environmental sciences and technology have their respective areas of training and specialization where their professional services are needed. The major disciplines in Environmental Sciences and Technology are Estate Management, Surveying and Geo-informatics, Architecture, Urban and Regional Planning, Quantity Surveying and Building (Hemuka 2015; Chima and Kalu, 2010). Between 1960 and the mid-1970s there were, only about six tertiary institutions in Nigeria training students in Environmental studies disciplines.

These premier institutions included University of Nigeria, Nsukka, University of Ife now Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile Ife, Kaduna Polytechnic and Yaba college of Technology. As the nation's youths population continued to grow, the number of tertiary institutions in the country also increased and today there are no fewer than fifty tertiary institutions in Nigeria including Abia State University, Abia State polytechnic, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana Afikpo training students and inculcating in them the relevant skills and knowledge needed for establishment of small scale enterprises which also promote diversification of economic system in Nigeria.

- **Estate Management and Valuation:** This is an academic discipline that deals with management and valuation of all forms of interest in land and buildings. The programme is designed to prepare students for professional practice in valuation, land management, land use planning and development, property and faculty management, real estate taxation and rating project management, feasibility and viability appraisals, estate agency, land acquisition and compensation (Nemuka, 2010, Egbenda, 2012 and Elekwachi, Udobi and Okoro, 2016).
- **Surveying and Geo-Informatics:** This is an academic discipline in environmental science and technology with accurate measurement of land to establish the boundaries, area and topography. The programme is designed to prepare students for professional practice in cadastral surveys which are surveys carried out for legal purposes such as needs survey plans showing defining legal property boundaries and size, topographical surveys which establishes the position and shape of natural and man-made features over a given area, geodetic surveys which are high accuracy surveys which are concerned with the curvature of the earth or the position fixing of control points for use in carrying our surveys of a lower accuracy, Engineering surveys (including building surveys) which are surveys carried out in connection with the construction of particular engineering works such as roads, railways, dams, reservoirs, sewage works, drainage,

building, pipelines, power lines etc. hydrographic surveys which is fix the position of the survey vessel to determine the depth of water and investigate the nature of sea bed used in design, construction and maintenance of herbours, inland water routes, offshore gas and oil related construction projects, sea defenses, pollution control and scientific studies of the ocean and military surveys usually out for defense purposes (Clancy, 1981 Onifade and Olafido, 2007). Graduates in these disciplines can render services in the following areas cadastral surveys, preparation of private lay out plans, sell of landed properties and processing of statutory and customary rights of occupancy certificates and general real estate consultancy.

- **Architecture:** Architecture as an academic discipline in environmental studies is concerned with the planning, design and construction of buildings and other physical structures to provide shelter and also beautify the physical environment. The programme is designed to train students for professional practice in the planning, and design of all structures. The young graduates may establish their own individual firms or enterprises and run them. By so doing, economy is being diversified. They can render professional services in the following domains – building design and construction to private individuals who need such services, general real estate consultancy, processing of survey and lay out ideas, preparation of cost estimates of simple constr4uction works etc.
- **Quantity Surveying:** This discipline deals with the management of construction project cost. The programme is designed to prepare students for professional practice in project cost estimation which is the cost of labour and materials required in the execution of various items of works in a project from the inception to the end of the project. Some of the graduates turned out may desire to be self employed by opening up their own firms and run them. The services rendered include building project management, building construction estimation and preparation of bills of quantities etc.
- **Building technology:** This discipline is concerned with the training of students in all matters relating to construction of buildings including the administration and control of contracts, building laws and regulations. The programme is designed to prepare students for professional practice in building construction and management of construction project. Graduates who may not secure employment may wish to practice and render such professional services as building construction, structural survey, building maintenance, building project management/supervision, drawing of simple plans, processing of building plans, cost estimation of simple construction works. Etc.
- **Planning:** This is designed as an academic discipline to deal with both space allocation (allocating adequate space for each of the various activities to be performed in an area) and location (evolving) a land pattern which makes all human activities in an area (Egolum, 2002; Anwa and Kenneth, 2013). Graduates who are not employed by government or private employees may be self-employed providing such professional services as layout design, building design and construction, environmental assessment analysis (EAA) services, processing of building plans etc.

However, it should be noted significantly that most of the graduates produced from our tertiary institutions come out without government jobs because of already saturated labour market. They establish their small and medium scale enterprises, manage and run them having acquired the relevant skills and knowledge. All these people operate in different ways offering professional services to the public in various dimensions thereby diversifying the nation's economy in other words, their individual contributions collectively have positive impact on the overall development and growth of the nation's economy.

Innovational Components that Accelerate Economic Diversification.

Recall that in our earlier observation, we stated that innovation connotes creating something new which deviates from the traditional way of practice (Chauham, 1979). A lot of innovations have been adopted and used in environmental science and technology disciplines to aid and facilitate economic development and diversification. These innovations come under the following areas:

- Development of functional entrepreneurial education
- Information and computer technology (ICT).
- Geographic Information System (GIS)
- Improved Education curriculum
- Improved man-power development
- Transfer of Technology and diffusion
- Policy issues etc.

(a) Development of Functional Entrepreneurial Education

All the courses offered in the faculty /school of Environmental Science and Technology are anchored and powered by skills acquisition which is driven by entrepreneurial education. Entrepreneurship is the bedrock of economic diversification, growth and development throughout the world. Entrepreneurial spirit among citizens is a very important factor in the growth and development of all countries (Ogar and Okenjom, 2015). Through entrepreneurial knowledge, individuals become aware of the opportunities that exist to empower themselves, develop ideas, and take personal responsibilities and initiative. These innovational technologies offered by the searching/learning of entrepreneurship education reduces the problem of youths' unemployment through the establishment of new enterprises and taking over of existing ones. By this, entrepreneurs showcase and utilize those competences, skills and knowledge they have acquired via entrepreneurship education. This becomes a stimulant to economic diversification and development in our country (Onuoha, 2007 and Isidore, 2013).

- #### **(b) Innovations via Information, Computer/communication Technology (ICT)**
- ICT is a veritable tool through which students in environmental science and technology acquire special innovations to function effectively. Formally, business was handled manually but the emergence of ICT has made it possible for business to be simplified and made easier. The innovation has made the whole world a global village. Information can be accessed at any point in time within seconds. Egboh (2009) observed that there is a positive correlation and link between ICT and economic diversification and sees it as a key element in

the industrial, commercial, agricultural etc developments of nation of the world especially the developing countries. No enterprise can grow without the application of ICT born out of creativity and innovation (Ikeme, 2007). Students in the school/faculty of environmental sciences and technology are taught how to effectively apply and adopt the ICT technologies in the day-to-day operations so as to be able to function well. They would now transfer the skills, knowledge and values form ICT technologies into their enterprises and run them well (Okonkwo, 2015).

(c) **Geographic Information System (GNS)**

This new innovation GIS is a system which deals with information related to the partial distribution of features on the earth's surface. The GIS is designed to effectively capture, store, update, manipulate, retrieve, analyze and display all forms of geographically referenced (Ogbonna, 2012, USCS, 2005 and ESRI, 1991). Hearnshaw and Unwin (1994) see GIS as one of the recent technological innovations that evolved in connection with the analysis of spatial data and information which in all its ramifications help to take proactive and reliable decisions on land matters and issues. They are also of the opinion that since environmental science and technology involves land and geographical location etc., students must be able to adopt and apply GIS effectively.

Major Areas of GIS Applications include the following:

1. Street Network-based
 - Address matching – finding locations given street addresses
 - Vehicle routing and scheduling
 - Location analysis, site selection
 - Development of evacuation plans
2. Natural Resource – Based
 - Management of wild and service rulers, recreation resources, flood plains, wet land, agricultural lands, acquitters, forest, wild life
 - Environmental Impact Analysis (EIA)
 - Hazardous or toxic facility setting
 - Ground water modeling and contamination tracking
 - Wildlife habit analysis, migration routes planning
3. Land parcel – based
 - Zoning, subdivision plan view
 - Land acquisition
 - Environmental impact statement
 - Maintenance of ownership
4. Facilities Management
 - Locating underground pipes, cables
 - Balancing leads in electrical networks
 - Planning facility maintenance
 - Tracking energy use

(d) **Innovations in Educational Curriculum**

Innovations into the curricula of various disciplines in the environmental science and technology have been re-structured to meet with the current trends of science

and technology. The dynamism and flexibility of the current curricula has given way for new and relevant courses to be introduced to replace those courses that are repugnant to the development of entrepreneurial skills for self-reliance (UNESCO, 2008). The essence of structuring school curriculum or curricula is to give room for skills acquisition which in turn facilitate development of small and medium scale enterprises upon which economic diversification is anchored.

(e) Improved Man-Power Development

Man-power development refers to the introduction of those innovations required for upliftment of economic diversification and training and re-training personnel who can internalize these innovations and be able to transfer the skills learnt or inculcate them into students. It becomes therefore imperative that Nigerian Government train and re-train her citizens massively in technology and makes technology-and-innovation a Nigeria way of life by creating Nigeria with a scientific mind, an engineering heart and technological soul (Momah, 2019).

(f) Transfer of Technology

Economic diversification and development of any country is driven by technology. The transfer and diffusion of technology becomes essentially important for any country that wishes to develop and diversify her economy. However, in the current dispensation, technological transfer is a complicated process involving a matrix of cultural, socio-economic, environmental intellectual, infrastructural, political and other related factors. A country can actually transfer technologies across national borders and into the technological base of another country. Most developing countries import her innovational technologies from developed countries of the world. However, imported innovational technologies into Nigerian educational system has had a boost in reading and learning environment. Consequently, Nigerian economy has been stimulated hence economic diversification (Dunning 1973, Broack & Hormats, 1990)

(g) Policy Issues

Positive governmental policies that are fundamental to the development of economic growth, stability and diversification are mostly centred around what constitute the key innovational pillars namely:

- Human capital development
- Innovation support structures
- Technology Receptor Programme
- Science, Technology and Innovation System
- Research and Development Intensity (R & D Intensity)
- Strategic Linkages
- Intellectual Property System
- Political Leadership and
- Entrepreneurialism

If all these key elements mentioned above could be articulated rightly, the economy of a national would drive in a positive direction creating room for all round economic development and diversification (Romer, 1992).

Challenges Facing Economic Diversification in Nigeria

Diversification of economic activities in Nigeria is affected by the following but not limited to these factors:

- Over dependency on Petroleum Resources (oil): Nigerians economy was described as mono economy because of its dependence on oil. Before the oil boom of 70s, Nigeria's economic activities were spread on agriculture, mining, transportation etc. but during the oil boom, attention was drawn to oil alone creating no diversified economy.
- Lack of adequate technologies to support economic diversification
- Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has not been optimally developed to bring about the required economic diversification.
- The individual enterprises have been facing financial challenges to run their business ventures
- Low level of man-power development to drive the economy retards economic diversification
- Lack of functional entrepreneurship education to create room for skills acquisition, that will empower our teaming graduates to run and manage their small and medium scale enterprises.
- Inability to bring about creativity and innovation which will be applied and adopted into business enterprises.
- Cultural barrier that is rigid to introduce new innovations could affect a nation's bid to diversify her economy
- Lack of systematic planning and monitoring
- Non-availability of infrastructure and equipment required for effective teaching-learning of entrepreneurship Education in our tertiary institutions of higher learning.
- Unfriendly business environment. Economic reality of a nation is the function of the role of investment both public and private sectors. But if the business environment is unfriendly, investors will withhold their money meant for investment. Thus, economic diversification will not take place.

Conclusion

Growth and economic diversification cannot be possible without additional creativity and innovation, business in small and medium scale enterprises. The nature and importance of entrepreneurship in developing and transferring technology and positively impacting an economy is therefore an area of importance to the society. To create something new (innovation) and value to both the organization and the market place takes a technical individual who is willing to assume the social, psychological and financial risk involved and achieve the resulting rewards. Therefore, our students should be encouraged to be creative and innovative and transfer such knowledge in their day-to-day operations. As soon as this is done, and achieved, collective and aggregate results will reflect positively on the economy hence economic diversification and development.

Recommendations

In view of the fact that introduction of innovative ideas into the students' learning process can tremendously bring out establishment of small and medium scale enterprise

which will usher in economic development and diversification. The following recommendations are proffered as remedial and palliative measures:

1. Re-structuring of school curricula: To be able to embrace the current trends in educational innovations, the school curriculum should be restructured. This done, will give way for possible innovation that will bring about positive changes in the economy.
2. Orientation of society, there is the need for attitudinal change in value orientation from job seekers to job creators thereby making entrepreneurship education to have significant promotional content to stimulate and sustain interest of our youth and society at large.
3. There should be an effective medium for technological transfer whereby students in the tertiary institutions of higher learning will be able to benefit from such scheme such will be utilized for effective development of small and medium scale enterprise.
4. There should be ICT centres in all tertiary institutions where students can access without restrictions
5. Provision of instructional and equipment such as information facilities, power, water supply, transportation, roads, etc. is recommended.
6. Students should be provided with good studios, labs, classrooms and well-equipped library for effective teaching and learning environments.
7. Creativity and innovations should be encouraged and promoted.
8. Friendly business environment ought to be created to enable investors invest in the country without fear of losing their monies.
9. Government should formulate policies that will enable young school leavers (graduates) opt to establish and run their enterprises
10. Rigid cultural barrier should be discouraged so that new innovation will be allowed to thrive.

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USE OF ELECTRONIC JOURNAL AND PRINCIPALS' MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN UYO LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated the extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' management effectiveness in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area. Three research questions were raised with corresponding hypotheses. The study adopted ex post facto research design. The population of all the principals and teachers (13 principals and 918 teachers) in the 13 public secondary schools in the study area were used. Sample of 145 were selected using proportionate random sampling technique. Researchers' designed questionnaire was utilized for the collection of data. Data collected were analysed using simple linear regression. The results show that the use of e-journal predicts principals' management effectiveness in the area of organization of school ground skills, principals' staff coordination skills, and principals' school policy planning was very low at .08%, .05%, and .08% and insignificant. On the basis of these results, the study recommends that Akwa Ibom State Government should urgently provide the schools with basic ICT support amenities such as computers, steady supply of electricity and other web- support resources to enhance zeal for the utilization of e-journals in the management of schools effectively. Also, Akwa Ibom State Government and corporate individuals should routinely train the teachers and principals on the uses and management of ICT facilities to improve their research and teaching skills for a better school effectiveness.

Key Words: E-journal, principal management effectiveness, school ground skills, principals' staff coordination skills, and principals' school policy planning

Introduction

The place of secondary school education cannot be underestimated. It serves as a link that coordinates the morals, values, and skills learnt in the primary schools while preparing the child for the desired attainment in the tertiary education. It is ascribed as a vital level of education that plays a pertinent role in raising a generation of people who can think for themselves, respect the views and feelings of others, respect the dignity of

labour and appreciate those values specified under our national aims, while living as good citizens (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). The objective of secondary education requires not just funds and infrastructural resources for its attainment but a proficient and effectiveness in the management of these school resources. Hence, requires the principal management effectiveness.

Basically, the management of academic and administrative affairs of schools traditionally falls within the purview of the principals. Unerringly, formal education in Nigeria is rapidly changing and technically tailored towards meeting certain set goals, such as “Education for All” (Nwaogu, 2013). The requirement of these various goals from the school principals are centred on the advancement of teaching and learning through the implementation of performance-based management, which is led by a management team, with the principal, at the fulcrum. Given this onerous task, the principal, as a matter of fact, must understand the role of school managers to effectively manage not only staff but the facilities to meet the overall objectives of the school system. Thus, the ability of the principal to effectively handle these responsibilities determines the extent of principals’ management effectiveness.

Fundamentally, management effectiveness is a measure of the success in school administration. A manager is one who is able to achieve the educational objectives of the school which include: high level of academic achievement both within and in public examination, winning of trophies in inter-schools’ competition, in games, sports, drama, debate and quiz; organization of conferences, workshops or seminars for teachers, proper management of schools’ funds and school facilities, as well as provision of teaching materials.

Management effectiveness is also the positive response to administrative efforts and actions with the intention to accomplish stated goals. The administrative performance in decision making, delegation of duties to subordinates, setting good examples, motivating the teachers and students alike in an effort to create a conducive working environment seem to enhance subordinate performance for school success. The administrative effectiveness of secondary school principals had been observed by Adegun in Okiki (2012), as a factor inhibiting attainment of goals in secondary schools.

The achievement of education management effectiveness in secondary schools by the principals is a function of accessing quality information that can sustain the managerial fulcrum and serve as peddle for propelling innovations. Similarly, principals need viable information to tackle the complexities of school system (Effiong, 2013). Thus, these underscore the essentiality of library in the management effectiveness of the principals.

The utilization of library unarguably could serve as a promoter of proficiency for an effective school system. This is given the fact that library facilities serve as content and knowledge repositories and house of all the educational information resources. Considering the importance of library however, Lance, Rodney and Hamilton-Pennell in Riley, Varon, and Varon (2017) asserted that students in schools with good library resources and full-time libraries performed at high levels than students in schools with inimical or no library resources. The implication herewith is that properly managed and maintained library facilities can promote students’ educational achievement vis-à-vis principal management effectiveness. Sadly, and very disappointing is the fact that most of the secondary schools in Nigeria that have it, the facilities are inadequate, poorly

equipped or poorly managed. However, the invention of information technology has subtle these lapses observed by way of electronic journals.

Electronic journals have become essential tools for research, teaching and learning. Msagati (2014) reiterated that e-journal provide access to timely, high quality and scientific information to scholars and researchers with a view to keepi+ng abreast with new discoveries and development. It is basically referred to as electronic publishing, serials and periodicals. It advantages ranges from providing access to wide ranges of viable resources; allows wide search options; save physical space; does not require human resources for shelving and rectification (Effiong, 2013). Nevertheless, in spite of the potentials of e-journals, most of the scholars and researchers do not fully utilize them (Ajegbomogun (2007) in Riley et al., 2017). Okolo and Megara (2008) highlighted major obstacles to the underutilization in the users of electronic journals in higher learning institution as being the lack of awareness about resources. In a similar study in Obafemi Awolowo University, Oyedapo and Ojo (2013) outlined limited searching skills, lack of accessibility to computers connected to internet, low internet bandwidth and unrealizable supply of power as militating against the use of e-journals. Going by the highlighted potentials and limitations of e-journal in educational advancement in Nigeria, close review has shown that no study was found conducted on the use of e-journals and principal management effectiveness in secondary schools, thus, this created a gap this study intends to fill.

Statement of the Problem

The essence of secondary school education in Akwa Ibom State seems unattainable because of alarming rate of failure in examinations, poor academic achievement, and high evident of teachers' lackadaisical attitude towards lesson note preparation, class management and class discipline. These are sad expressions of principal poor management skills, thus prompted the contemplation of the researcher on whether the principals do not have access or are out-rightly unaware of the potentials of e-journal for the self-empowerment in management approaches. It is therefore on this note that the researchers deem it necessary to examine the extent of utilization of e-journals in the improvement of principals' management effectiveness in Secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' organization of school ground?
2. What is the extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals staff coordination?
3. What is the extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predict principals' school policy planning?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study

1. The extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' organization of school ground is not significant.

2. The extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals' staff coordination is not significant.
3. The extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals' school policy planning is not significant.

Significance of the Study

The findings of the study would generate viable data on the extent to which principals utilize e-journals for effective management of schools. This would enlighten the principals on the potentials of electronic journals and in a run long promotes the efficiency in the management and achievement of the ideals of secondary education on the students.

Methodology

Design of the Study

The study employed ex-post facto research design. This design was utilized because the fact about the issue under consideration had occurred or is already in existence without the influence, or alteration, or manipulation of the researcher. Ndiyo (2005) inferred that ex-post facto design research is research that is undertaken after the event has taken place and the data are already in existence. The data was extracted directly from the respondents using designed research instrument.

Area of the Study

The study was conducted in Uyo Local Government Area. Uyo Local Government Area is one of the local government areas in Akwa Ibom State. The area has boundary with Uruan, Ibiono Ibom, Itu, Ibesikpo Asutan and Nsit Ibom Local Government Areas. Uyo local government area hosts the seat of power in the State and has experienced remarkable growth in the enrolment of students into secondary schools. Basically, the Local government has total of thirteen (13) public secondary schools and 22 primary schools (Source: Ministry of Education). The choice of the area for the study emanated from its proximity to the researcher and the urbanization characteristics such as availability of electricity and accessibility to network which are essential factor required for the accessibility to e-journals.

Population of the Study

The population of the consist all the 13 principals and 918 teachers in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government area (Source: Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Education, 2019).

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Sample of 145 consisting of 13 principals and 132 teachers were used for the study. This sample was derived from the population using proportionate random sampling technique for teachers while census was used for the principals (because of the number).

Instrument for Data Collection

Researchers’ designed questionnaire was utilized for the collection of data. This instrument was tagged “Use of E-Journal and Principal Management Effectiveness Questionnaire (UEPMQ)”. This instrument was built on four-point Likert modified scale of very high extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), and Very Low Extent (VLE). The coding interpretation were as follows: VHE (4), HE (3), LE (2) and VLE (1).

Instrument Administration

The instrument was administered first by intimating the principals through written letter for permission to conduct the study on them (Principals and the Teachers). Afterwards, the respondents were briefed on the essence and significance of the study. The administration was assisted by the help of researcher’s ad-hoc assistants who were trained on the rudimentary of effective instrument administration. At the end of the administration, the return rate of 95.2 percent was recorded, giving total valid respondents of 138.

Method of Data Analysis

Data collated were analysed using simple linear regression according to the research questions raised.

Data Analyses and Discussion of Findings

The data analysed were presented based on the research question raised as follows:

Data Analysis

Research Question 1: What is the extent to which utilization of e-journal predict principals’ organization of school ground skills?

Table 1: The extent utilization of e-journal predicts principals’ organization of school ground skills.

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.090 ^a	.008	-.984	.41821

a. Predictors: (Constant), Utilisation of e-journals by the principals

The result in Table 1 shows the R-Square (coefficient of determination) value of 0.008 which implies that about 0.8 percent of the total variation in the organization of school ground is explained by principal utilization of e-journals. This shows that the extent to which principals’ utilization of e-journals in secondary schools predicts principals’ organization of school grounds skills is very low.

Research Question 2: What is the extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predict principals’ staff coordination skills?

Table 2: The extent utilization of e-journal predicts principals' staff coordination.

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.222 ^a	.049	-.092	.42934

a. Predictors: (Constant), Utilization of e-journal by the principals

The result gives the R-square value 0.049 implying that about 5% of the total variable in principals' staff coordination is account for by the utilization of e-journal. This implies that the extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' staff coordination skills in secondary schools is low.

Research Question 3: What is the extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predict principals' school policy planning?

Table 3: The extent utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals school policy planning

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.088 ^a	.008	-.985	.41539

a. Predictors: (Constant), Utilisation of e-journals by the principals

R-Square value of 0.008 indicates that 0.8 percent of the total variation in principals' school policy planning is explained by utilization of e-journals by the principals. This implies that the extent of utilization of e-journals by the principals has a very low contribution to the principals' school policy skills in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: The extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' organization of school ground is not significant.

Table 4: The Regression analysis on the use of e-journal as it relates with the principal organization of school ground (N=145).

Variables	Sources of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-cal.	Fcrit.	Decision at P<.05
Principal Organ. of School Ground	Regression	20.41	1	11.84	3.10	3.51	*Not Significant
Use of e-journal.	Residual		144	1.811			
	Total	6.31	145				
		26.71					

Table 4 indicates that the calculated F-value of 3.10 is less than the critical F-value of 3.51 at 0.05 level of significance with 1 and 144 degree of freedom. This result shows that null hypothesis is accepted, thus, the extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' organization of school ground is not significant.

Hypothesis 2: The extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals' staff coordination is not significant.

Table 5: The Regression analysis on the extent of utilization of e-journal by the principal and principals staff coordination (N=145).

Variables	Sources of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-cal.	Fcrit.	Decision at P<.05
Principal Staff Coordinating skill Use of e-journal	Regression	20.41	1	5.42	2.14	3.51	*Not Significant
	Residual		144	1.08			
	Total	2.33	145				
		22.74					

Table 5 reveals that the calculated F-value of 2.14 is less than the critical F-value of 3.51 at 0.05 level of significance with 1 and 144 degree of freedom. This result shows that null hypothesis is accepted, thus, the extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals' staff coordination is not significant.

Hypothesis 3: The extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals' schools policy planning is not significant.

Table 6: The Regression analysis on the extent of utilization of e-journal by the principal and principals' school policy planning (N=145).

Variables	Sources of variation	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F-cal.	F-crit.	Decision at P<.05
Principals' School policy planning Use of e-journal	Regression	18.21	1	8.04	2.10	3.51	*Not Significant
	Residual		144	1.81			
	Total	9.13	145				
		27.34					

Table 6 reveals that the calculated F-value of 2.10 is less than the critical F-value of 2.85 at 0.05 level of significance with 1 and 144 degree of freedom. This result shows that null hypothesis is accepted, thus, the extent to which utilization of e-journal by the principal predicts principals' school policy planning is not significant.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of the findings was done according to the analysed research questions thus:

Utilization of E-journals and Principals' Organization of School Grounds Skills

The results of the analysis in Table 1 shows that the extent to which principals' utilization of e-journals in secondary schools predicts principals' organization of school grounds skills is very low. This is a sad indication that most of the secondary school principals do not use e-journals in the organization of school grounds. In other words, their inability to adopt current school grounds that can promote aesthetic atmosphere might be related to the low extent to which they utilize the e-journals innovation. This level of usage aligns with the position of Ajegomogun (2007) that while e-journal have become essential tools for learning, teaching and researching the one I have is a long 0, most of the scholars and researchers are not fully utilizing them.

Utilization of E-journals and Principals Staff Coordination Skills

The result of analysis in Table 2 implies that the extent to which utilization of e-journal predicts principals' staff coordination skills in secondary schools is low. This is indicated by the 5 percent variation in principal staff coordination skill. The implication is that principals' non-utilisation of e-journals could be related to the low extent staff organization skill. This finding is supported by the study carried out by Ajegomogun (2007) in Riley *et al.*, (2017) on the extent of usage of e-journal in tertiary institution in Southwest Nigeria which found that while e-journal have become essential tools for learning, teaching and research, most of the scholars and researchers are not fully utilizing them.

Utilization of E-journals and Principals School Policy Planning

The results of the findings in Table 3 indicate that the extent of utilization of e-journals by the principals has a very low contribution to the principals' school policy skills in public secondary schools in Uyo Local Government Area at 0.8 percent. This is an indication that principals do not consult and utilize e-journal greatly for school policy planning skill. The results align with the assertion of Ajegomogun (2007) in Riley *et al.*, (2017) while e-journal have become essential tools for learning, teaching and research, most of the scholars and researchers are not fully utilizing them.

Conclusion

In the light of the results of the analyses obtained, it could be concluded that the extent to which the principals use e-journals for organization of schools ground, coordination of staff and school policy planning is very low, implying that the principals' management effectiveness is very low given the fact that most of them do not utilize e-journal in the management of their schools.

Recommendations

It is against this backdrop that the study recommended the following:

1. Akwa Ibom State Government should urgently provide the schools with basic ICT support amenities such as computers, steady supply of electricity and other web- support resources. This will enhance zeal for the utilization of e-journals in the management of schools effectively.

2. The Government and corporate individuals should routinely train the teachers and principals on the uses and management of ICT facilities to improve their research and teaching skills for a better school effectiveness.

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IMPACT OF ICT ON ACQUIRING INDEPENDENT LEARNING SKILLS AMONG SOCIAL STUDIES STUDENTS IN JUNIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KATSINA STATE

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Abstract

This study investigated “Impact of Information and Communication Technology on Acquiring Independent Learning Skills among Social Studies students in Junior Secondary schools in Katsina state”. The objectives of this study amongst others were to investigate the impact of ICT on acquiring independent learning skill among JSS 2 students in Katsina State. Two research questions and hypotheses were drawn from the objectives of the study. Areas related to this study were reviewed. The design of this study was the two-by-two pre-test post-test quasi experimental control group design. The targeted population was one hundred and one thousand, eighty-nine (101, 089) students A simple random sampling technique was adopted to draw three hundred and seventy-eight (378) sampled students. Social Studies Achievement Test (SSAT) made up of forty multiple items drawn from three topics in Social Studies were developed and validated as test instrument for data collection. The two research questions were answered using descriptive statistical techniques like Mean and Standard Deviation while the hypotheses were tested using sample t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The outcome of the study revealed that, the ability to acquire independent learning skills was found to be higher with the use of Computer Assisted Instruction than with the use of conventional method of teaching. One hypothesis was rejected and the other one was retained. The study concluded that students exposed to CAI were found to acquire independent learning skills more than students exposed to conventional method.

Key Words: Impact, ICT, Independent, Learning, Skills, Social Studies, Junior Secondary School

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is one of the most important and widely discussed issues in contemporary education policy. Many educationists agreed that, when properly used, it would improve teaching and learning. According to Poole in Oyenike (2010), lack of computer knowledge is now regarded as the new illiteracy. This has propelled stakeholders to provide schools with computer equipment and qualified personnel essential to produce skilled students that are proficient and

efficient in ICT. There is no doubt that the application of ICT in classroom instruction can facilitate students' learning and comprehension of many disciplines in both developed and developing nations.

One of these disciplines is Social Studies. This discipline (Social Studies) is one of the core subjects in secondary schools that have over the years assumed an important position in the school curriculum. Many scholars perceived it as effective tool for achieving citizenship education in Nigeria. The subject also enables the learners to develop the principle of critical and problem-solving skills that will allow them to address their personal and societal problems that may arise in their future lives. In view of this, the Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria classified it as one of the core subjects in Junior Secondary School curriculum (FRN, 2009). To be more precise, the Federal Ministry of Education identified the following as the overall objectives of Social Studies;

Develop the ability to adapt to changing environment; Become responsible and disciplined individuals capable of and willing to contribute to the development of their societies; Inculcate the right types of values; Have compassion for other people, Appreciate their culture, history and those fundamental factors that make them human; Develop the capability to recognize the many dimensions of being human in different cultural and social contexts; and Develop a sense of solidarity and sharing based on a sense of security in one's own identity. (FRN 2009).

However, in Katsina state, the teaching of the subject is bedevilled with problems that may mar its laudable benefits to the students, teachers and other stake holders. Among the salient ones is non utilization of ICT in teaching the subject at all levels. Many of ICT facilities are not available. Many of the available ones are not functional. To crown it up, many social studies teachers are not ICT literate hence their inability to utilize them in their classroom instruction. The net effect of this could be on the inability of students to acquire independent learning skills. Okebukola (2004), asserted that many secondary schools in Nigeria and Katsina state in particular do not have ICT facilities for classroom teaching. He maintains that computer is not part of classroom instruction in over 90% of public schools in Nigeria. Thus, the chalkboard and textbooks continued to dominate classroom activities in most schools in Katsina state. The achievement and failure of students in Social Studies, aside other variables, strongly depend on the instructional media used (Okebukola 2004). Some of the media used by teachers are monotonous and the students become very passive.

This factor has contributed in no small measure in not acquiring independent learning skills. To corroborate this assertion, the finding of a research carried out in Cross River State by (Okon, 2012) on Teachers' Teaching Behavior and Academic Achievement of Students in Social Studies in secondary schools indicated three consecutive years of students' failure in acquiring independent learning skills. This and many other reasons have necessitated the researcher to carry out this study to examine the effect of ICT on JSS 11 students' ability to acquire independent learning skills, as they are the future leaders of tomorrow. In particular, the cardinal objective of this study is to find out the influence of ICT on JSS students' independent learning skills

Statement of the Problem

Many studies conducted in Nigeria and elsewhere have shown that there were low academic achievements and its attendant consequence of low acquiring independent learning skills among students in such basic skills as literacy, numeracy and life skills due to non-utilization of ICT equipment. This has generated an alarming rate of learning and teaching in Katsina and other states of the federation that does not translate to the production of analytical, critical and engaging products; incompetent and unskilled teachers that do not use active pedagogies, and that the needs of prospective job seekers were not met as the content of education is irrelevant. These problems have necessitated UNESCO in identifying a number of roadmaps for setting ICT usage in educational programs. These, among others include, framework and vision of ICT usage in schools, curriculum, technology and infrastructure, pedagogy and content development, monitoring professional development, and supervision.

Objectives

The objectives of this study were to;

- 1 ascertain whether the use of ICT will enhance independent learning skill acquisition between control and experimental groups in Social Studies;
- 2 find out the impact of the use of Computer Assisted Instruction on the rate of acquiring independent learning skill between female and male students in social studies.

Research Questions

- 1 What difference exists in the independent learning skill acquisition between control and experimental groups in Social Studies?
- 2 What is the impact of ICT on the level of independent learning skill acquisition between male and female students in Social Studies?

Hypotheses

To carry out this study, the following hypotheses are put forward;

- Ho1. There is no significant difference in the independent learning skill acquisition of students between control and experimental groups in Social Studies.
- Ho2. There is no significant difference in the level of independent learning skill acquisition between male and female students in Social Studies.

Review of Related Literature

Based on some researches carried out by scholars on the use of ICTs in Social Science disciplines, of which Social Studies is one, their findings showed that there are direct and indirect effects of ICT application on learning based on teachers and students' attributes. Attwell and Battle (2009), studied the performance of students that have computer at home and those that have at school of approximately 64,300 students in the United States. Their findings suggested that students, who had access to computers at home for educational purposes, have improved scores in Reading and Math.

Sosin (2004), developed a database of 67 sections of introductory economics, enrolling 3,986 students, taught by 30 instructors in 15 institutions in the United States of America during the spring and autumn semesters of 2002. He found significant, but

low, positive impact on students' performance due to ICT use. Nevertheless, the finding showed that some ICT seems to be positively correlated to performance while others do not.

On the role of ICT on independent learning skill, it was reported that students were highly motivated and engaged with the learning tasks (docplayer.net). Van Grinsven and Tillema, (2006); Hinds, (2007); Schunk, (2005); Alan (2004) showed that independent learning improved academic performance; increased motivational and confidence (Van Grinsven and Tillema, 2006; Black,. 2007); the stimulation of lifelong learning (Williams, 2003); allowing students to become more aware of and better able to manage their limitations (Zimmerman, 2002); enabling teachers to provide differentiated tasks for students (Deeson, 2006); and promoting social inclusion by countering alienation (Weekes and Wright, 1998). In addition, Becker (2000) asserted that ICT enhances students' engagement, which invariably augments the amount of time students spend working outside class room instruction.

Research Design

The design for this study is quasi-experimental research design. Population of this research covers JSS 2 students of the state. There are two hundred and thirty-four (234) junior secondary schools and one hundred and one thousand, eighty-nine (101,089) students. Below is the table that shows the distribution of this population based on the eleven educational zones.

Table 1: Distribution of the Research Population According to the Educational Zones

Zones	Schools	Students
Baure	21	5442
Daura	23	5592
Dutsinma	20	6529
Faskari	24	7251
Funtua	23	14593
Kankia	22	5802
Katsina	26	19739
Malumfashi	30	15312
Mani	23	6126
Musawa	13	3398
Rimi	20	7273
Safana	18	4028
Total	263	101,089

Source: (Katsina State Ministry of Education)

Sample

The sample for this research is three hundred and seventy-eight (378) students. To ensure validity of the instrument, experts in the field of Social Studies have assessed its relevance to the research topic, coverage of research questions, appropriateness of language usage and clarity of purpose. Their inputs have been incorporated into the final items.

To ensure that the instrument is reliable, Pearson Product Moment Correlation formula between odd and even scores (split-half) was employed. This yielded a result of 0.87 co-efficient, which is considered as reliable.

Results

Research Question One: What difference exists in the independent learning skill acquisition between control and experimental groups in Social Studies?

Table 2: Difference in Independent Learning Skills Acquisition between control and experimental groups in Social Studies.

Variable	Study Groups	N	Mean	STD	Mean Difference
Skills Acquisition	Control	80	2.4563	.66653	1.20625
	Experimental	80	3.6625	.77040	

The figure showed that those taught with CAI scored a mean of 3.6625 with a corresponding S.D. of .77040 whereas their colleagues in control group scored a mean of 2.456 with a standard deviation of .66653.

Research Question two: What is the impact of ICT on the level independent learning skills acquisition between male and female students in Social Studies?

Table 3: Level of Acquiring Independent Learning Skill between Male and Female Students in Social Studies

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	STD	Mean Difference
Skills Acquisition	Male	30	48.850	9.174	1.167
	Female	30	47.683	8.998	

From the data presented above, it is clear that there is no significant difference in the level of independent learning skills acquisition between male and female students taught Social Studies using ICT.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference in the independent learning skill acquisition between control and experimental groups in Social Studies.

Table 4: Independent t-test on Independent Learning Skills Acquisition between control and experimental groups in Social Studies

Variable	Study Groups	N	Mean	STD	Mean Difference	Df	T computed	T critical	p
Skills Acquisition	Control	80	2.4563	.66653	1.20625	158	2.811	1.96	0.032
	Experimental	80	3.6625	.77040					

P calculated < 0.05, t computed > 1.96 at df 158

The table above revealed that the calculated p value of 0.032 is lower than the 0.05 level of significance and the computed t value of 2.811 is greater than the 1.96 t critical value at df 158. The hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implied that using ICT in classroom instruction more especially in Social Studies enhances students' acquisition of independent learning skills in Katsina State.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in the level of independent learning skills acquisition between male and female in Social Studies.

Table 5: T- Test on the Rate of Acquiring Independent Learning Skills between Male and Female Students in Social Studies

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	STD	Mean Difference	Df	T computed	T critical	P
Skills Acquisition	Male	30	48.850	9.174	4.16	58	1.776	1.96	0.081
	Female	30	47.683	8.998					

P calculated > 0.05, t computed < 1.96 at df 58

The table revealed that there is no significant difference in the level of independent learning skills acquisition between male and female students Social Studies because the calculated p value of 0.081 is slightly higher than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the computed t value of 1.77 is also marginally lower than the 1.96 t critical value at df 58. The hypothesis is therefore retained.

Discussions of Findings

The t-test in Table 4 indicated that there is significant difference in the acquisition of independent learning skills between students in Social Studies using ICT and those taught without ICT. As presented in the table, the p value as calculated (0.032) is lower than the alpha level of significance (0.05) and the computed t value of 2.811 is greater than the 1.96 t critical value. This implied that students who were exposed to the use of the Computer Assisted Instruction were significantly better in acquiring independent learning skill than those in control group. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. In support of this finding, Brothen and Wambach, (2000), reported that Computer assisted instruction encourages a student to take responsibility of his learning, acquire effective study habits, and persist until he has mastered the content.

On the last hypothesis (2), the data presented in Table 5, showed that there is no significant difference in the level of independent learning skills acquisition between male and female students taught Social Studies. This implied that the hypothesis is retained. To corroborate this finding with other studies, Dange (2013) reported that Computer Assisted Instruction as a method of teaching Science enhances both boys and girls equally in developing study habits.

Conclusion

The paper concluded that use of (ICT) facilitated independent learning skills acquisition amongst JS2 students when compared with the conventional mode of instruction. With this development, the spirit of personal study habit among JS 2 students is likely to be inspired. Also, the performance of JS 2 students in the art of acquiring independent learning skill when exposed to CAI method of instruction has no relation with their sex. Male and female compete favorably with one another in pursuit of independent learning skill.

Recommendations

- 1 All schools should be provided with functional ICT digital centers for students use unhindered. This will help Social Studies students to develop ICT independent learning skills to improve their academic performance and equally equip them to meet up with the challenge of online examination currently adopted by some examination bodies like JAMB.
- 2 Teachers of Social Studies should be encouraged to attend orientation, workshops, seminars and conferences where different ICT related courses are discussed and taught by ICT experts.
- 3 Junior Secondary Schools' curriculum of Social Studies should be regularly reviewed to incorporate new ICT Packages and learning guides. This will help Social Studies teachers to develop their skills and competency in instructional delivery. In addition, maintenance culture should be embedded into the school policy to ensure durability of ICT facilities.

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